

D3.2

Initial report on the PoDIUM platform developments

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building
trust and sustainability for CCAM

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Table of contents

Contents

Contributors.....	2
Quality Control.....	2
Version History	3
Legal Disclaimer	3
List of figures.....	6
List of tables.....	10
List of abbreviations and acronyms.....	11
Executive Summary	18
1. Introduction	19
1.1. Project intro.....	19
1.2. Purpose of the deliverable	19
1.3. Intended audience.....	19
1.4. Structure of the document and its relationship to other work packages/deliverables	20
2. Use Case 1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm	21
2.1. Scenario Descriptions	21
2.2. Communication Aspects.....	23
2.3. Connected Entities	30
2.4. Services and Data Exchange	36
2.5. Data Truthfulness	41
3. Use Case 2: PDI for Use-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs	43
3.1. Scenario Descriptions	43
3.2. Communication Aspects.....	46
3.3. Connected Entities	50
3.4. Services and Data Exchange	62
4. Use Case 3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor	75
4.1. Scenario Descriptions	75
4.2. Communication Aspects.....	79
4.3. Connected Entities	85
4.4. Services and Data Exchange	101
5. Use Case 4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance	128

5.1.	Scenario Descriptions	128
5.2.	Communication Aspects.....	134
5.3.	Connected Entities	138
5.4.	Services and Data Exchange	151
5.5.	Trust and Integrity	158
6.	Use Case 5: Risk Management in Highway Tunnel	166
6.1.	Scenario Descriptions	166
6.2.	Communication Aspects.....	177
6.3.	Connected Entities	178
6.4.	Services and Data Exchange	189
7.	Conclusions	198
	References	199

List of figures

Figure 1: UC1 Scenario Description for Scenario 1.....	22
Figure 2: UC1 Scenario Description for Scenario 2.....	23
Figure 3: UC1 Communication View (see also [4])	24
Figure 4: UC1 MEC Connectivity.....	26
Figure 5: FR1 and FR2 realization in the German LL.....	27
Figure 6: UC1 Multi-Connectivity Communication.....	29
Figure 7: Scheduler functions.....	29
Figure 8: UC1 Functional View of the CAV	31
Figure 9: UC1 IT environment view of a CAV	31
Figure 10: UC1 Multi-Connectivity Concept of CAVs	32
Figure 11: UC1 Functional blocks of a connected VRU	33
Figure 12: Smartphone-IT Environment View.....	33
Figure 13: Cooperative Awareness HMI.....	34
Figure 14: UC1 functional components.....	37
Figure 15: UC1 Sequence Diagram	40
Figure 16: Self-assessment of the DT	42
Figure 17: UC2 scenario description diagram - scenario 1 ‘Management of high-priority vehicles’	44
Figure 18: UC2 scenario description diagram - scenario 2 ‘Advanced traffic management based on real-time response’	45
Figure 19: UC2 scenario description diagram - scenario 3 ‘VRUs protection’	46
Figure 20: UC2 Communication view	47
Figure 21: UC2 Edge Computing Architecture.....	49
Figure 22: UC2 and UC3 Functional view of the CAV and CVs	51
Figure 23: UC2 and UC3 Diagram of the operation of perception, positioning and ADF functions for CAV	54
Figure 24: UC2 and UC3 Diagram of the positioning operation for CVs and EV	55
Figure 25: UC2 Diagram of the generation and transmission of CAMs	56
Figure 26: Flow diagram of the reception of DENM from the infrastructure	56
Figure 27: UC2 and UC3 Physical view of the CAV	57
Figure 28: UC2 Physical view of the CVs	57
Figure 29: HMI wireframe for UC2 CAV and CVs.....	58
Figure 30: UC2 Sequence diagram for the VRU application.....	59
Figure 31: IT environment view for VRU devices	59
Figure 32: Camera used for road user detection in UC2.....	60
Figure 33: UC2 Sequence diagram of SPU functional components	61
Figure 34: SPU IT environment view in UC2.....	62

Figure 35: UC2 Platform services 62

Figure 36: Architecture of the Digital Twin used in UC2 64

Figure 37: Road users’ detection and trajectory prediction 65

Figure 38: IT view for UC2 cloud 68

Figure 39: UC2 UML sequence diagram - scenario 1 ‘Management of high priority vehicles’ 70

Figure 40: UC2 UML sequence diagram - scenario 2 ‘Advanced traffic management based on real-time response’ 71

Figure 41: UC2 UML sequence diagram - scenario 3 ‘VRUs protection’ 72

Figure 42: UC3 Scenario Description for scenario 1 - Daily commuting across borders..... 76

Figure 43: UC3 Scenario Description for scenario 2 - Safety incidents across borders..... 78

Figure 44: UC3 Communication view 79

Figure 45: Traffic camera models used in UC3: left- *AXIS Q6225-LE PTZ*; right- *AXIS P1467-LE* 81

Figure 46: Edge clouds in a UC3 cross-border scenario 83

Figure 47: Diagram of the generation and transmission of CAMs and CPMs 86

Figure 48: Diagram of the generation of a DENM message from the UC3 CAV. 87

Figure 49: Diagram of the reception of CPM at vehicle level..... 87

Figure 50: Flow diagram of the reception of DENM, IVIM and MCM from the infrastructure..... 88

Figure 51: HMI wireframe for UC3 CV..... 89

Figure 52: VRU's functional view diagram..... 89

Figure 53: Passenger app functional view..... 92

Figure 54: Sequence of VAM transmission by the VRU 93

Figure 55: Sequence of a CPM reception by the VRU 93

Figure 56: High collision risk detected by the MEC..... 94

Figure 57: High collision risk detected by the VRU 94

Figure 58: Passenger app Log in and booking sequence diagram 95

Figure 59: Passenger App travel sequence diagram 96

Figure 60: Safety App HMI showing nearby vehicles and "No Risk" sign..... 97

Figure 61: RSU's functional view diagram 98

Figure 62: Message forwarding by the RSU between vehicles and the MEC 100

Figure 63: RSU used in UC3. Models: Commsignia ITS-RS4 (left) and Cohda Wireless MK6 (right) ... 100

Figure 64: Detailed functional view diagram 102

Figure 65: Snippet of the Functional view depicting the functional modules of the Local TMC 106

Figure 66: Snippet of Functional view depicting the functional components of the Global TMC 107

Figure 67: Mobility HUB internal functional view 108

Figure 68: 3GPP architecture model where it establishes the VAE layer..... 110

Figure 69: Simulated scenario 113

Figure 70: NAR of the different scenarios. 114

Figure 71: PE of the different scenarios. 114

Figure 72: Complete architecture of ENIDE-MILLA Cloud services 116

Figure 73: UC3 platform environment view (Edge & Cloud), ideal deployment 116

Figure 74: UC3 platform environment view (Edge & Cloud), LL demo deployment..... 117

Figure 75: Flow diagram of CAM and CPM messages dissemination from vehicles to the infrastructure for UC3..... 119

Figure 76: Flow diagram of strategies dissemination for UC3 120

Figure 77: Flow diagram of the incidents for UC3..... 121

Figure 78: CPM generation flow diagram 122

Figure 79: Collision risk calculation and alarm propagation flow diagram 123

Figure 80: Passenger data flow check in and use shuttle 124

Figure 81: Contents of the Perceived Object field included in the CPM and standardized in the common data dictionary by ETSI (TS 102 894-2)..... 126

Figure 82: UC4 Straight scenario 128

Figure 83: UC4 Activity Diagram for the Straight Scenario 129

Figure 84: UC4 Right turn scenario 130

Figure 85: UC4 Activity diagram for scenario Right Turn 131

Figure 86: UC4 Left turn scenario..... 131

Figure 87: UC4 Activity diagram for scenario Left Turn 133

Figure 88: UC4 Activity Diagram: Trust Scenario 134

Figure 89: UC4 Communication View..... 135

Figure 90: UC4 Telco Node architecture 137

Figure 91: UC4 functional view of the CAV 139

Figure 92: C-ITS message transmission 140

Figure 93: C-ITS message reception 141

Figure 94: CAV Positioning 141

Figure 95: HMI visualization 142

Figure 96: IT Environment View 142

Figure 97: HMI concept view..... 143

Figure 98: functional view Connected VRU..... 144

Figure 99: IT Environment view Connected VRU 145

Figure 100: RSU functionality for UC4..... 146

Figure 101: Access relay sequence..... 147

Figure 102: RSU IT environment view 148

Figure 103: RSU location for UC4 148

Figure 104: C-ITS Sensor Stream flow 150

Figure 105: Functional View UC4 151

Figure 106: UC4 MSC Straight Scenario Description 153

Figure 107: UC4 MSC Right Turn Scenario Description 154

Figure 108: UC4 MSC Left Turn Scenario Description 155

Figure 109: UC4 MSC Scenario Trust 156

Figure 110: Successfully connected TPM 159

Figure 111: Output of the tpm2_pcrread command output 160

Figure 112: Example of IMA measurements 161

Figure 113: High level description of the Secure Boot process..... 162

Figure 114: Successful verification of the boot images during the secure boot procedure 162

Figure 115: Output of the bootsript showing the value of the first 3 PCRs correctly extended 164

Figure 116: Multiple sensor sources contributing to truthfulness..... 165

Figure 117: UC5 Scenario: Road Works Warning – CAV only (note : figure not in scale) 167

Figure 118: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning – CAV only: activity diagram 168

Figure 119: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning – CAV and CV: car follow with C-ACC 169

Figure 120: UC5 Scenario: “cut-in” with C-ACC (at Road Works)..... 169

Figure 121: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning: car follows with C-ACC: Activity Diagram 170

Figure 122: UC5 Scenario “cut-in” with C-ACC ” (at Road Works): Activity Diagram..... 171

Figure 123: UC5 Traffic Jam Alert with take-over 172

Figure 124: UC5 Scenario Traffic Jam Alert with take-over: Activity Diagram 173

Figure 125: UC5 Scenario “L4 ODD keep” (with Traffic Jam Alert) 174

Figure 126: UC5 Scenario Traffic Jam Alert where vehicle exits the ODD 174

Figure 127: UC5 Scenario of “L4 ODD keep” and “L4 ODD exit” (with Traffic Jam Alert) 176

Figure 128: UC5 Communication View..... 177

Figure 129: CAV functional view for UC5 179

Figure 130: C-ITS messages transmission..... 181

Figure 131: C-ITS messages reception..... 181

Figure 132: Positioning in open sky (GNSS+RTK) 181

Figure 133: Positioning in tunnel using RF signals from Software Defined Radio positioning system..... 182

Figure 134: Positioning in tunnel using RSU trilateration-based system 182

Figure 135: Positioning information for the cooperative applications 182

Figure 136: General scheme of automated driving functions based on cooperative applications 183

Figure 137: IT environment view..... 183

Figure 138: HMI concept view..... 184

Figure 139: Simplified representation of the arrangement of the SDR along the tunnel..... 186

Figure 140: Simplified representation of the arrangement of the trilateration system 187

Figure 141: RSU functionality for UC5..... 188

Figure 142: UC5 RSU IT environment view 188

Figure 143: RSU location for UC5 189

Figure 144: UC5 Functional View 190

Figure 145: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning – CAV only: sequence diagram 191

Figure 146: UC5 Scenario “car follow” with C-ACC (at Road Works): Sequence Diagram 192

Figure 147: UC5 Scenario: “cut-in” with C-ACC: Sequence Diagram 194

Figure 148: UC5 Scenario Traffic Jam Alert with take-over: Sequence Diagram 195

Figure 149: UC5 Scenarios of “L4 ODD keep” and “L4 ODD exit” (with Traffic Jam Alert): Sequence Diagram 196

List of tables

Table 1: Messages exchange information for UC1 41

Table 2: Messages exchange informion for UC2 - scenario 1 ‘Management of high priority vehicles’ 73

Table 3: Messages exchange information for UC2 - scenario 2 ‘Advanced traffic management based on real-time response’ 73

Table 4: Messages exchange information for UC2 - scenario 3 ‘VRUs protection’ 74

Table 5: Overview of planned cameras in LL of UC3 82

Table 6 : Types of messages used in UC3 and their standards and data formats 125

Table 7: Messages used in UC4 157

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
4G	4 th Generation of mobile technology standards
5G	5 th Generation of mobile technology standards
5GC	5G Core
ACC	Adaptive Cruise Control
AD	Automated Driving Assisted Driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance System
ADF	Automated Driving Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
ASN.1	Abstract Syntax Notation One
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BTP	Basic Transport Protocol
C2C-CC	Car-2-Car Communication Consortium
CA	Cooperative Awareness
C-ACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAN	Control Area Network
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CP	Collective Perception
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CS	Chip Select

CV	Connected Vehicle
C-V2X	Cellular V2X
CWDM	Coarse Wavelength Division Multiplexing
DB	Database
DCC	Decentralized Congestion Control
DEN	Decentralized Environmental Notification
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DSRC	Dedicated Short-Range Communications
DT	Digital Twin
DTB	Device Tree Blob
DWDM	Coarse Wavelength Division Multiplexing
eMMC	embedded MultiMediaCard
eNB	Evolved NodeB (4 th generation base station)
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EV	Electric Vehicle
EV	Emergency Vehicle
FR	Frequency Range
gNB	(next) generation NodeB (5 th generation base station)
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPIO	General Purpose Input/Output
GPS	Global Positioning System
GTW	Gateway
HAB	High Assurance Boot
HD	High Definition
HLN-TJA	Hazardous Location Notification – Traffic Jam Alert
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HSM	Hardware Security Module
HW	Hardware

I2V	Infrastructure-to-Vehicle
ID	Identifier
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IMA	Integrity Measurement Architecture
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IQR	Interquartile Range
IT	Information Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITS-G5	European standard for vehicular communications based on the IEEE-1609. X and IEEE-802.11p standards
ITS-S	ITS Station
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LL	Living Lab
LMB	Labelled Multi-Bernoulli
LSTM	long short-term memory
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MAPEM	MAP (topology) Extended Message
MBMS	Multimedia Broadcast Multicast Service
MCM	Manoeuvre Coordination Message
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MISO	Master In, Slave Out
ML	Machine Learning
MOSI	Master Out, Slave In
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MSC	Message Sequence Charts

MUX	Multiplexing
NARI	Neighbourhood Awareness Ratio
NAT	Network Address Translator
NB	NodeB
NIC	Network Interface Controller
NSA	Non-Standalone
OBU	On-Board Unit
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
ODE	Objects Detection Engine
PC	Personal Computer
PC5	5G reference point for direct communications between UEs
PE(r)	Position Error
PGW	Packet Gateway
PLMN	Public Land Mobil Network
PoE	Power over Ethernet
PTO	Point To Point
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
PWCE	Pixel World Coordinates Engine
pWLAN	public WLAN
QoS	Quality of Service
RADAR	Radio Detection and Ranging
REST	representational state transfer
RM	Resource Manager
RME	Risks Manager Engine
RMT	Risk Management in Tunnel
ROS	Robot Operating System
ROS2	Robot Operating System 2
RoT	Root of Trust
RRH	Remote Radio Head

RSS	Received Signal Strength
RSU	Roadside Unit
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
RWW	Road Works Warning
SA	Standalone
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SCLK	Serial Clock
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SDRAM	Synchronous Dynamic Random Access Memory
SEN	Service Edge Node
SGW	Serving Gateway
SHA	Secure Hash Algorithm
SL	Sidelink
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLAM	Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping
SM	Single Mode
SPAT	Signal Phase And Timing
SPATEM	Signal Phase And Timing Extended Message
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interface
SPL	Secondary Program Loader
SPU	Sensor Processing Unit
SSE	Surfaces Segmentation Engine
T4P4S	A Target-independent Compiler for Protocol-independent Packet Processors
TA	Trust Anchor
TAB	TPM2.0 Access Broker
TC	Trusted Computing
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TCE	Trajectories Calculation Engine

TCG	Trusted Computing Group
TCP	Transport Control Protocol
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TDOA	Time Difference Of Arrival
TEN	Telco Edge Node
TL	Traffic Light
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
TMS	Traffic Management System
TOA	Time of Arrival
TOF	Time of Flight
TPA	Trust Platform Agent
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
TSS	TPM2 Software Stack
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UPER	Unaligned Packed Encoding Rules
UPF	User-Plane Function
USB	Universal Serial Bus
Uu	LTE/5G radio interface
UULM	Universität Ulm, Institut für Mess-, Regel- und Mikrotechnik
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2I2V	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure-to-Vehicle
V2N2V	Vehicle-to-Network-to-Vehicle
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VA	Video Analysis
VAE	V2X Application Layer

VAM	VRU Awareness Message
VIMA	VRU-aware Intersection Movement Assistance
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WASM	WebAssembly
WLAN	Wireless Local-Area Network
YOLO	You Only Look Once

Executive Summary

PoDIUM aims to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure to address the challenges in road automation and telecommunications, especially those linked with connectivity, cooperation, data management, interoperability and reliability, trust and data truthfulness, in order to foster the development of advanced Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions. This deliverable provides a detailed specification of the PoDIUM platform architecture that will enable these developments. It will guarantee, on a conceptual level, the interoperability between all Living Labs.

This document provides a detailed overview of the 5 use cases, developed on basis of a common architecture as described in deliverable D3.1. Each UC description is structured into four or five different sections:

- a use case description, split into several individual scenarios;
- communication aspects, which not only describe the involved entities such as CAVs, RSUs, or VRUs, but also applied communication technologies including 5G and ITS-G5, as well as communication features such as multi-connectivity;
- connected entities such as CAVs, RSUs, or VRUs, covering functional views and IT environments;
- services and data exchange, where the focus lies on digital twins, traffic management, and cooperative manoeuvre planning using a wide range of C-ITS messages; and
- data truthfulness, which addresses aspects of data integrity and trust in received data. This point is covered in UC1 and UC4.

This deliverable is intended for stakeholders and experts involved in the development of cooperative, connected, and automated mobility systems. It ensures that the system meets the identified stakeholders' needs and requirements. The demonstration of the use cases in the Living Labs will further validate the system's functionality and showcase its potential impact on improving CCAM.

1. Introduction

This section shortly introduces the PoDIUM project, outlines the purpose of this document, and identifies the intended audience.

1.1. Project intro

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UCs) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of three well-equipped Living Labs (LLs) in Germany, Italy, and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for the availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) platform. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability, and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advanced data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards Digital Twins (DTs).
- New Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust, and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange, and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with the integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The aim of PoDIUM is to enhance CCAM services in Europe. To reach this goal the project focuses on the development and integration of the PDI needed to ensure the vehicle's connectivity via certain network technologies. A total of five PoDIUM UCs will be tested and validated under real-life conditions in the three LLs, located in Germany, Spain, and Italy. These UCs require advancing several technologies and elements that will be integrated under the common PoDIUM architecture. In previous deliverables (see [2] and [3]), a set of requirements have been specified.

The objective of Deliverable 3.2 is to present the specific characteristics of each use case of the PoDIUM project. The goal is to use the common reference architecture as a reference and thus as a basis for further development of the use cases. This ensures interoperability of the various heterogeneous networks and software components and will guarantee, on a conceptual level, the interoperability between all LLs.

1.3. Intended audience

This deliverable is classified as "Public", therefore, it will be uploaded on the PoDIUM website, where it will be available for all project partners and any interested readers, such as stakeholders and experts involved in the development of CCAM systems. Nevertheless, the consortium members are the main intended audience of this document.

1.4. Structure of the document and its relationship to other work packages/deliverables

The document is structured according to use cases, offering a comprehensive technical overview of the technologies used, and their proposed implementation within each use case and the corresponding living lab.

The deliverable therefore contains the following sub-chapters and is structured as follows:

- Section 2-6 describe the use cases with a common subsection structure.
- Section 7 provides a conclusion, summarizing the key points of the deliverable.

The subsections of each use case are structured as follows:

- Scenario Descriptions: describing basic supported procedures by the use case.
- Communication Aspects: providing communication characteristics and technologies utilized within the use case.
- Connected Entities: listing the entities involved within the use case.
- Services and Data Exchange: outlining the semantic interoperability and detailed functionality regarding data flow.
- Trust and Integrity: representing the security trust model, privacy preserving and access control developments.

The common reference architecture developed and outlined in Deliverable 3.1: “Architecture Description” (see [1]) serves as the basis for the use case implementation. Furthermore, the use case specific parts will be defined and described in detail. The results will be the basis for the LLs integration in work package 4.

2. Use Case 1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm

UC1 explores the benefit of a cooperative local environment model for managing complex urban traffic situations to support the ambitious EU safety and environmental targets by improving safety and efficiency in these situations. To improve availability and redundancy, different communication channels (5G mobile network with cm- and mm-wave; ITS-G5, 60GHz WiFi) will be realized and assessed.

2.1. Scenario Descriptions

In UC 1, two related scenarios are executed and compared. In Scenario 1, an obstacle (e.g. a parked truck) blocks one lane. Two CAVs arriving from opposite directions pass the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre. This scenario is investigated under two conditions a) with dynamic traffic information only available from the CAVs (lightweight solution) and b) with additional supporting information from the infrastructure sensors (baseline solution). In Scenario 2, a connected VRU without cooperation capabilities and a CAV passes the obstacle. This scenario will be only realized with infrastructure support.

In Scenario 1, a MEC server, two CAVs and, for the baseline solution, an arbitrary number of infrastructure sensors are included as actors. The scenario can be divided into two phases. The first phase is the continuous computation of the environment model. Hereby, the two vehicles send their location and velocity, planned route, and their on-board environment computed from their object detections to the MEC server. For the baseline solution, the infrastructure sensors also send their object detections. The MEC server then computes a digital twin and distributes it to the vehicles. As soon as the vehicles approach the blockage, they enter the second phase, during which the road blockage needs to be addressed. This entails a cooperative manoeuvre planning on MEC and manoeuvre handling by road users. The two vehicles are cooperatively manoeuvred by the MEC server until both vehicles have passed the obstacle. During the second phase, the activities as described for the first phase are continued as the DT is continuously updated with new data throughout the whole scenario. A detailed description of the sequence of activities is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: UC1 Scenario Description for Scenario 1

In Scenario 2, a MEC server, a connected VRU, a CAV and an arbitrary number of infrastructure sensors are included as actors. Again, the scenario can be partitioned in two phases. The first phase is the continuous computation of the environment model. Hereby, the CAV and the infrastructure sensors send their objects detections to the MEC server. The VRU and the CAV send their route, position, and velocity. The MEC server then computes a DT and distributes it to the connected road users. As soon as the road users approach the blockage, they enter the second phase blockage handling: cooperative manoeuvre planning on MEC and manoeuvre handling of the road users. The VRU is manoeuvred around the obstacle and afterwards both road users continue their itinerary. During the second phase, the activities as described for the first phase will be continued as the digital twin is continuously updated with new data throughout the whole scenario. A detailed description of the sequence of activities is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: UC1 Scenario Description for Scenario 2

2.2. Communication Aspects

This chapter describes the communication aspects of UC1 of the German LL. The goal is to present a comprehensive overview of the communication architecture, communication entities and the use of various communication technologies within the UC1. Furthermore, it describes how certain communication aspects are planned to be implemented within the UC.

2.2.1. Communication Architecture

The communication architecture chapter presents a description of the UC specific communication view including all involved entities. Furthermore, it provides insights of the communication of the entities and their role for the implementation of the UC scenarios, the communication technologies and how they are utilized in the UC, and finally the specific communication features that support specific aspects of the UC. The communication view for UC1 is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: UC1 Communication View (see also [4])

The local data processing and communications layer comprises VRUs, connected vehicles (CVs) and CAVs as well as RSUs and SPUs. CVs and CAV use direct communications (60 GHz Wifi as well as ITS-G5) in addition to cm-Wave and mm-Wave 5G. Note that a CV is a vehicle equipped with wireless communications technology that enables data transfer with other vehicles, infrastructure, or other networks, while a CAV is a vehicle equipped with various hardware and software that are collectively capable of wirelessly communicating with the world around it (other vehicles, traffic signals, the cloud) and performing part or all of the real-time operational and tactical functions required to operate in on-road traffic. Additionally, a VRU is connected through 5G cm-Wave communications to the MEC. The RSU is connected through a wired connection as well as cm-Wave 5G to the MEC as well as through direct communication (60-GHz-Wifi and ITS-G5) to the CV/CAV. The SPU is connected through 60-GHz-Wifi to the RSU as well as through cm-Wave 5G to the MEC. UC1 makes use of multi-connectivity as illustrated through the communication triangle in the middle of Figure 3.

2.2.2. Communication Entities

The individual entities are equipped with different communication technologies to fulfil the requirements of the use case scenario.

2.2.2.1. Connected Automated Vehicle (CAV)

Role:

In UC1, the CAVs communicate their current status, location, on-board environment computed from their object detections and planned routes to the MEC. For this, the CAVs can choose from multiple communication technologies (5G cm-wave, 5G mm-wave, ITS-G5, 60-GHz-Wifi) to allow for reliable and optionally redundant data transmission. Cooperative manoeuvres suggested by the MEC are automatically processed and assessed according to the state and environment model of the CAV.

Implementation:

The CAV is connected via 5G modems, and periodically sends status updates of their location, object tracks (based on the vehicle sensor data) and planned route. The Bosch CAV can additionally send sensor data (e.g. radar locations) to offload computations to the MEC. Schedulers are used to choose the communication technology for data transmission, based on the QoS demands needed for the data transmission and the available communication technologies. If required, data can be duplicated and simultaneously transmitted using

multiple communication technologies to increase the transmission reliability and add redundancy Cooperative driving manoeuvres computed by the MEC are transmitted back to the CAV as manoeuvre suggestions, which the CAV accepts or declines according to its state and environment model.

2.2.2.2. Roadside Unit (RSU)

Role:

In UC1, the RSU is used to establish the direct communication (CAM, MCM, CPM, see [5], [6], and [22]) to connected road users (CV/CAV) via ITS-G5, or 60-GHz-Wifi to connect to the infrastructure sensor units or CVs/CAVs via a high-speed link. In this scenario it also acts as a gateway for the infrastructure sensors to send their data to the MEC server.

Implementation:

The RSU is connected through a wired fibre connection (multiplexed on dark fibre) as well as cm-Wave 5G to the MEC, and through direct communication (60-GHz-Wifi and ITS-G5) to the CV/CAV. The RSU contains also a SPU and acts as the router/gateway to the MEC Server via wired line (multiplexed on dark fibre), cellular (cm-Wave), and Wifi (60 GHz).

2.2.2.3. Signal Processing Unit (SPU)

Role:

In UC1, the SPUs are used to detect both regular vehicles as well as vulnerable road users in the environment, which are then sent to the MEC Server to provide baseline information for the DT. In particular, the participants of UC1 can be detected by the sensors connected to the SPUs in order to create a redundant data source for environment data.

Implementation:

The processing of the sensor data is done locally on the SPUs themselves, while the communication from the SPUs to the MEC Server is realized via 5G cm-wave (FR1) connections as well as 60-GHz-Wifi with the RSU acting as a gateway 60-GHz-Wifi receiver. The data exchange itself is realized via raw ROS2 [27] detection messages sent via AMQP [28] at a fixed rate of 10Hz.

2.2.2.4. Vulnerable Road User (VRU)

Role:

The VRU will be represented by a cyclist in the UC1 scenario. The cyclist will be integrated into a cooperative driving manoeuvre in the scenario. For this purpose, the cyclist will be detected by the infrastructure sensors and integrated into the DT. In addition, the cyclist regularly sends his position and movement data to the MEC and communicates his planned route to the MEC in order to be able to carry out coordinated driving manoeuvres with the support of the MEC.

Implementation:

The cyclist is connected via a Nomadic Device. This will be implemented via a standard Android smartphone supporting 5G cm-Wave. A corresponding Android-based software is used to ensure the connection to the MEC and to implement the ITS message interface. The Android software will enable the cyclist to communicate interactively with the MEC via a specific developed HMI in order to complete cooperative driving manoeuvres.

The regular information updates on position and movement data is implemented via ITS VAM messages [23], which are transmitted to the MEC between 1-10Hz. The ITS message MCM will be used to coordinate the cooperative driving manoeuvres. The MCM is used to transmit manoeuvre recommendations from the MEC to the cyclist in order to coordinate all the road users involved in the traffic scenario.

2.2.2.5. Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)

Role:

The MEC has a central role in UC1, it processes sensor information from connected infrastructure sensors and the data from connected road users which is transmitted to the MEC. The MEC fuses the data into a global environment model, the DT, and uses it to generate an efficient plan for the coordinated execution of cooperative driving manoeuvres by sending recommendations for action to all road users involved.

Implementation:

The MEC is connected simultaneously to an upgraded LTE (4G) core (called Evolved Packet Core, or EPC) which was defined in the 5G non-standalone (5G NSA) network architecture solution, as well as to pure 5G core network (called 5G Core or 5GC), which was specified as 5G standalone (5G SA) network architecture solution. Additionally, a direct fibre connection between RSU and MEC exists. 5G NSA used only in combination with 5G mm-Wave.

Figure 4: UC1 MEC Connectivity

The data gateways of EPC and 5GC are located in the Nokia Lab in Ulm beside the MEC-Server.

2.2.3. Communication Features

This section describes all specific communication technologies in UC1 and how the technologies are utilized within the different types of communication.

2.2.3.1. 5G cm-Wave

Purpose:

The frequency bands below 6GHz, summarized under Frequency Range 1 (FR1) are also called cm-Wave to distinguish them from the higher 5G frequency bands identified as mm-Wave. The cm-Wave frequency bands are traditionally used for mobile communications and partly shared with previous mobile communication generations such as LTE. In UC1, the cm-Wave is used for the standard cellular communication between communication entities and the MEC-Server.

Implementation:

In the German LL the cm-Wave is used for both 5G implementation steps – non-standalone (NSA) and standalone (SA). As Nokia doesn't have own frequencies for on-air use, only unused frequencies of the mobile operators can be used. Currently only band 38 (2.6GHz, TDD) can be used with a bandwidth of 40MHz. The available data rate and latency is sufficient for V2X communication.

Deployment:

In UC1 the Nokia on-air test network is used with the following components:

- LTE and 5G core network in Finland with data gateways (SGW, PGW, UPF) in Nokia lab in Ulm
- Base station in Nokia lab in Ulm

- Antenna site on Blutspendezentrale in Ulm science park I for cm-Wave communications
- Antenna site at LL Ulm Lehr for mm-Wave communications (not yet implemented)

Figure 5: FR1 and FR2 realization in the German LL

2.2.3.2. 5G mm-Wave

Purpose:

5G mm-Wave includes frequency bands from 24.25 GHz to 52.6 GHz, which have been labelled in 3GPP as Frequency Range 2 (FR2). Specified 5G mm-Wave frequency bands and channel bandwidths are published in 3GPP TS 38.101 [24]. Frequency bands in FR2 have significantly shorter transmission range but higher available bandwidth than frequency bands below 6GHz, which traditionally are used in mobile communication networks.

In UC 1, the 5G mm-Wave is one communication technology used to build a direct communication between the CV/CAV and the MEC-Server with a high data rate. This provides a redundant communication path.

Implementation:

In the German LL the band n258 on 26GHz (range: 24.25 - 27.50GHz) is used. The configured channel bandwidth is 100MHz. Up to 8 component carriers can be used. The mm-Wave is realized with 5G NSA in combination with the available cm-Wave band.

Deployment:

In addition of the NSA 5G cm-Wave part (in section 2.2.3.1) 3 remote radio hats (RRH) are installed in Ulm Lehr in the testing area of UC1. The connection to the base station in the Nokia lab is realized via a fibre fronthaul connection. A dark fibre is used with DWDM multiplexing.

2.2.3.3. ITS-G5

Purpose:

ITS-G5 (also called IEEE 802.11p or pWLAN) is a Wifi standard for local ad-hoc networks between road users and infrastructure (V2V/V2X). Road users with an ITS-G5 OBU can communicate directly to each other or they can connect to a local SPU equipped with a RSU. The SPU can then forward the network traffic to the MEC server or other connected entities, providing an additional communication path.

Implementation:

The ITS-G5 Wifi is based on the 802.11p standard and uses the 5.9 GHz band. It is optimized to work with distances of up to 1000m and road user velocities of up to 200km/h. The standard was already introduced in 2010.

Deployment:

In UC1 at least one CAV is equipped with a Cohda MK5 OBU and each SPU at the German LL is equipped with a Cohda MK5 RSU.

2.2.3.4. 60-GHz-Wifi

Purpose:

60-GHz-Wifi offers Wifi in the 60 GHz range which allows, depending on the specification, theoretical data rates up to 20-40 Gbit/s. In UC 1, the 60-GHz-Wifi is one communication technology used to build a direct communication between the CV and the RSU as well as between the RSU and the SPU. This provides a redundant communication path.

Implementation:

There are different specifications for 60-GHz-Wifi in the IEEE 802.11 family of Wifi WLANs. The current standard IEEE 802.11ay (Enhanced Throughput for Operation in License-exempt Bands above 45 GHz) is a follow-up to IEEE 802.11ad. The final standard IEEE 802.11ay-2021 was approved in March 2021.

Deployment:

In UC1 each SPU is equipped with a MIKROTIK wAP 60Gx3 AP access point [49] for the 60 GHz spectrum. The RSU is equipped with three MIKROTIK wAP 60Gx3 AP access points to ensure a line-of-sight connection to all SPUs. Also, the CAV is equipped with several MIKROTIK wAP 60Gx3 AP access points to ensure a connection to the RSU regardless of the orientation of the CAV.

2.2.3.5. Multi-connectivity

Purpose:

UC 1 makes use of Multi-connectivity as illustrated through the communication "triangle" between CV/CAV, RSU, and MEC in Figure 6. The entities CV/CAV, RSU, and the MEC server possess the scheduling ability to assign messages, packets, or data flows to one or multiple of the communication technologies available at each node. This ability is used in UC1 to showcase the impact of multi-connectivity on the communication reliability.

Figure 6: UC1 Multi-Connectivity Communication

Scheduler Architecture:

The scheduler consists of the following function: First, it consists of an API for external configuration, second a local control plane and finally a data plane function. The API provides the possibility for network apps, i.e., external programs, to configure the functions of the scheduler. The local control plane is designed for programming the data plane either through internal default parameters or through external configuration obtained from the configuration API. Finally, the data plane carries the scheduling functionality through the programs deployed by the control plane.

Figure 7: Scheduler functions

Implementation:

Multi-connectivity is implemented within the scheduler through a transparent p4 [19] programmable software switch, which runs either on a communication PC or directly on the MEC. The architecture of the p4 programmable switch utilizes the standard T4P4S compiler [20] approach to support different hardware such as running on a standard CPU. The structure of the scheduler comprises in a classical p4 manner a packet parser, match/action tables as well as a deparser. The packet parser defines the packet headers required for the multi-connectivity approach, i.e., it includes the packet headers required for the scheduler to decide on the multi-connectivity especially in terms of the mapping of a packet to one or more communication technologies such as 5G, 60-GHz-Wifi and ITS-G5. The

match/action tables provide the necessary means to execute the matching on the packet headers defined in the parser and the mapping to the different communication technologies, while the deparser is responsible for constructing and forwarding the data packet on the line. The specific parametrization of the packet headers for the multi-connectivity is tested with respect to different inherent headers of the communicated data. When the scheduler p4 program runs on the software switch, it can be parametrized at runtime to change the multi-connectivity configuration in terms of header values to be matched upon and actions such as packet cloning and forwarding on multiple communication technologies.

Deployment:

The scheduler is deployed on the CV/CAV through a transparent communication PC that is connected to the CAV processing and computing server. The communication PC is connected via 5G modem, 60-GHz-Wifi transceivers and an ITS-G5 OBU and it forwards all messages (e.g. CAM, CPM and MCM) obtained from the computing server on a subset of the available communication technologies in both directions. On the MEC, RSU, and SPU, the scheduler program runs directly on the server (optionally using a similarly transparent communication PC) with the same aforementioned capability. The scheduler configuration through match/action tables allows to configure the mapping of specific messages or message types to communication technologies.

2.3. Connected Entities

This chapter covers all developments related to entities that interact at road level with PoDIUM platform services in UC1.

2.3.1. Connected and Automated Vehicles

This section describes the functional view of the CAVs. Their automated driving functions provide information to the platform and follow platform instructions.

2.3.1.1. Functional view

Each CAV contains the following functional blocks with their respective functionality (see also Figure 8):

- **Localization:** Signals from a GNSS-based inertial system are used for a precise localization of the vehicle with respect to the earth coordinate system.
- **Perception:** First, the onboard sensor data (Video, LiDAR, RADAR) is fused to form a vehicle-centric environment representation. Afterwards, track-to-track fusion is employed to incorporate incoming perception data (CPMs) into the onboard environment model.
- **Planning:** In UC1, the behaviour planning is carried out on MEC server using the centralized DT as input to enable cooperative behaviours of multiple CAVs. The manoeuvre suggestions are received by the CAV in form of MCMs. Meanwhile, an onboard behaviour planner can run on background to provide fallback manoeuvres in case of service interruptions. Manoeuvres computed onboard or received from the MEC server are fulfilled by the motion planning, which calculates a driving trajectory.
- **C-ITS Message Handling / Data Transmission:** Functionality that enables the exchange of C-ITS messages (specifically CAM, CPM and MCM) with other PoDIUM entities. The message encoding, decoding and transmission is realized using AMQP with a standard publisher-subscriber protocol. Messages received via AMQP are subsequently converted from ASN.1 description to ROS/ ROS2 messages [27].

- Motion Control: Based on the localization and planning of the automated driving software, computed trajectories are executed by controlling the steering, acceleration, and deceleration of the vehicle.

Figure 8: UC1 Functional View of the CAV

2.3.1.2. IT environment view

Figure 9: UC1 IT environment view of a CAV

The IT environment of the CAV is loosely coupled into two parts, as shown in Figure 9. The first contains the car or automation PC (CarPC) that implements the driving functionality. The second contains the communication PC (ComPC) which hosts the scheduler and forwards the messages to the various communication methods or collects the messages from them. Depending on the concrete implementation, the communication units are either connected directly to the communication PC or through the switch (PoE Switch) that connects the car and communication PC. Note that some communication units (60 GHz and mm-Wave Modem) are mounted on the front (F) and back (B) of

the vehicle to ensure a connection independent of the orientation of the car. The vehicle's sensors are connected to the car PC, this connection can also be made via the switch.

2.3.1.3. Multi-connectivity Concept

The Multi-Connectivity Concept describes the multi-connectivity aspect of the CAVs:

- **5G:** The 5G modem is connected to the Nokia test network and the MEC server
- **ITS-G5:** The ITS-G5 is connected to the RSU and hence to the MEC server via fibre
- **60-GHz-Wifi:** The 60-GHz-Wifi connected to the RSU and hence to the MEC server via fibre

The CAVs run a communication PC in addition to the on-board unit running the CAV functions as depicted in Figure 10. The scheduler running on the communication PC performs the functionalities of data prioritization, duplication/deduplication, and is able to perform traffic transformation and monitoring.

Figure 10: UC1 Multi-Connectivity Concept of CAVs

2.3.2. Connected VRUs

This section describes the functional and IT environment view of the VRUs. Furthermore the concept for cooperative awareness and the respective HMI for the VRUs is described.

2.3.2.1. Functional view

This section describes the functional view of the connected VRU, as shown in Figure 11. The VRU is connected via an Android smartphone with a dedicated App.

Figure 11: UC1 Functional blocks of a connected VRU

The App contains the following blocks with their respective functionality:

- **Movement Data Handling (Sensor):** this functionality provides the basic message data. The various values are provided by the respective sensor of the smartphone and can be retrieved via the dedicated Android API.
- **C-ITS Message Handling:** this part provides the basic functionality for structuring C-ITS messages and filling them with values. Furthermore, also the encoding of the C-ITS messages in ASN.1 UPER [29] is encapsulated here. The implementation is crucial for creating the C-ITS message and sending / receiving them to / from the edge server.
- **Status Service:** this function is responsible for the correct processing of the VAM messages, i.e., it ensures the continuous report of movement data to the edge server via the VAM message.
- **Cooperative Service:** similar to the status service function, the cooperative service handles the bidirectional communication between VRU and edger server for cooperative traffic manoeuvres. Therefore, it is responsible for processing MCM messages.
- **HMI Service:** this service provides the interface to the bicyclist for executing cooperative traffic manoeuvre. The HMI maps the state of the MCM processing onto a UI. The edge server sends recommended actions to the VRU. The VRU has to manually accept or decline a recommended action of the MEC server in order to participate in a cooperative traffic manoeuvre.

2.3.2.2. IT environment view

The IT environment view (see Figure 12) presents the software and hardware of the VRU:

- **Smartphone:** The VRU is equipped with a commercially available Android smartphone that meets the requirements in terms of outdoor capability, i.e., IP68 [21].
- **CellularNIC:** Another criterion for the selection of hardware is the support of the required mobile radio frequencies. In the project, the VRU will only be connected in the cm-Wave (FR1) band.

Figure 12: Smartphone-IT Environment View

2.3.2.3. Cooperative Awareness HMI concept

In order to participate in cooperative traffic scenarios, the VRU must be able to interact bidirectionally with the MEC server. The MEC server transmits recommended action requests to the VRU via MCM messages. These MCM messages must be processed on the VRU side and displayed to the VRU as information. Furthermore, certain MCM requests must also be responded to, whereby e.g. the VRU must explicitly accept manoeuvre suggestions. The following Figure 13 represents the basic concept of the cooperative awareness HMI:

Figure 13: Cooperative Awareness HMI

The HMI consists of interactive components and information panel elements are explained in detail in the following:

- **MEC Server Connection:** This button fulfils the function of establishing a connection to the MEC Server in order to register the VRU in the system. It also monitors the connection status to the MEC server so that it is always visible whether the connection to the MEC Server is still active.
- **VAM Status:** This component can be used to activate and deactivate the continuous status messages (VAM). The movement data of the VRU is automatically entered in the VAM and sent to the MEC server. It is also planned to add a planned route of the VRU here so that the cooperative planner can take this information into account for optimized planning of the traffic manoeuvre.
- **Cooperation:** This is the central function for signalling a willingness to cooperate to the MEC server. Activating cooperation requests support for a traffic manoeuvre on the MEC server. This is done by sending MCM messages.
- **Cooperation State:** If the VRU is in an active cooperation scenario, the current state of the cooperation is displayed in this information panel. This includes, for example, the general availability of cooperation from the MEC server, whether the VRU has to confirm a manoeuvre proposed by the cooperation planner or if the VRU has successfully completed a manoeuvre.
- **Manoeuvre Information:** For a currently ongoing cooperative traffic scenarios, information on the specific VRU manoeuvre is displayed in this panel. This includes, for example, the distance of the calculated waypoints or the remaining manoeuvre duration.

2.3.3. RSUs

RSUs are stationary wireless and/or wireline communication devices which collect traffic data from the LL and transmit it to the MEC.

2.3.3.1. Functional view

This section describes the functional view of the RSUs. An RSU is used to forward data between connected road users and the infrastructure SPUs via a high-speed link (ITS-G5 or 60-GHz-Wifi). It is also used as a gateway between the infrastructure SPUs and the MEC server via cm-wave 5G network.

2.3.3.2. IT environment view

The RSU hardware is represented by an ITS-G5 unit MK5 RSU from Cohda Wireless. The RSU itself only provides ITS-G5 and Ethernet connectivity. The software is a custom firmware written in C that forwards messages in both directions.

2.3.3.3. Multi-connectivity Concept

The Multi-Connectivity Concept describes the multi-connectivity aspect of the RSU:

- **5G-cm Wave:** The 5G modem is connected to the Nokia test network and hence the MEC server
- **ITS-G5:** The ITS-G5 is connected to the CAVs
- **60-GHz-Wifi:** The 60-GHz-Wifi connected to the CAVs
- **Optical Fibre:** fixed connection to the server

The RSU runs a scheduler that per default relays the data traffic from the CAVs to the MEC server and vice versa. The scheduler on the RSU can be programmed to utilize multiple technologies in the section between the RSU and the sever, i.e., 5G-cm-Wave and fibre, as well as utilizing multiple technologies between the RSU and the CAV, 60-GHz-Wifi and ITS-G5.

2.3.4. SPUs

SPUs are stationary devices which collect and process perception data from the sensors such as cameras and LiDAR.

2.3.4.1. Functional view

This section describes the functional view of the sensor infrastructure. The infrastructure itself consists of multiple SPUs. Each infrastructure unit contains the following function blocks with their respective functionality:

- **Environment Perception (Sensor):** This function provides sensor data from cameras and radars overlooking the test site
- **Road User Detection:** This module provides a pipeline, which extracts object data from raw sensor data and determines the class and world location of each object
- **Sensor Fusion:** This function enables the fusion of camera and radar object lists into one object list
- **Data Transmission:** To provide the object data to the edge server, an AMQP transmitter is used
- **Time Synchronization:** A GPS receiver in combination with chrony [7] is used to synchronize system and sensor clocks to the MEC server

2.3.4.2. IT environment view

The IT environment view presents the software and hardware of the SPU:

- **Camera:** Each light pole is equipped with one or two GigE cameras [50]
- **Radar:** 9 out of 12 cameras are paired with a Bosch automotive radar each, overlooking the same area as the respective camera

- **GPS receiver/Raspberry Pi:** Each pole is equipped with a GPS receiver for time synchronization and camera triggering via PTP [51]
- **SPU:** All sensors and other devices attached to each light pole is connected to the SPU itself, which is a regular Mid-Tower PC with a mid-level graphics card and additional Ethernet interfaces
- **5G Modem:** Each SPU is connected to the Nokia test network via a USB 5G modem
- **60-GHz-Wifi:** Each pole is equipped with a 60 GHz antenna for direct communication with the reference system and RSU
- **Docker:** The SPU software is sandboxed in three Docker containers: one container is responsible for providing radar target data, the second one consists of an inference server for object detection while the third container contains the main data processing and transmission pipeline

2.3.4.3. Multi-connectivity Concept

The Multi-Connectivity Concept describes the multi-connectivity aspect of the SPU:

- **5G:** The main communication channel of each SPU is its 5G modem connected to the Nokia test network and the MEC server
- **60-GHz-Wifi:** As a backup, a high-throughput link to the edge server is available via a point-to-point 60-GHz-Wifi connection to the reference system, which is connected to the MEC server via fibre

2.4. Services and Data Exchange

This section contains information about the type of data exchanged by the elements of the platform services and identifies the services involved in the functionality and their interaction.

2.4.1. Functional components

For UC1, the PoDIUM framework is utilized as follows: SPUs detect all road users and send their detections to the multi-sensor multi-object tracking module within the DT. The environment model based on this data is enriched by the CAMs and CPMs of all CAVs inside the track-to-track fusion module. Both modules monitor their functionality with a self-assessment. Based on the DT, the cooperative manoeuvre planner suggests possible manoeuvres to the involved CAVs and VRUs via MCM messages. All sent and received messages go through the C-ITS Message and User Handling module, which make sure the messages are sent via the right communication method to the right receiver(s), as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: UC1 functional components

2.4.1.1. Digital Twin

The DT is responsible for the fusion of all available information about the current situation. This includes the fusion of data about the same entity detected by multiple sensors as well as combining the data about different entities detected by different sensors. Additionally, the module tracks all road users and performs a classification of all tracks. It creates a digital representation of the road in a form, that can be used by subsequent modules. In UC1, the DT is mainly used by the cooperative manoeuvre planner. Therefore, it is important, that all road users are present in this representation. To achieve these goals, a two-step framework is used.

The first part is the multi-sensor multi-object tracker. It performs the filtering and fusion of data, that is statistically independent. This includes, e.g., the detections of the SPU. It fuses the data in a stochastic manner. Therefore, models for the kinematic movement of the tracks as well as a measurement model for all detectors are needed. Based on Bayes-formula, the number of objects and the kinematic state of each object is estimated.

The second part is the *track-to-track* fusion: This part fuses all information, which is not guaranteed to be independent. This includes, e.g., the CPMs and CAMs of other road user.

Functional View:

- Receiving of data: The DT receives data in form of proprietary detection lists per detector/SPU.
- Provision of the result: The DT creates a CPM containing all relevant information.

IT Environment View:

- The DT runs in a dedicated ROS2 node inside a Docker container.

2.4.1.2. Infrastructure-based Road User Detection

The goal of the Infrastructure-based Road User Detection is to use the sensor data available at the infrastructure to extract and detect road users and other objects.

The sensor data incorporates both camera data and radar data. For both sensor modalities, a processing pipeline is implemented, which expects raw sensor data at the input and employs both deep learning neural network object detectors as well as classical clustering algorithms to detect road users in the scene and provides a unified detection list, which is then sent to the DT. Since the camera image does not provide any depth information, a post-processing module is incorporated, which can estimate object reference points from bounding boxes and map them into the world coordinate system, while for the radar pipeline, the tangential velocity component is estimated.

Another component of the processing pipeline is the optional detection fusion module, which can merge detection lists originating from both the camera and radar pipelines into one list while exploiting the specific features of a specific sensor and improving system reliability, which is modelled with Subjective Logic opinions.

Functional View:

- Receiving of data: The detection module receives raw image data and spatial target lists from the attached sensors.
- Provision of the result: The processing pipeline outputs lists of detected objects, which are sent to the DT.

IT Environment View:

- The processing pipeline runs in dedicated ROS2 nodes inside a docker container, in addition to another Docker container providing a server for neural network inference.

2.4.1.3. Cooperative Manoeuvre Planner

The cooperative manoeuvre planning module runs in a dedicated docker container and employs ROS2 to send and receive data within the MEC platform. The cooperative manoeuvre planner is responsible for guiding connected road users through corridor situations. Based on the DT, the cooperative manoeuvre planner continuously analyses the scene for connected road users. Road users signal their cooperation willingness by periodically sending MCMs. When a corridor situation is detected, the planner assesses the cooperation capability, determines a passing sequence, and orchestrates the involved connected road users using manoeuvre suggestion that are sent as MCMs. In return, acknowledgment or declination from road users is received via MCMs.

Functional View:

- Receiving of data: The cooperative manoeuvre planner receives CPMs from the DT and MCMs from connected road users.
- Provision of the result: The cooperative manoeuvre planner provides manoeuvre suggestions to the involved road users using MCMs.

IT Environment View:

- The cooperative manoeuvre planner runs in a dedicated ROS2 node inside a docker container.

2.4.1.4. C-ITS Message Handling (Scheduler)

The scheduler runs as a software switch with a Hardware Abstraction Library provided by T4P4S [20]. By default, the software switch runs on the CPU and employs a local control plane to configure the

switch data plane on the MEC platform. The scheduler sends and receive packets from the available network ports and is responsible for deduplication packets in uplink and possible duplication of packets in downlink direction. The scheduler works transparently with respect to the data connections to the broker and is responsible for forwarding the ITS messages that are received as data packets to and from the broker.

Functional View:

- Forwarding of data packets: The scheduler receives data packets from road users in uplink direction for deduplication and forwarding to the broker and possible duplicates data packets received from the broker in downlink direction to road users.

IT Environment View:

- The scheduler runs as a software switch on the CPU with a hardware abstraction library.

2.4.1.5. VRU Functions

The goal is to achieve increased visibility for the VRU in road traffic. In addition, the VRU should be able to be integrated into cooperative traffic manoeuvres coordinated by the MEC server. This functionality is to be implemented via C-ITS messages. The functionality serves to increase safety for the VRU in road traffic, so that traffic manoeuvres with the support of MEC server can be carried out with a higher level of safety.

Functional View:

- Providing continuous updates of movement data of the VRU to the MEC server. The data will be provided via VAM messages and the MEC server will use the data to merge the specific parts like speed, direction, and position into the digital twin.
- For the realization of cooperative manoeuvres, MCM messages are exchanged with the MEC server. The MCM message provides manoeuvre suggestions which the VRU can accept in order to be part of a cooperative manoeuvre. Therefore, the MCM is used as a bi-directional communication channel to coordinate traffic manoeuvres. An HMI is required on the VRU side to implement the cooperative functions and to process the MCM messages accordingly.

IT Environment View:

- The VRU functionality will be realized within an Android-based smartphone app. The App will use a V2X stack to process and send the C-ITS messages. An attempt will be made to implement the functionality on commercially available smartphones to enable the widest possible use.

2.4.1.6. CAV Functions

The CAVs are tightly integrated into the PoDIUM framework. They are able to respond adequately to manoeuvre request via MCM send their position via CAM respective their local environment model via CPM to enrich the DT. The CAVs support the different communication methods specified in the corresponding chapter.

Functional View:

- Provide continuous updates to the DT via CAM and CPM
- React adequately to the manoeuvre suggestions via MCM

IT Environment View:

- The CAV Functions are realized by hardware inside CAV with the possible exception for functions that are offloaded into the MEC. For a detailed view, refer to the corresponding chapter.

2.4.2. Data Flow and Storage

A data-flow represents the way in which data is exchanged by entities of the use case. Data storage is the retention of information by entities of the UC, and to have it accessible as necessary.

2.4.2.1. General view of the exchange of information

The exchange of information is represented in sequence diagrams (Figure 15) which show the interaction between the different entities. In UC1, a basic distinction is made between two scenarios. The first scenario involves a CAV with optional RSU / SPU support and in the second scenario the VRU is taken into consideration.

The messages CAM, CPM and MCM are used to exchange information between CAV and edge server, during VRU uses VAM and MCM. The CAM for CAV and VAM for VRU are used for the continuous transmission of status information, e.g. the current position, speed and planned route are transmitted. The MCM is used for bi-directional communication for cooperative traffic manoeuvres and the request or willingness of cooperation. Here, manoeuvres are recommended by the edge server to safely resolve critical traffic situations. In the VRU scenario, CAV has to accept the suggested manoeuvres before they are sent to the VRU.

Figure 15: UC1 Sequence Diagram

2.4.2.2. Message exchange

The following Table 1 shows detailed information about the used messages respectively for the CAV and the VRU scenario.

Type of message	Purpose	Standard	Data format
CAM (Cooperative Awareness Message)	To send location and speed from CAVs and EV to the C-ITS Message and User Handling, and from this service to the Digital Twin	ETSI EN 302 637-2	ASN.1 UPER
VAM (Vulnerable Awareness Message)	To send location and speed from VRU to the C-ITS Message and User Handling, and from this service to the Digital Twin	ETSI TS 103 300-3	ASN.1 UPER
CPM (Collective Perception Message)	To send detection of VRUs by means of infrastructure sensors, indicating location, position of the VRU	ETSI TR 103 562	ASN.1 UPER
MCM (Manoeuvre Coordination Message)	Communication of cooperative traffic manoeuvre between the edge server and VRU	ETSI TS 103 561	ASN.1 UPER

Table 1: Messages exchange information for UC1

2.4.2.3. Semantic interoperability aspects

For data exchange we use message definitions based on the CPM Release 2 [25], the CAM Release 2 Draft [26], and the VAM Release 2 [23] as provided by the ETSI. We adapted the message definitions to meet our use case requirements. We extended the data fields by an increased number of bits for angle and speed variances, a modified covariance matrix definition, an associated station ID field for perceived objects, and a trajectory prediction container. For the MCM, we use our own definition published in [8], as there is no official release from the ETSI yet. These changes lead to binary incompatibility between our versions and the official ETSI standard for all involved messages.

2.5. Data Truthfulness

As the cooperative manoeuvre planner depends crucially on the DT (Figure 16), it is important to assess the quality of this information. If all statistical assumptions of the multi-object multi-sensor tracker are met, it can be shown that the fusion is Bayes-optimal, i.e., there is no better performing method. Therefore, for UC1, we assess the DT by checking whether its assumptions are actually met by the real data. A common assumption is, e.g., that the measurement noise is Gaussian-distributed with zero-mean and known variance. If the actual data shows a different variance, then the result is no longer guaranteed to be optimal. To decide, whether the data follows the assumptions, Subjective Logic is used. Subjective Logic is a second order logic that is able to explicitly express the statistical uncertainty of the current estimation which is important in this context because of the few samples.

It is important to note that this approach does only provide an assessment relative the assumptions of the filter. It cannot deliver an assessment of the absolute quality of some sensor or data but only in comparison to the assumptions of the filter. However, depending on the assessment, data from non-conforming sources can be excluded from the fusion process which should enhance the overall result. This module runs in tight connection with the DT and provides no output processable by other modules.

Figure 16: Self-assessment of the DT

3. Use Case 2: PDI for Use-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs

Barcelona serves as the urban demonstration for Use Case 2 in the Spanish Living Lab. The demonstrations will take place in a segment of Gran Via Avenue that is part of a firefighter’s corridor and the neighbouring streets. This area includes some traffic light junctions as well as bike lane crossings and pedestrian crossings. Gran Via, a major artery with three to five lanes and numerous public transportation lines, is a complicated metropolitan area with high traffic and presence of heterogenous mobility actors. As such, it presents difficult situations for traffic efficiency and safety, which CCAM technologies will help to resolve with the support of Physical and Digital Infrastructure.

3.1. Scenario Descriptions

In UC2 there are three scenarios that highlight the importance of the data gathered from connected and automated vehicles in controlling urban signalized crossings in complex road networks, like allowing a high-priority vehicle to cross junctions or providing safety to road users, as well as in more complicated scenarios like traffic plan optimization in a sub-network made up of several intersections. Scenario 1 (Figure 17) is about the management of high priority vehicles. The trigger is the reception of the emergency alert, and then the emergency system asks the Traffic Management System for opening the corridor, and constantly sends the position and speed of the emergency vehicle. The Traffic Management System modifies the traffic plans by acting dynamically on the traffic lights as the emergency vehicle approaches the crossings. In parallel, the Traffic Management System informs Connected and Automated Vehicles about the reserved lane for the emergency vehicle.

Scenario 2 (Figure 18) relates to advanced traffic management based on real-time response. The scenario starts while all connected vehicles in the road network will be sending their position, speed and origin and destination to the Traffic Management System, which will select the optimal control strategy to avoid congestion and accidents. For this, The Traffic Management System will send messages to vehicles about the traffic status and hazards so that they can decide about the most appropriate route.

Finally, scenario 3 (Figure 19) is about VRUs protection, which will be detected and classified by artificial intelligence cameras. At the same time the connected vehicles will be sending their position and speed to the Traffic Management System, where a collision risk estimator will calculate the potential risks of collision between a vehicle and a VRU. If so, it will send warning messages to the involved VRUs and vehicles.

Figure 17: UC2 scenario description diagram - scenario 1 'Management of high-priority vehicles'

Figure 18: UC2 scenario description diagram - scenario 2 'Advanced traffic management based on real-time response'

Figure 19: UC2 scenario description diagram - scenario 3 'VRUs protection'

3.2. Communication Aspects

The communication components of UC2 of the Spanish LL are covered in this chapter, with the purpose of giving a general understanding of UC2's communication architecture, communication entities, and communication technologies utilization.

Moreover, the communication-related intended implementations in UC2 are provided, outlining how specific communication-related elements are implemented.

3.2.1. Communication Architecture

The communication architecture describes the communication context used in UC2, covering all involved entities. In addition, it provides insights about the entities' communication and their role in the implementation of the three UC2 scenarios, communication technologies and how they are employed, and, finally, communication features that support specific aspects of the use case. Figure 20 shows the communication view for UC2.

Figure 20: UC2 Communication view

UC2 showcases the application of multi-connectivity to elevate vehicular operation’s efficiency and safety, as illustrated in Figure 20. This framework highlights the synergy of diverse communication technologies, fostering uninterrupted interactions among vehicles, infrastructure, and users within the transport network.

The local data processing and communication layer integrates several critical entities, including Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), Connected Vehicles (CVs), Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs), Roadside Units (RSUs), Emergency Vehicles (EVs), AI Cameras, as well as Traffic Lights.

CVs, equipped with wireless technology, facilitate data exchange with other vehicles and infrastructure, enabling applications ranging from safety enhancements and cooperative manoeuvres to traffic optimization. CAVs extend these capabilities, incorporating technology that allows wireless interaction with their environment, including traffic signals and cloud services, facilitating autonomous navigation.

Both CVs and CAVs utilize direct communication technologies like C-V2X (LTE-PC5), alongside cm-Wave 5G networks, offering the bandwidth and low latency essential for the dynamic information exchange crucial to connected and automated vehicles.

EVs and VRUs also connect through cm-Wave 5G networks for cloud-based applications. In emergencies, EVs communicate their status to the Traffic Management Centre (TMC) via cm-Wave 5G to optimize traffic flow along designated city corridors, aiding congestion and accident mitigation by informing CAVs of strategic manoeuvres. For VRUs scenario, the focus is on reducing accident risks at complex intersections, where AI cameras and VRU sensors, linked to the PoDIUM platform via cm-Wave 5G, enhance CAVs' ability to detect road users despite on-street obstacles.

3.2.2. Communication Entities

Individual entities are supplied with various communication technologies to meet the needs of the three scenarios in UC2.

3.2.2.1. Connected Vehicles (CV) & Connected Automated Vehicle (CAV)

Role:

In UC2, CAVs and CVs use two communications technologies, C-V2X (LTE-PC5) and cellular network (preferably 5G, but 4G is also possible), to inform about:

- Their location, speed and direction via CAM messages.
- Priority requests and common operations-related messages from the EV to the emergency management centre.

On the other hand, CAVs and CVs receive information about abnormal situations (via DENM messages) from the MEC/Cloud thanks to AI camera detected events and the constant monitoring from the traffic management centre.

Implementation:

CVs and CAVs are integrated with On-Board Units (OBUs), which run ETSI ITS communication protocol stack [40], and 5G. This setup is augmented by a cellular modem, facilitating the exchange of C-ITS messages via IP protocol. For direct message transmission over C-V2X (LTE-PC5), these vehicles employ commercial devices from Cohda Wireless or Commsignia.

C-ITS messages are periodically transmitted in compliance with ETSI standards and simultaneously across both technologies. This dual transmission approach leverages C-V2X capability for fast communication, facilitating instant exchanges even in areas with poor cellular coverage. On the other hand, cellular networks, with their broad availability, are the primary medium for V2I communications. In regions where cellular service is poor, strategically deployed RSUs utilizing C-V2X technology fill in the connectivity gaps, enhancing the network's resilience and ensuring uninterrupted communication for vehicles in diverse settings. This strategy ensures that the connected vehicle ecosystem is adaptable and efficient, functioning effectively across a broad spectrum of environmental conditions.

3.2.2.2. Roadside Unit (RSU)

In UC2, the RSU plays a pivotal role in facilitating direct communication between connected road users (CVs/CAVs) and the infrastructure. Through C-V2X, the RSU enables vehicles to exchange C-ITS messages with each other and with the infrastructure (MEC), ensuring a high-speed and reliable link that is crucial for the safety and efficiency of vehicular operations.

In UC2, the C-V2X (LTE-PC5) connection delivers ad-hoc complementarity and redundancy, ensuring seamless connectivity, especially in areas with suboptimal 5G signal quality. RSUs are designed to effortlessly manage all communications between CVs/CAVs and cloud computing services.

Additionally, the RSU serves as a critical gateway for infrastructure sensors, channelling their data directly to the MEC server. By acting as a complementary conduit for sensor vehicle data, the RSU ensures that the MEC platform receives the information it needs to optimize traffic management and vehicle routing decisions, thereby improving the safety and efficiency of road transportation systems.

Implementation:

The RSU is connected through a cm-Wave 5G/4G connection to the MEC as well as through direct communication (C-V2X LTE-PC5) to the CV/CAVs.

3.2.2.3. Signal Processing Unit (SPU) – Traffic cameras

The SPU consists of a camera system integrated with an AI-powered local server, both of which are connected via a wired connection. This advanced setup is designed for the real-time detection of events in the context of UC2. Utilizing cutting-edge cm-Wave 5G technology, the AI local server establishes a connection with the MEC infrastructure. This seamless integration facilitates the triggering of near real-time notifications through C-ITS messages, enhancing the responsiveness and efficiency of the system in urban traffic management scenarios.

3.2.2.4. Vulnerable Road User (VRU)

In UC2, a VRU, such as a pedestrian, bicyclist, or scooter rider, is seamlessly integrated into the traffic management system using cm-Wave 5G technology, connecting them to the MEC. This innovative approach ensures near real-time communication and enhances safety for VRUs in urban environments. As they navigate street sections under surveillance by advanced AI-powered cameras and as CVs/CAVs draw near, the system's cutting-edge AI cameras spring into action. These cameras are adept at detecting VRUs and employ a sophisticated Risk Estimator algorithm to forecast potential collision trajectories between VRUs and approaching vehicles. Should the algorithm predict a collision risk, it promptly triggers the generation of a warning message. This critical alert is then disseminated to both the identified VRU and the approaching CV/CAV, facilitated by the cm-Wave 5G network and C-V2X.

3.2.2.5. Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)

Role:

In UC2, the MEC platform occupies a central role by integrating and processing data from both infrastructure sensors and connected road users. This data, encompassing a wide array of inputs from the immediate environment, is transmitted to the MEC where it is synthesized into a comprehensive global environment model, effectively creating a digital twin of the real-world traffic scenario. Using this approach, the MEC develops and deploys coordinated plans for cooperative manoeuvring, which is critical for optimising traffic flow and improving road safety through the synchronised execution of driving manoeuvres. Figure 21 depicts the computational edge design of UC2.

Implementation:

The MEC is wirelessly connected to the public 5G network, which is specifically configured to meet certain Service Level Agreements (SLAs) that are designed to guarantee the latency and throughput requirements that are crucial for the successful implementation of UC2.

Figure 21: UC2 Edge Computing Architecture

3.2.2.6. Cloud server

In UC2, cloud computing plays a pivotal role by offering extensive data processing and communication services on a regional scale. This cloud infrastructure is seamlessly integrated with MEC through wired

connections, ensuring the required throughput and latency are met. Such a configuration not only facilitates high-speed data transmission but also supports the latency-sensitive applications crucial for UC2's success. This strategic pairing of cloud computing with MEC optimizes network efficiency, enabling robust and responsive communication, which is essential for UC2.

3.2.3. Communication Features

This section covers all the communication technologies in UC2 and how they are used in different types of communication.

3.2.3.1. 5G/4G cm-Wave

Purpose:

In UC2 the cm Wave is used for the standard cellular communication between communication entities and the MEC-Server.

Implementation:

To experiment with real-world conditions, UC2 leverages the public 5G/4G mobile network. The primary frequency bands utilized are the 3.5 GHz and the 700 MHz bands. The 3.5 GHz band is chosen primarily for its ability to provide high throughput, essential for supporting data-intensive equipment such as video cameras. On the other hand, the 700 MHz band is used to ensure extensive 5G/4G coverage under all circumstances.

3.2.3.2. C-V2X LTE-PC5

Purpose:

Cellular-V2X (C-V2X) is the umbrella term which encapsulates all 3GPP V2X technologies, including both direct (PC5) and mobile network communications (Uu). In 2016, 3GPP published V2X specifications based on LTE as the underlying technology. It is generally referred to as "cellular V2X" (C-V2X) to differentiate itself from the 802.11p based V2X technology. The direct communication between vehicle and other devices (V2V, V2I) uses the so-called PC5 interface.

C-V2X enables road users equipped with a C-V2X OBU to communicate directly with each other, as well as connect to C-V2X-compatible RSUs. The RSU plays a crucial role in this network by forwarding traffic to the MEC server or other connected entities, thus providing an additional, essential communication pathway.

Implementation:

The C-V2X LTE-PC5 technology operates in the 5.9 GHz band, same as ITS-G5. Specifically for Europe its spectrum allocation is between 5875 – 5905 MHz. Optimized for vehicular communication, it provides around 300 to 500 meters of coverage in urban settings, but this can extend to around 1000 meters under optimal conditions with clear line-of-sight and minimal interference [18].

In UC2, CVs/CAVs are equipped with C-V2X (LTE-PC5) compatible Commsignia or Cohda MK6 OBUs, and so are the RSUs installed on the roadside.

3.3. Connected Entities

This chapter covers all developments related to entities that interact at road level with PoDIUM platform services in UC2, the latter being described in section 3.3.1, as well as those connected entities shared between UC2 and UC3. There are two groups of connected entities: on the one hand there are road users, that include connected conventional and emergency vehicles, connected and automated vehicles and vulnerable road users; on the other hand, there are sensors and actors, that include traffic controllers and infrastructure-based road user detectors (AI cameras in UC2). In general terms in this chapter the connected entities are described providing their functional view, together with their sequence view between functional components and finally their IT environment view.

3.3.1. Connected and Automated Vehicles

The UC2 CAV is a shuttle bus with autonomous driving functions and hybrid connectivity (5G and C-V2X). Other Connected Vehicles (CVs), including the Emergency Vehicle (EV), implement a subset of functionalities of the CAV architecture. Therefore, this section describes CAV, CVs and EV’s functionalities.

The CAV, developed by MILLA for UC2 and UC3, is a SAE-4 automation level connected vehicle. The main goal of the Milla CAVs is to be able to develop fully automated transport services for persons and/or goods. To do so, Milla CAVs are connected to a proprietary cloud via 4G/5G that permits to create supervision services to be able to monitor the vehicle at any time, as well as interacting with the vehicle in case of incidence of any kind that requires human intelligence to take action in order to solve a complex problem that the CAV is not able to solve by itself. At the same time, the Milla Cloud is the interfacing point that integrates the Milla vehicles fleet into external transport services orchestrators.

The CVs include passenger vehicles (for UC2 and UC3) and the Emergency Vehicle for the UC2’s scenario 1 “Management of high-priority vehicles”.

3.3.1.1. Functional view

Figure 22 shows the functional view of the CAV and CVs for PoDIUM UC2 and UC3, since the same vehicles will be involved in both use cases. All the main functions running in the vehicles are described in this section, as well as interaction among them and with the external systems (e.g. Clouds).

Figure 22: UC2 and UC3 Functional view of the CAV and CVs

Most of the functions are implemented by all kinds of vehicles, while the ADF functions and the Cloud Interface are exclusive of the MILLA’s CAV vehicle. Only part of this architecture applies to CVs and the EV.

The EV is the simplest vehicle in terms of architecture, where only the Communications (only 5G), V2X stack and Positioning apply. The CVs will have the same architecture but including C-V2X technology.

Communications (Cellular, C-V2X)

The interface of the CAV and CVs with external entities is the communications module. It consists of both 5G and C-V2X (OBU) modems, able to talk with the MEC services and with other C-V2X stations respectively.

The OBU (On-Board Unit) is a Cohda Wireless device with the same software/functional architecture than the RSU (see 3.3.3.1). It is a transmitter/receiver (physical layer) of C-ITS messages using C-V2X

technology. Such messages are decoded and analyzed in the V2X stack, which is in charge of the rest of the layers (GeoNetworking, BTP, Facilities and Application) from the ETSI C-ITS standard [40].

The 5G modems are 5G SA (Standalone) compatible, being able to transmit and receive (physical layer) via 5G any kind of information.

Both technologies are expected to be available at the same time (except in those areas with bad signal coverage), therefore there is no need for any management to switch between them. The V2X stack will be in charge of sending and receiving C-ITS messages through this communications' function, while the Vehicle Applications Layer uses this function to establish contact with the Cloud for the CAV monitoring and remote control.

V2X stack (ETSI C-ITS)

This module implements the required C-ITS stack (GeoNetworking, BTP, Facilities and Application layers) and services for the scenarios of UC2 and UC3 handling every message received from the MEC (PoDIUM platform) and from nearby C-V2X units (vehicles, VRUs, etc.), and generating new messages to be disseminated/sent to the same both entities (MEC and C-V2X stations).

When a C-ITS message is received, it passes through the entire ETSI C-ITS stack where it is decoded and processed by the corresponding C-ITS service, which determines the relevance for the current situation of the vehicle and fills the Local Dynamic Map (LDM) accordingly, which serves as the messages database for the Automated Driving Functions (for the CAVs) and for the driver HMI application (for CVs and CAVs).

When a specific C-ITS service, such as the Cooperative Awareness (CA) service or the Decentralized Environmental Notification (DEN) service, needs to generate a new C-ITS message, it is constructed layer by layer from the ETSI C-ITS stack and is sent to the Communications function for the C-V2X and 5G dissemination.

HMI

Warnings (e.g. DENMs) and manoeuvre recommendations, which are sent as C-ITS messages and stored in the Local Dynamic Map (LDM), are captured by the HMI to display such information. The main goal is showing informative or safety data to the driver.

The HMI also shows the current location of the vehicle on a map, as well as the location and other relevant data related to the warnings and recommendations. Other cooperative perception data sent from nearby vehicles (e.g. CAM) is also shown on the map.

Perception

The perception system is, generally speaking, the set of sensors installed in the vehicle that feeds of input data for the vehicle to understand its environment state. These sensors are of different nature: cameras, LiDAR, radars, At this layer all the inputs from the different sensors are treated to feed with understandable environment data models, to the internal data layers. MILLA's CAV is equipped with cameras, a LiDAR, and radars.

Positioning

The Positioning system can be considered as a specific kind of sensor. It is the most relevant input to obtain the internal reference position of vehicle. This positioning system is fed of the standard Satellite GPS coordinates, but also uses an external private service to obtain a RTK (Real Time Kinematic) correction that will reduce the margin of error of the vehicle from almost a few meters to a centimetric accurate coordinate.

This positioning system is also equipped with an inertial central that also gives a precise estimation about the orientation of the vehicle. For the obtention of the RTK correction, one local antenna integrated at the vehicle emits a signal that are perceived by the RTK correction service provider's infrastructure. This infrastructure of the provider can make an accurate estimation of the position of the emitter. The vehicle needs to get that estimation done by the provider, and this information is obtained by the inertial centre using 5G communications. The better the link between the inertial

centre and the RTK correction provider’s infrastructure, the lower the probability of error for the Positioning.

The Positioning system used at MILLA CAVs also uses a camera to provide a SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) -based additional input to its inertial central when calculating and providing its position estimation to the Data Fusion & LDM layer.

Data Fusion & Local Dynamic Map (LDM)

The Data Fusion & LDM layer has 3 main goals:

- Evaluate all perception items in real time to identify the data models and the state of the environment. Most of the data provided at the perception layer are complementary and serve to complete the final data model that is going to be provided to the LDM layer.
- Feed of all the motion related items to ensure an accurate evaluation with an as-precise-as-possible Positioning estimation. This evaluation is not done using only the Positioning system, but also all available perception components that could provide additional feedback about the evolution of the Localization of the vehicle. Such is the case of the odometry system of the vehicle, or specific treatments of some sensors at the perception layer.
 - As an example of these treatments, the *perceived* distance to the road borders is constantly evaluated at the perception layer. That output is used as an input to evaluate the coherence of the Positioning input.
 - Other outputs of the perception layer used as an input at the Localization are the evaluation of the traced lines of the road.
- The evaluated perception data models and with the Localization permits to fully update the LDM layer, that is being update with a frequency of at least 20Hz.

Vehicle Applications Layer

In the “top” of the vehicle firmware’s layer, a set of applications are being created depending on different needs. The common factor for these applications is that they are data consumers of the other layers, as well as their connectivity with vehicle components with a target to complete the global service.

Cloud Interface

Is an application that creates a link between the CAV and the clouds. The main tasks of this application are:

- Inform to the CLOUDs about the detailed vehicle state and activity.
- Send commands or behave directives, such as a command to reach some specific destination, or the directive to limit a maximum nominal speed while circulating in autonomous mode.
- Show some specific information to the passengers of the vehicle.

ADF Planning

The goal of the ADF (Automated Driving Function) Planning layer is to create the global trajectory path for the vehicle to reach a destination, as well as include the dynamic manoeuvres directives to adapt the behave of the vehicle to the state of the road.

When an application unit at the Application Layer transmits a command for the vehicle to reach a destination, the ADF Planning feeds of the LDM layer to calculate an optimal trajectory to reach the destination. While the vehicle enters in autonomous mode, the ADF Planning is also feeding of the LDM layer to be able to adapt its immediate behave to the conditions of the environments.

In Autonomous-Mode, these calculations are constantly being provided to the ADF Motion module.

ADF Motion.....

The ADF Motion layer uses mainly the dynamic path being provided by the ADF Planning Layer. This

input is decomposed to micro-commands that are sent to the vehicle components via the CAN bus to the vehicle’s robotized components.

3.3.1.2. Sequence view between functional components

Operation of perception, positioning, V2X info and ADF functions for CAV

To operate the CAV vehicle properly, the perception and the positioning data are made available in the LDM for the ADF to retrieve it. The C-ITS messages (locations of other vehicles, cooperative perception data, incidents and strategies) are added to the LDM to enhance the autonomous vehicle’s general perception of the environment (Figure 23).

Figure 23: UC2 and UC3 Diagram of the operation of perception, positioning and ADF functions for CAV

Operation of positioning and V2X info for CVs and EV

Unlike the CAV, the CVs and EV don’t have perception, which means that only positioning and V2X data is inserted in the LDM for future use. Figure 24 shows the relationship among the functions involved in the positioning and the V2X data.

Figure 24: UC2 and UC3 Diagram of the positioning operation for CVs and EV

Message exchange with the UC2 PoDIUM platform services

The following sequence diagrams, exclusive from UC2, show the transmission and reception of CAM, and the reception of messages including CAM and DENM, which are the C-ITS messages involved in UC2.

Generation and transmission of CAMs

All kinds of connected vehicles, including the CAV, CVs and EV, will generate CAM messages according to the ETSI C-ITS standard. Such messages will reach the platform at the MEC and the CLOUD (depending on the configuration of each scenario) via 5G (for Scenarios 1, 2 and 3) and C-V2X (for Scenario 3). CAM messages require, among other information, the location and dynamics information of the vehicle, which is extracted from the LDM (see Figure 25).

Figure 25: UC2 Diagram of the generation and transmission of CAMs

Reception of DENM from the infrastructure

When new manoeuvre recommendations and warnings are generated by the TMC with the goal to inform the road users, they reach the CAV/CVs via 5G and C-V2X in form of DENM messages that are processed by the V2X stack function, which checks the relevancy of those messages for the vehicle and sends the appropriate information to the LDM. The HMI and the ADF (see Figure 26 for more details) retrieve such information (and other) from the LDM to perform their operations.

Figure 26: Flow diagram of the reception of DENM from the infrastructure

3.3.1.3. IT environment view

CAV IT view

Figure 27 shows the IT structure of the components at MILLA CAV. The CAV is a vehicle with robotized components able to be controlled via CAN, as well as communicate the state of its inner components to the ADF PC. The ADF PC is an entity composed by the ADF subsystem itself and the Data-Fusion & LDM modules that are updated thanks to a direct connection with the on-board vehicle’s sensors, via

CAN, ethernet and USB. The ADF PC is connected to a set of other components via an internal ethernet LAN.

Figure 27: UC2 and UC3 Physical view of the CAV

CV IT view

The Connected Vehicles for UC2 are not equipped with perception capabilities like the CAV. They are connected via 5G and C-V2X technologies to send CAM messages and receive DENMs, which are analysed in the V2X stack and sent to the LDM (Figure 28).

Figure 28: UC2 Physical view of the CVs

EV IT view

The Emergency Vehicle’s IT architecture consists of an Android device running all functionalities of the CV, except the C-V2X unit.

3.3.1.4. HMI

The CAV/CV HMI is designed to show real-time incidents and manoeuvres relevant for the vehicle/driver, as well as the current position and other dynamics information. Figure 29 shows the HMI wireframe.

On the left side of the screen, the current speed of the vehicle and icons representing the incidents (DENM) generated by the UC2 PoDIUM platform are displayed.

The incidents for UC2 are:

- Emergency Vehicle approaching
- Reserved lane
- VRU collision risk

The upper part of the screen shows the manoeuvres/reactions expected from the driver/vehicle. The CAV will apply those manoeuvres automatically, while the drivers of the CV will check the HMI to be advised about the recommended manoeuvre.

Figure 29: HMI wireframe for UC2 CAV and CVs

3.3.2. Connected VRUs

This chapter describes the service developed for the connected VRUs to alert them of potential risks of collision with vehicles based on their position.

3.3.2.1. Functional components

With the aim of warning VRUs about the existence of a risk of collision with other vehicles, a mobile application has been developed in Android operating system, using Flutter which features a service that sends query requests to the Google Firestore database, where in turn collision risk events coming

from the PODIUM Risk management service have been stored. Firestore supports queries based on geoposition, returning all elements in the collection within the specified range. The application periodically collects the device's position and performs the corresponding query. Once it receives the elements, notifications are sent to the device, and the application's map marks the points where incidents are located.

3.3.2.2. Sequence view between functional components

Figure 30 shows the sequence diagram of functional components that interact among the VRU Application, the MapWidget service for updating the map where the collision risk exists, the Firebase service for geoposition, the NotificationService for displaying warning in case of risk of collision, and the devices (smartphone and/or wearable) for warning VRU about the existence of risk of collision with other vehicles.

Figure 30: UC2 Sequence diagram for the VRU application

3.3.2.3. IT environment

The VRU's hardware and software are displayed in the IT environment view (see Figure 31):

- Smartphone: A mid-range Android smartphone that is available for purchase is attached to the VRU.
- Cellular NIC: Only the cm-Wave band will be used for VRU connectivity in UC2, with the application operating on both 4G and 5G networks.
- Smart wearable device: With the aim of increasing road safety of VRUs, particularly bicycle and e-scooter users, it is proposed in UC2 to use a smart device that avoid VRU having to attend the smartphone while crossing the street. It will probably be a smartwatch connected to the smartphone by Bluetooth, allowing the reception of the warning message by means of vibration and/or audio alerts.

Figure 31: IT environment view for VRU devices

3.3.3. Connected roadside entities

3.3.3.1. RSUs

The PoDIUM UC2 plans to run Scenarios 1 and 2 with 5G technology, while Scenario 3 will be executed with C-V2X. There will be used Cohda Wireless or Commsignia RSUs for both UC2 and UC3 that have been modified in terms of software considering the requirements from both use cases, despite UC2 involves only one unit (for the VRU scenario), while the UC3 requires a total of 3 RSUs.

The details of these RSU entities, such as function and IT diagrams, and other useful diagrams and specifications can be found in the RSU section from UC3 (see section 4.3.3).

3.3.3.2. Sensor Processing Units

Figure 32: Camera used for road user detection in UC2

There will be two cameras installed on the road mounted over poles located at the crossing that will be used for the detection of road users. The camera model is Dahua IPC-HDBW2231R-ZAS-S2 (Figure 32), a high image definition camera equipped with advanced characteristics that allow the acquisition of live images for further video analytics on the local server.

3.3.3.2.1. Functional components

As described in section 3.1, scenario 3 consists of a pipeline of detecting vehicles and VRUs and anticipating risks situations between these two actuators using artificial intelligence techniques. To be able to detect these risky situations with good criteria some components with a specific pipeline have been defined, which are described below:

- **Objects Detection Engine (ODE):** Component in charge of detecting a list of pre-defined objects in movement and classifying them among the following – *persons, cars, bicycles, motorbikes, trucks, vans, buses, electric scooters, trams, dogs and cats* –. This module has been trained to be able to detect the objects described before and assign an identity, letting the system track them and obtain further calculus.
- **Surfaces Segmentation Engine (SSE):** Component in charge of defining the surface areas in the street which will be used by the ‘*Risks manager engine*’ to properly decide if a risk is going to appear or not. This AI module has been trained to detect *sidewalks, roads, crossings and bike lanes*.
- **Trajectories Calculation Engine (TCE):** Component in charge of obtaining the results from ‘*Objects detection engine*’ and use each of these objects and their identities to properly calculate their respective speeds and the trajectories.
- **Pixel World Coordinates Engine (PWCE):** Component in charge of transforming each pixel of the image to real-world coordinates using the intrinsic camera parameters, letting the ‘*Risks manager engine*’ to assign a real GPS location to each of the detected objects and to the risks.
- **Risks Manager Engine (RME):** Component in charge of obtaining the results of each of the other components and managing them to finally decide if a risk could appear or not. It is also in charge of communicating all the necessary actions to the external components.

3.3.3.2. Sequence view between functional components

Figure 33 shows the sequence diagram that shows the interaction between the functional components described in the previous section.

The sequence begins when the cameras send the images to the *Objects detection engine (ODE)* for identifying road users, and to the *Surfaces Segmentation Engine (SSE)* for defining the surfaces where potential risks could happen. The first (ODE) sends the identified objects to the *Trajectories calculation engine (TCE)* for calculating the road users speed and trajectories, and together with the SSE output to the *Pixel world coordinates engine (PWCE)* for transforming detected objects and risks into real-world coordinates.

Finally, with the outputs of TCE, PWCE and SSE, the *Risks manager engine (RME)* decide if there is a potential risk of collision and then send it to road users through the RSU.

Figure 33: UC2 Sequence diagram of SPU functional components

3.3.3.3. IT environment

Figure 34 shows the IT environment view of SPU in UC2 that contains the following hardware and software:

- 2 cameras, each one installed on each pole of the crossing where road users will be detected, connected by wire with the Edge Computer for computing and fed by PoE from the 5G router.
- An Edge Computer with two Docker containers where all functional components above mentioned will be properly distributed for their running.
- A 5G Router that will serve as communication layer between the Edge Computer and the RSU.

Figure 34: SPU IT environment view in UC2

3.4. Services and Data Exchange

This chapter describes the functional interaction and data exchange between services in UC2 of the Spanish LL. The aim is to provide detailed information of the different services that are functioning in UC2, and which type of data will be communicating each of them, together with the timeline, formats and standards used for this purpose.

3.4.1. Functional components

This chapter reports the specific services that are deployed in UC2, both on the cloud or edge level (see Figure 35), followed by detailed description of each of them. Other types of services deployed on the road level, like CAVs or those related with VRUs, have been described in Section 3.3.

Figure 35: UC2 Platform services

The functional components, belonging to the ‘Platform services’ block, that comprise the main functions necessary for the implementation of the UC2 are the following:

3.4.1.1. Digital Twin

This function is responsible for creating the digital representation of the road network, collecting static and dynamic real-time data from the different data sources, and fusing them together to provide a complete state of all road users (see Figure 36).

To reflect the reality of the behaviour of the road network and estimate the possible interactions between the different users, a network model is used that constitutes a DT of the physical space. The network model includes the structure of the roads and the location of the different static elements. All the dynamic elements that interact in the road network are located in this static model. MISTRAL Mobility Platform, developed by ETRA, uses this information from the DT to generate additional information for mobility management. Among the information managed in the DT that contributes to this use case, the following can be highlighted:

1. Static information: Information on intersections, road topology, vertical and horizontal traffic signs, etc.
2. Dynamic/Real-time information: Geolocation and speed of Connected Vehicles and VRUs.
3. Real-time alerts: Warnings to VRUs about collision risk with vehicles and to connected vehicles about collision risk with VRUs.
4. Added value features: Collision risk estimation.

The DT, in addition to serving as a representation of the physical world (Digital Shadow), acts on it in different ways (Digital Twin) either through strategic or tactical actions.

The DT is structured at two levels: The macro and the micro. The macro level (DT-macro) allows the modelling of the macroscopic road network in which reality is represented by a series of magnitudes that represent the state of mobility (vehicle flows, densities, speeds, traffic plans, etc.). MISTRAL uses the DT-macro to carry out the strategic management of mobility making use of the information corresponding to the different modalities and being able to act on the different verticals.

The micro level (DT-micro) is intended for the individual representation of the different elements of the road network or parts of the road network that require special attention. The DT-micro is used to represent vehicles and VRUs using specific variables for each type of actor (type, position, direction, speed, etc.). The DT-micro allows the analysis of the possible interactions between the different actors and the analysis of risks.

The DT feeds on the information provided by the different vertical systems with specific mobility management functions such as traffic light control or information to the public through panels or other means. For this reason, it has specific APIs to perform these functions. The DT also has APIs to disseminate information to other systems.

Figure 36: Architecture of the Digital Twin used in UC2

3.4.1.2. Advanced Perception Model

This chapter describes, in connection with all the engines defined in section 3.3.3.2, the Advanced Perception Model that has been created in UC2 with the aim of being able to identify different risk situations between VRUs and vehicles.

Each of these engines is composed of deep learning models which provide an intelligence and added value using the information obtained, through the installed cameras on the road.

A brief description of the algorithms utilized in these engines is provided:

- **Objects Detection Engine (ODE):** A *You Only Look Once (YOLO)* deep learning model has been trained, following the common defined criteria in object detection tasks, to be able to detect different road users – persons, cars, bicycles, motorbikes, trucks, vans, buses, electric scooter, tram, dogs and cats –, given a frame, and extract their position. Additionally, another deep learning model called ByteTracker [52] has been employed, using the previous extracted elements, to take the detected objects and assign an identifier, in order to track them through the following frames.
- **Surfaces Segmentation Engine (SSE):** Two segmentation models have been trained, following the common defined criteria in segmentation tasks, to be able to detect sidewalks, roads, crossings, and bike lanes. Both models are using a U-Net architecture [53] with a mix vision transformer as encoder.

- **Trajectories Calculation Engine (TCE):** Mathematical algorithms have been used to obtain the results of *ODE* and calculate their respective speeds, also taking in account the depth factor of the view in the camera. Once the speed has been obtained and also the direction of each element, this engine is able to predict, using another mathematical algorithm, the trajectory in the next *x* seconds.
- **Pixel World Coordinates Engine (PWCE):** Using the intrinsic parameters of the camera, the results from *ODE* and some geospatial operations, this module is able to give the exact latitude and longitude coordinates of each detected element in the video.
- **Risks Manager Engine (RME):** Working as an orchestrator, it takes all the outputs from the other engines and apply pre-defined rules (to be defined) to raise alerts to the involved users in the road.

Below, Figure 37 shows an image that represents the road user detection and trajectory prediction as outputs of the mentioned engines that compose the Advanced Perception Model.

Figure 37: Road users' detection and trajectory prediction

3.4.1.3. Collision Risk Estimator

This function receives information about the location and speed of Connected Vehicles (autonomous or not) from the Connected Vehicle Manager through the Cooperative Server (AURORA, developed by ETRA), and about the VRUs detected by sensors (AI cameras). It will generate a prediction of their trajectories, for both vehicles and VRUS, and will estimate the potential risk of collision. When the risk of collision exceeds a certain threshold, it will send messages to Connected Vehicles and VRUs.

3.4.1.4. Traffic Management and Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning

This function comprises four subfunctions, that in UC2 are responsible for the following:

- **Traffic Metrics Generator:** this subfunction receives and processes the positions and speeds sent by the connected vehicles and generates traffic metrics that are, once calculated per

integration period, shared with both the Digital Twin and the TMS. To generate the metrics, this subfunction:

- Accounts the number of vehicles travelling from an origin zone and a destination zone, generating an O-D matrix per integration period, also calculating the average travel time and average travelled distance for the trips accounted.
- Calculates the travel time of each vehicle along each road segment and aggregates the result to generate the average travel time, average speed and average delay per road segment and integration period.
- **Traffic Status Assessment:** this functionality acts as a client of the TMS and receives from it notification of relevant incidents occurring in the road network, translating them to DENM messages that are sent to CVs/CAVs.
- **Cooperative Manoeuvre Recommender:** from the tracking of the position of the EVs along their corridors and the positions received from CV/CAVs, estimates the coincidence of EVs and CV/CAVs, and whenever suitable sends messages to CVs/CAVs recommending them to get out of the reserved lane for the EV.
- **Emergency Priority Manager:** uses the position of sent periodically by EVs to make a prognosis of the arrival time at intersections equipped with traffic lights, to request, at the suitable time, the TMS to send priority requests to the traffic controllers so the EVs cross the junctions with green light.

3.4.1.5. C-ITS Message and User Handling

This function provides connectivity between road users and the infrastructure. It comprises two different services, the Connected Vehicle Manager and the Cooperative Server (AURORA). The first is a gateway from the vehicle side that sends messages between CVs and AURORA, while the latter is a cooperative server from the infrastructure side that allows the communication with the TMS following standardized interfaces. All these messages could be sent in a bidirectional way, depending on the type of pf message (e.g. a CAM message from the CV to the C-ITS Message Handling, and a DENM message in the opposite direction).

The Connected Vehicle Manager, also known as V2X Gateway for UC3 (see section 4.4.1.4), is a solution developed by IDIADA that opens a bidirectional interface between the Cooperative Server (AURORA) managed by the Road Operator, and the road users / vehicles. This way, the operator can receive all C-ITS messages sent from the vehicles (CAV, CVs, and EV) on the road in real-time. At the same time, the operator can order the dissemination of a specific C-ITS messages down to the road users. This Gateway solution is based on the MQTT protocol, which is used by the V2X stack on vehicles to establish a Pub/Sub communication model with the messaging broker placed in the Connected Vehicle Manager (deployed in the MEC or the Cloud).

The basic Pub/Sub model has been enhanced following a smart subscription approach where the subscriptions from the users are based on their interests and location. This way, the infrastructure is only responsible to publish the C-ITS messages on the corresponding topics, being able to emulate unicast, multicast and broadcast dissemination, allowing a lighter deployment, better scalability of the platform and potentially lower latencies. The hardest work relies on the vehicles' side, which needs to update its preferences (topics) while moving. This distributes the efforts among multiple devices/users (VRUs, CVs, CAVs) over time.

Apart from the messaging broker, the Connected Vehicle Manager from IDIADA is composed of a set of JAVA-based containerized modules that deal with the data processing and extraction, implementing the GeoNetworking, BTP and Facilities layer from the ETSI ITS standard [40], as well as the interfaces (API) with the AURORA server.

Except for the interface with AURORA, the rest of the components of the C-ITS Message and User Handing are shared between UC2 and UC3 for the IDIADA implementation. UC3 runs two different versions of this component in order to evaluate the differences on the communication protocol, while UC2 runs only the IDIADA version to concentrate the evaluation efforts on other metrics like Edge/Cloud performance comparison.

3.4.1.6. VRU Manager

This service that is in charge of the interaction with the mobile Apps of the VRUs, ensuring that the alerts generated by the Collision Risk Estimator are received by the users for which they are considered relevant (from their position) and not by other users.

This service is composed by:

- Firestore database, where the risk collision warnings are stored and that provides geoquery facilities for the VRU Apps (see section 3.3.2) obtaining the warnings that are relevant for the users.
- Data adaptor that receives the risk collision warnings generated by the Risk management functionality (Collision Risk Estimator, see section 3.4.1.3) and sends them to Firestore.

3.4.1.7. Other: external systems

The diagram in Figure 35 shows two functional blocks classified as *external systems* that are not part of the services developed within PODIUM but are integrated and play an important role in some scenarios of UC2:

- The Traffic Management System controls the traffic lights in the city of Barcelona and:
 - Has a crucial role in the Traffic Optimisation scenario, processing the values generated by the Traffic Metrics Generator, combining them with the data from infrastructure sensors to:
 - Make a prognosis of the evolution of the situation in the road network and apply the suitable traffic control strategy, what, in turn, translates in adaptation of the times for the colours of the traffic lights.
 - Provide relevant information to traffic operator so they can identify relevant incidents or, in some cases, detect the incidents automatically. Such incidents are notified to CVs/CVAs by the Traffic Status Assessment Service.
 - Has also a crucial role in the Priority for Emergency Vehicle scenario, being responsible of the interaction with traffic controllers to request priority of the emergency vehicle, so the traffic light that controls the movement to me made by the vehicle across a junction gets green as soon as possible.
- The Emergency Management System (Mycelium) for the firefighter vehicles in Barcelona shall inform about the vehicles that shall travel through the corridors to attend an emergency, indicating which corridor and the moment the vehicle begins the trip.

3.4.2. IT environment view

Cloud IT View

The cloud environment shall be provided by a virtualized environment, where several VM run and host the multiple services and system of the UC2 PODIUM services (see Figure 38).

Figure 38: IT view for UC2 cloud

Some of the services are built as *docker* images and run on *docker* containers, which in turn are deployed in Linux VMs. The actual number of VMs dedicated to this purpose will be decided as part of the deployment process, to adapt to the computation resources requirements of the different components.

One VM is dedicated to Connected Vehicle Manager (IDIADA Gateway) *docker* container.

One or more VMs run the *docker* containers for:

- CCAMTrafficService, covering the following functional blocks:
 - Traffic metrics generation
 - Traffic status assessment
 - EMEBO+, covering the following functional blockEmergency priority management
- CoopManRec:
 - Cooperative manoeuvre recommender
- CollisionRiskEstimator:
 - Cloud instance of the Risk management functional block (available to make tests with 5G communication in parallel to V2X)
- VRU_manager: a data adaptor for sending data from the Risk management functional block to the Firebase service that feeds VRU app (see section 3.3.2)
- MongoDB database engine and storage for Digital Twin database
- MQTT middleware

Some other services are built as Windows Services and deployed in Windows VMs:

- SQL Server database engine and storage for:
 - Digital Twin (some historic data is stored in SQL database)
 - Traffic Management System databases
- An instance of the Barcelona Traffic Management System that is connected to the intersection participating in pilot tests, thus avoiding affecting the rest of the road network.

In addition to this, the VRU protection use case, for the purpose of informing the VRUs about the high collision risk events detected by the Collision Risk Estimator, makes uses of the Firebase real-time database service provided by Google, where the Collision Risk events generated are stored.

3.4.3. Data Flow and Storage

This chapter is intended to identify the interactions between the different services and data sources (PDI, vehicles and other road users) and the kind of data exchanged within those interactions.

3.4.3.1. General view of the exchange of information

In this subchapter a general view of the exchange of information in UC2. For this purpose, UML sequence diagrams are used, as interaction diagrams that graphically represent how interactions between different services are carried out. These diagrams are time focus and show the order of the interaction visually by using the vertical axis of the diagram to represent time what messages and other types of exchanges of information are sent and when.

There are three different scenarios in UC2, with some commonalities but also involving different services, so the interaction between them is represented in various UML sequence diagrams, as shown in Figure 39, Figure 40 and Figure 41.

The commonalities both the three scenarios can be described in two groups of exchange of information:

CAM dissemination from vehicles to the infrastructure

Cooperative perception data in form of CAMs is periodically generated by the CAV/CVs. Following a hybrid approach, such vehicles are disseminating those messages to the MEC and cloud via 5G and to the nearby RSU and other CAV/CVs via C-V2X technology.

The C-ITS Message Handling, since it receives those messages sent by the CAV/CVs and the same ones retransmitted by RSUs, will face duplications. Its function consists of storing in the LDM only one of the messages by applying a filter.

The LDM, as described in section 3.3.1, aggregates all incoming data, including the CAMs generated by the vehicles, and provides them to the Local Traffic State on demand.

Incidents dissemination

The TMC, using the Traffic strategy & incidents dispatcher function, monitors the status of the road network and detect incidents thanks to multiple data sources. Additionally, this function can receive a DENM transmitted by the CAV indicating a malfunction or an incident within the vehicle. This DENM also reaches the nearby vehicles and RSUs via 5G and C-V2X.

Regardless the data source, when an incident is detected, a start request is sent to the C-ITS Message Handling which, as for the strategy messages, it needs to ask the LDM for specific geographical information to generate the DENM that will be transmitted to the stations down on the road.

When the incident is no longer active, the TMC sends a stop request to finalize the dissemination of the C-ITS messages (DENM).

Figure 39: UC2 UML sequence diagram - scenario 1 'Management of high priority vehicles'

The Traffic Management System receives CAMs from vehicles and the Emergency Management System (for the EV), and it manages priority request for the EV in order to modify the traffic plans to open green light to it along the corridor. Then the TMS sends DENM messages to the vehicles with the aim of reporting them about a reserved lane for the EV. MAPEM and SPATEM messages are going to be generated to internally validate information about the road infrastructure and traffic signals.

Figure 40: UC2 UML sequence diagram - scenario 2 'Advanced traffic management based on real-time response'

The Traffic Management and/or Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning receives CAM messages (both with speed and location, and origin-destination information) from the vehicles. Then, its internal modules, Traffic Metrics Generator and Traffic Status Assessment, with information from the TMS, internally calculates the optimized route planning, and sends DENM messages to vehicles informing about the traffic status so that they could manage to select the optimized route to arrive to their destinations.

Figure 41: UC2 UML sequence diagram - scenario 3 'VRUs protection'

All cameras detect road users, together with their location, speed and predicted trajectory. This information is sent to the Collision Risk Estimator, which calculates the risk of collision between vehicles and VRUs detected and sends warning to road users involved, by means of risks alerts to VRUS and DENM messages to CVs and CAVs.

3.4.3.1.1. Message exchange

Once the general view of the exchange of information is shown, detailed specifications of each type of message or data exchanged between the different services is provided, in accordance with the arrows shown within the UML sequence diagrams and considering the involved functional components described in section 3.4.1.

For this purpose, the detailed information regarding messages and other types of data exchange is shown by means of tables that contain descriptions about the following features associated to these data: type of message, identifying the name of the message or other type of information; the purpose of sending it; the standard version for each type of message, if it is the case; and the data format used for ensuring that both emitter and receiver could interchange the information in a proper way. Following Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4 show this detailed information respectively for scenario 1 'Management of high priority vehicles', for scenario 2 'advanced traffic management based on real-time response', and for scenario 3 'VRUs protection'.

Type of message	Purpose	Standard	Data format
CAM (Cooperative Awareness Message)	To send location and speed from CVs, CAVs and EV to the C-ITS Message and User Handling, and from this service to the Digital Twin	ETSI EN 302 637-2	ASN.1 binary

DENM (Decentralized Environmental Notification Message)	To send a warning from the Digital Twin to CVs and CAVs about a reserved lane for the EV	ETSI EN 302 637-3	ASN.1 binary
Corridor assignment, start and cancellation	To send the assignation of emergency corridor to the vehicle, the beginning of the EV circulation along the emergency corridor and finally the cancellation of the corridor, from the Firefighters' management system (Mycelium) to the Digital Twin	-	Proprietary format
Priority request	To send priority request for EV from the Digital Twin to the traffic controllers	-	Proprietary format
MAPEM (Map Extended Message) – optional	In PoDIUM only used to internally validate the road infrastructure from the traffic controller	ETSI TS 103 301	Proprietary format
SPATEM (Signal Phase and Timing Extended Message) - optional	In PoDIUM only used to validate internally the timing of traffic lights	ETSI TS 103 301	Proprietary format

Table 2: Messages exchange informion for UC2 - scenario 1 'Management of high priority vehicles'

Type of message	Purpose	Standard	Data format
CAM (Cooperative Awareness Message)	To send location and speed from CVs and CAVs to the C-ITS Message and User Handling, and from this service to the Digital Twin	ETSI EN 302 637-2	ASN.1 binary
CAM (Cooperative Awareness Message)	To send the journey plan, including origin and destination, from CVs and CAVs to the Digital Twin	ETSI EN 302 637-2 (with proposed extension; see 3.4.3.2)	ASN.1 binary
DENM (Decentralized Environmental Notification Message)	To send a warning from the Digital Twin to CVs and CAVs about the existence of a disruptive event at a certain road stretch	ETSI EN 302 637-3	ASN.1 binary

Table 3: Messages exchange information for UC2 - scenario 2 'Advanced traffic management based on real-time response'

Type of message	Purpose	Standard	Data format
CAM (Cooperative Awareness Message)	To send location and speed from CVs and CAVs to the C-ITS Message and User	ETSI EN 302 637-2	ASN.1 binary

	Handling, and from this service to the Digital Twin and the Collision Risk Estimator		
DENM (Decentralized Environmental Notification Message)	To send risk alerts from Collision Risk Estimator to the C-ITS Message and User Handling, and then to CVs and CAVs	ETSI EN 302 637-3	ASN.1 binary
Collision risk warning for VRUS	To send VRUs a warning when there is a risk of collision with a CV/CAV, from the Collision Risk Estimator to the VRU Manager, and then to VRU APP (mobile phone and/or wearable device)	-	Proprietary format

Table 4: Messages exchange information for UC2 - scenario 3 ‘VRUs protection’

3.4.3.2. Semantic interoperability aspects

This chapter includes a description of issues considered when a deviation from the standard is proposed for a certain type of message or exchange of information. In this case, in UC2 scenario 2 ‘advanced traffic management based on real-time response’ there is a proposition of extension for a CAM message with the purpose of sending the journey plan, including its origin and destination, from the CVs and CAVs to the Digital Twin.

ETSI EN 302 637-2 [5] proposes a ‘PathHistory’ data field that intends to represent the vehicle’s recent movement over some past time. In this scenario there is a need to obtain the route that the vehicle is going to do in the future, so the destinations of the vehicles are needed to optimise the traffic flow and select the most appropriate strategy to control the network. For this reason, a proposition of using this data field to provide the next route of the vehicle, instead of the previous one, is considered, since there is no data field in the ETSI standard dedicated to this purpose.

For the management of this deviation of the standard, it is proposed to consider its extension, to avoid losing the previous functionality already included in the last version of the standard.

4. Use Case 3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

Use case 3 will be demonstrated on the cross-border AP7 highway between Spain and France, between the high-transited towns of La Junquera and Le Boulou. The aim is to ensure smooth and safe traffic management, while enabling interoperability and validating new PDI functionalities, by leveraging and merging data from connected and automated vehicles, traffic cameras and third-party providers.

4.1. Scenario Descriptions

Use Case 3 explores two scenarios:

- 1) Daily commuting service supported by traffic management.
- 2) Safety incidents across borders mitigated through a continuous, efficient, and resilient service.

In both scenarios, the main Platform (Edge and Cloud servers) including the AAE Traffic Management Centre, the MILLA Fleet Management Cloud, the ENIDE Transport Service Orchestrator Cloud, 1 CAV, 3 CVs, a number of traffic cameras (infrastructure sensors), the shuttle Passenger App and the VRU's Safety App are included as actors. In the second scenario, the VRU does not play any role.

Scenario 1 demonstrates an on-demand commuting and goods transfer service across the France-Spain border using an automated Electric Vehicle (EV) shuttle. The aim is to maximise the use of the shuttle and minimise its presence on the road without passengers onboard or without goods loaded. The shuttle will work on continuous service during peak hours, and on-demand during off-peak hours through a dedicated mobile app. Traffic status will be monitored through data received by the traffic cameras, connected vehicles, and third-party providers, and thereafter appropriate traffic management strategies are launched automatically by the Platform's Traffic Management Centre. Additionally to the CAV shuttle, 3 more CVs will be circulating in the highway and will be receiving and responding to the Platform's strategies.

Scenario 1 is partitioned into consecutive phases. Shuttle booking, shuttle departure, shuttle journey and shuttle arrival, while just before arriving at the stop, the VRU collision risk analysis comes into play. The same happens during departure of the shuttle.

At the beginning, a new passenger makes a shuttle booking by consulting the Passenger App (Figure 42). The app intercommunicates with the MILLA and ENIDE cloud to provide useful info to the user, and handles the booking. The scheduling function defines the journey destination and time of departure, which can vary as the service is "on-demand". As the CAV shuttle is on the road, it sends and receives data to/from the Platform and surrounding CVs. When approaching the destination stop, any pedestrians on its way are warned in case there is risk getting hurt by it. Finally, the shuttle arrives at destination, picks up new passengers and repeats the process.

SCENARIO 1

Figure 42: UC3 Scenario Description for scenario 1 - Daily commuting across borders

Scenario 2 follows the point of view of the automated shuttle and demonstrate solutions offered by the new CCAM services to mitigate potential risks in its journey. The safe and timely response and mitigation of risky scenarios are key factors here, as well as robustness, low latency and high bandwidth communications taking advantage of edge computing, allowing for real-time supervision and the future deployment of fully autonomous shuttles without a security operator.

This scenario is divided in two distinct “safety” typologies:

- a) Incident caused by another vehicle, be it automated or conventional.
- b) Self-reported issue by the shuttle during its journey.

Scenario 2-a is organised in consecutive phases (see [Figure 43](#)). Firstly, when a cross border incident, e.g. a stopped vehicle, is detected (by the cameras or by passing-by vehicles with sensors), the platform disseminates a hazard alert, processes it, and launches new traffic strategies to the CVs approaching the incident area, including the CAV shuttle. The vehicles respond with the appropriate manoeuvres and speed adjustments, either manually or automatically.

When approaching the incident area, the shuttle hands-over control to the Telesupervisor (via the MILLA cloud), who monitors the situation live and helps it to navigate the area safely. Finally, after leaving the incident area, the Telesupervisor hands over control to the CAV shuttle, which continues on its way to the destination. Meanwhile, the MILLA cloud system updates the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) and informs the passengers via the ENIDE app.

In Scenario 2-b (see again [Figure 43](#)), the CAV shuttle is forced to drive slower (60 km/h) on the highway due to a safety-related internal issue. The CAV shuttle self-reports about its issue and abnormal driving behaviour to the surrounding vehicles as well as to the Platform via a DENM alert. In this occasion, multiple actions are launched in parallel: The Telesupervision is notified and activated, while the Platform re-transmits the DENM alert to approaching vehicles that are further away (and out of range) and generates the corresponding traffic strategies for a “mobile hazard”. The shuttle Passenger App is also updated about the issue and the new ETA. The Telesupervisor supports the CAV shuttle to arrive to the destination safely.

Figure 43: UC3 Scenario Description for scenario 2 - Safety incidents across borders

4.2. Communication Aspects

This section looks into the communication architecture and related entities, as well as the communication features and networks that will be used in Use Case 3.

4.2.1. Communication Architecture

Figure 44: UC3 Communication view

The communications architecture of UC3, as depicted in the Figure above, illustrates the integration of various communication technologies to support the seamless interaction between vehicles, infrastructure, and users within the transportation ecosystem.

The local data processing and communications layer is composed of several key components, including VRUs, CVs, CAVs, and RSUs. These elements utilize advanced communication technologies to enhance vehicular and traffic management systems.

CVs are equipped with wireless communication technology, allowing them to exchange data with other vehicles, infrastructure, or networks. This enables a wide range of applications, from safety features to traffic flow optimization. CAVs take this a step further by integrating hardware and software that enable them to communicate wirelessly with their surroundings, including other vehicles, traffic signals, and cloud services. These capabilities allow CAVs to perform many of the operational and tactical functions needed for navigating on-road traffic, potentially without human intervention.

Both CVs and CAVs leverage direct communication technologies C-V2X (LTE-PC5), in addition to cm-Wave 5G /4G networks. These technologies provide the necessary bandwidth and low latency for the rapid exchange of information critical for the functioning of connected and automated vehicles.

In this system, a user of the shuttle service, referred to as a "Shuttle user," connects to the MEC platform via cm-Wave 5G/4G communications to access on-demand shuttle services. Similarly, VRUs and RSUs also connect to the MEC through cm-Wave 5G/4G. RSUs have an additional connection through C-V2X (LTE-PC5) directly to CVs and CAVs, facilitating a comprehensive network of vehicular communication.

4.2.2. Communication Entities

4.2.2.1. Connected Vehicles (CV) & Connected Automated Vehicle (CAV)

Role:

In UC3, CAVs and CVs use two communications technologies, C-V2X (LTE-PC5) and cellular network (preferably 5G, but 4G is also possible), to inform about:

- All of them communicate their location, speed and direction with CAMs.
- Vehicles equipped with LiDAR and RADAR communicate detected objects with CPMs.
- CAVs communicate their abnormal status e.g. break down, with DENMs.

They receive:

- CAMs from their neighbours and CPMs from their neighbours and MEC to create an awareness view.
- Information about abnormal situations within DENM from neighbour CAVs and the MEC.
- Suggested cooperative manoeuvres within IVIMs and MCMs from the MEC. They process and assess this information, advising the driver with an HMI, and CAVs could automatically activate the manoeuvre according to their state and environment.

Implementation:

- CVs and CAVs are equipped with an On-Board Unit (OBU) that consists of a single computer executing the ETSI ITS communication protocol stack. This unit is complemented by a cellular modem for transmitting and receiving C-ITS messages over the IP protocol. Additionally, it is connected to a commercial equipment provided by Cohda Wireless or Commsignia, enabling the transmission of messages over C-V2X.
- C-ITS messages are periodically transmitted according to ETSI standards and simultaneously over both technologies. The reasoning for transmitting simultaneously in both technologies is that C-V2X is used for direct V2V communications, ensuring low-latency transmission when vehicles are within coverage range of each other even in areas lacking cellular coverage. Communication V2I is mainly conducted using cellular networks due to their extensive coverage compared to potential networks deployed through C-V2X RSUs. However, in regions identified for insufficient 4G or 5G coverage, operators can strategically deploy RSUs to fill coverage gaps and eliminate areas of the road lacking connectivity. This approach enhances the reliability and effectiveness of connected vehicle communication systems in diverse geographical scenarios.

4.2.2.2. Roadside Units (RSU)

Role:

In UC3, the RSU plays a pivotal role in facilitating direct communication between connected road users (CVs/CAVs) and the broader transportation infrastructure. Through C-V2X (LTE-PC5), the RSU (as well as the OBU) enables vehicles to exchange C-ITS messages (CAM, IVIM, MCM, CPM, MAPEM) with each other and with the infrastructure (MEC). This ensures a high-speed, reliable link that is crucial for the safety and efficiency of vehicular operations.

The C-V2X (LTE-PC5) connection in UC3 provides ad-hoc complementarity and redundancy to ensure seamless connectivity even in spots with suboptimal 5G signal quality (e.g. due to geographical barriers). Furthermore, the RSU is instrumental in maintaining uninterrupted connectivity in cross-border scenarios. It seamlessly takes over the management of all communications between the CVs/CAVs and cloud computing services, as well as the MEC, during inter-PLMN handovers (PLMN means Public Land Mobile Network). This capability is essential for ensuring uninterrupted service and data flow, even as vehicles cross from one country to another.

By acting as a complementary conduit for vehicle data, the RSU ensures that the MEC platform receives the information it needs to optimize traffic management and vehicle routing decisions, thereby improving the safety and efficiency of road transportation systems.

Implementation:

The RSU is connected through a cm-Wave 5G/4G connection to the MEC as well as through direct communication (C-V2X LTE-PC5) to the CV/CAVs.

4.2.2.3. Sensor Processing Unit (SPU) – Traffic cameras

Figure 45: Traffic camera models used in UC3: left- *AXIS Q6225-LE PTZ*; right- *AXIS P1467-LE*

Role:

The LL in UC3 (AP7/E9 cross-border highway) will feature between 4-5 installed traffic cameras. The live video feed from the cameras will be transmitted to the MEC for processing via AI video analytics (see further below, in Section 4.4 *Services & Data exchange*). The processed feed will provide real-time data regarding average traffic volume, as well as identification of any obstacles (stopped vehicles) in sight.

Implementation:

The model of the cameras will be either *AXIS Q6225-LE PTZ* (Figure 45, left image) or *AXIS P1467-LE* (Figure 45, right image). 3-4 of the cameras will be already pre-installed, as part of the 5GMED project [31], which runs in the same LL location. In PoDIUM we plan to install an additional 1-2 cameras, in other spots of the highway and/or facing the opposite traffic direction. The cameras will be placed either on an existing pole or variable-message panel, or on a new pole that PoDIUM will set, which will also feature a wind/solar energy generator (e.g. Camera ID 03 in the table below).

For implementing the remote connection to the MEC, the cameras will have a specific interface that can be managed and accessed remotely. The camera will be wirelessly connected (cm-Wave 5G) to the corresponding MEC(s) via 5G router, co-installed in the same location as the camera. The wireless connection allows more flexibility in the installations. In a real deployment scenario, the cameras could be connected via optical fibre. However, obtaining permits for installing optical fibres in said locations would be too complicated, therefore the wireless connectivity option was preferred.

An overview of the planned cameras is provided in the table below. The locations are indicated as “highway kilometer from French border”, measured on the south direction (driving from France towards Spain).

The plan is for the 5GMED cameras to be installed by Q2 2024. The 1-2 PoDIUM cameras will either be installed simultaneously, or at a further date with a tentative milestone for completion before the end of the year.

	Camera model	Km from French border	Support	Orientation – Facing towards vehicles coming from:	Project
01	PTZ - AXIS Q6225-LE 50 Hz	0,000	Pole	France	5GMED
02	fixed - AXIS P1467-LE	0,055	VMS	Spain	5GMED
03	fixed - AXIS P1467-LE	2,800	Pole (solar/wind)	Spain	PoDIUM
04	PTZ - AXIS Q6225-LE 50 Hz	3,700	Pole	France	5GMED
05	PTZ - AXIS Q6225-LE 50 Hz	6,500	Pole	France	5GMED
06	PTZ - AXIS Q6225-LE 50 Hz	7,150	Pole (solar/wind)	France	PoDIUM (optional)

Table 5: Overview of planned cameras in LL of UC3

4.2.2.4. Vulnerable Road User (VRU)

Role:

The VRU is represented by a pedestrian with a smartphone that wishes to take the shuttle CAV of the UC3 scenario and he/she is involved in two different roles.

1. In the first role, the VRU functions as a client of the shuttle CAV, utilizing the "**Passenger App**" on their smartphone. This application facilitates interaction with the shuttle service by allowing the user to book the CAV, receive crucial information regarding the service's time schedule and stay informed about any modifications or delays resulting from traffic incidents.
2. The second role involves the VRU acting as a pedestrian in the vicinity of the shuttle stop, necessitating safety precautions to prevent collisions with the shuttle CAV or other CVs. To enhance safety, the VRU employs the "**Safety App**" on their smartphone, which triggers an alarm in situations where a high probability of collision is detected.

Moreover, the VRU actively transmits and receives C-ITS messages to and from the MEC. These messages are used for calculating the collision risk and alert the pedestrian and/or neighbour vehicles, if necessary.

Implementation:

The pedestrian uses an Android smartphone connected to an available public cellular network. Given the relaxed timing constraints owing to the relatively low speeds of pedestrians and vehicles within parking areas, the connectivity technology can be either 5G or 4G.

On this Android operating system, we deploy the communication protocols stack, the Passenger App and the Safety App, all of them communicate with their respective servers in the Edge or Cloud, through the cellular network using the IP protocol.

The communication protocols stack is in charge to periodically transmit information about the position and movements of the VRU to the MEC and receive the position and movement of surrounding vehicles, as well as collision risk alarms from the MEC. For this, it uses ETSI C-ITS messages, specifically, the VRU transmits VAMs and is able to receive CAMs, CPMs and DENMs. This application provides the whole ETSI ITS communication protocols stack (GeoNetworking, Basic Transport Protocol (BTP) and Facilities messages), transmitted over IP and programmed for Android.

The Safety App implements the HMI to notify collision risk alarms to the user. These alarms are generated by calculating the collision probability, which is computed in both, the smartphone and in the MEC. By calculating it in the smartphone, we plan to evaluate its viability by assessing CPU consumption and response time. When calculated in the MEC, we are going to use DENM messages to notify the collision risk to the VRU.

The Passenger app communicates via 4G/5G mobile networks with the corresponding ENIDE cloud (see further below). Information exchanged includes MILLA shuttle booking requests and

confirmations, availability of the on-demand service and shuttle capacity, and relevant trip info such as current location and estimated time of arrival of the shuttle, traffic state along the route, etc.

4.2.2.5. Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)

Role:

In UC3, the MEC platform occupies a central role by integrating and processing data from both infrastructure sensors and connected road users. This data, encompassing a wide array of inputs from the immediate environment, is transmitted to the MEC where it is synthesized into a comprehensive global environment model, effectively creating a digital twin of the real-world traffic scenario. Leveraging this model, the Local TMC (see further below, in Section 4.4.1.3) deployed in every MEC formulates and dispatches coordinated plans for cooperative driving manoeuvres, issuing actionable recommendations to all participating road users. This coordination is crucial for optimizing traffic flow and enhancing road safety through the synchronized execution of driving manoeuvres.

To ensure seamless mobility across different regions and countries, UC3 employs a network of MEC platforms as illustrated in the Figure 46 below. These are strategically implemented to cater to specific geographic areas, thereby facilitating localized processing and decision-making that aligns with regional traffic conditions and regulations. Furthermore, these MECs are interconnected with country-level cloud computing resources, which orchestrate V2X services within a country. This hierarchical structure enables efficient data management and service delivery on a national scale while supporting the unique requirements of each region.

In the context of cross-border scenarios, UC3 takes a pioneering approach by integrating two cloud computing systems. This dual-cloud setup is designed to manage the complexities of cross-border mobility, ensuring that vehicles can seamlessly transition between countries without disruption to the V2X services they rely on. Through this innovative infrastructure, UC3 addresses the challenges of interoperability and continuity in cross-border transportation, paving the way for international cooperative driving and mobility solutions.

Implementation:

The MEC is wirelessly connected to the public 5G network, which is specifically configured to meet certain Service Level Agreements (SLAs). These SLAs are designed to guarantee the latency and throughput requirements that are crucial for the successful implementation of UC3, as identified in the early stages of the project.

Figure 46: Edge clouds in a UC3 cross-border scenario

4.2.2.6. Cloud servers

AAE Platform Cloud for the Global TMC

Role:

Cloud servers are used for the coordination of the individual Edge servers (MEC). The role of the Cloud server is to host the Global TMC, which ensures the harmonization of traffic strategies across several adjacent highway sections handled by the MECs.

Following the structure defined in the 5GMED project, due to legal restrictions regarding national data of vehicles and road users, 2 Cloud servers (hosting 2 Global TMC platforms) will be set up by AAE, one dedicated to managing the MECs on the Spanish highway side, and one on the French side.

Implementation:

The AAE Platform Cloud will be deployed over Amazon Web Services and will communicate with the MECs via the Internet (cable connection).

Additionally, the two cross-border Clouds must communicate with each other (via the internet), to exchange relevant traffic and incident data which can affect the traffic strategies across borders, such as the location of an incident (stopped vehicle or traffic jam), or the applicable traffic strategy (e.g. speed limitation) on the adjacent highway section to the border.

ENIDE & MILLA Clouds for passenger App and shuttle fleet management

Role:

The Clouds for passenger App and shuttle fleet management contain 3 elements; a mobile application for the passenger, a cloud for the mobile application to provide functionalities and a cloud fleet manager for the management of Milla vehicles.

Implementation:

The application will be compatible with Android OS and with mobile connectivity. The Cloud of the mobile application (ENIDE Cloud) will be deployed in AWS [44]. The MILLA Cloud Fleet Manager is deployed on an OVH server [43], located in Gravelines, France.

4.2.3. Communication Features

4.2.3.1. 5G/4G cm-Wave

Purpose:

In UC3 the cm Wave is used for the standard cellular communication between communication entities and the MEC-Server.

Implementation:

To experiment real-world conditions, UC3 leverages the public 5G/4G mobile network. The primary frequency bands utilized are the 3.5 GHz and the 700 MHz bands. The 3.5 GHz band is chosen primarily for its ability to provide high throughput, essential for supporting data-intensive equipment such as video cameras. On the other hand, the 700 MHz band is used to ensure extensive 5G/4G coverage under all circumstances. For cross-border scenarios, accessing the public 5G/4G mobile networks of both countries involved is crucial to maintain seamless connectivity and service continuity.

4.2.3.2. C-V2X LTE-PC5

Purpose:

Cellular-V2X (C-V2X) is the umbrella term which encapsulates all 3GPP V2X technologies, including both direct (PC5) and mobile network communications (Uu). In 2016, 3GPP published V2X specifications based on LTE as the underlying technology. It is generally referred to as "cellular V2X"

(C-V2X) to differentiate itself from the 802.11p based V2X technology. The direct communication between vehicle and other devices (V2V, V2I) uses so-called PC5 interface.

C-V2X enables road users equipped with a C-V2X OBU to communicate directly with each other, as well as connect to C-V2X-compatible RSUs. The RSU plays a crucial role in this network by forwarding traffic to the MEC server or other connected entities, thus providing an additional, essential communication pathway.

Implementation:

The C-V2X LTE-PC5 technology, operates in the 5.9 GHz band, same as ITS-G5. Specifically for Europe it the spectrum allocation is between 5875 – 5905 MHz. Optimized for vehicular communication, it supports effective typically have around 300 to 500 meters in urban settings, but this can extend to around 1000 meters under optimal conditions with clear line-of-sight and minimal interference [18]. In UC3, CVs/CAVs are equipped with C-V2X (LTE-PC5) compatible Commsignia or Cohda MK6 OBUs, and so are the RSUs installed on the roadside.

4.3. Connected Entities

This chapter describes the functional and IT views of all the connected entities for UC3, including the CAV, CVs, RSUs and VRUs. Some of those entities are shared between UC2 and UC3, which leads to having chapters not covered in this UC3 section in order to avoid duplicated content.

4.3.1. Connected and Automated Vehicles

UC3 CAV consists of a shuttle bus with autonomous driving functions and hybrid connectivity (cellular network and C-V2X (LTE-PC5)). Other CVs implement a subset of functionalities of the CAV architecture.

Since the same architecture and implementation for the CAV and CVs for UC3 is leveraged in UC2 as well, the functional and IT views have been previously described in the UC2 section (refer back to chapter 3.3.1.1, page 51).

However, some vehicle functions are used differently between UC2 and UC3, since the scenarios and use cases address different needs. The following subsection presents a set of relevant sequence views from UC3.

4.3.1.1. Sequence view between functional components

Message exchange with PoDIUM platform

The following sequence diagrams show the transmission and reception of CAM, and the reception of the UC3-related messages including CAM, CPM, DENM, IVIM and MCM.

Generation and transmission of CAMs and CPMs

All kinds of connected vehicles, including the CAV and CVs, will generate CAM messages according to the ETSI C-ITS standard (see also Table 6). However, CPM messages will be sent only from those vehicles with perception capabilities (CAV and a specific CV).

As shown in Figure 47, such messages will reach the platform at the MEC via 5G and C-V2X (LTE-PC5). CAM and CPM messages require, among other information, the location of the vehicle sender, while the CPMs require, additionally, the perceived objects detected by the perception system. Both the location and the objects are extracted from the LDM, where they have been previously stored (see Figure 23).

Figure 47: Diagram of the generation and transmission of CAMs and CPMs

Generation of DENM messages

Figure 48 shows the situation when the CAV detects an internal issue that prevents itself to continue with autonomous mode. In this case an alert is sent from the ADF function to reach the V2X stack that invokes the DEN (Decentralized Environmental Notification) service to build a standard DENM message, which is disseminated via 5G and C-V2X (LTE-PC5) to the nearby vehicles and RSUs, as well as to the MEC to let the TMC know about this issue, which will potentially lead a strategy change.

Figure 48: Diagram of the generation of a DENM message from the UC3 CAV.

Reception of CPMs generated by the infrastructure

The CPMs generated by the infrastructure are received by the vehicles using 5G and C-V2X (LTE-PC5) (through the RSUs) and are stored in the LDM, as shown in Figure 49. This LDM data is used by the ADF function as shown in the diagram of Figure 23.

Figure 49: Diagram of the reception of CPM at vehicle level

Reception of DENM, IVIM and MCM from the infrastructure

When new strategies and incidents are generated by the TMC with the goal to inform the road users, they reach the CAV/ CVs via 5G and C-V2X (LTE-PC5) and are processed by the application layer of the V2X stack function, which checks the relevancy of those messages for the vehicle and sends the appropriate information to the LDM. The HMI and the ADF retrieve such information (and other) from the LDM to perform their operations (refer to Figure 23 for more details).

Figure 50: Flow diagram of the reception of DENM, IVIM and MCM from the infrastructure

4.3.1.1. HMI

The CAV/CV HMI is designed to show real-time incidents and manoeuvres relevant for the vehicle/driver, as well as the current position and other dynamics information.

As represented by the wireframe in Figure 51, the current speed of the vehicle and icons representing the incidents are displayed on the left side of the screen. The upper part of the screen shows the manoeuvres applicable for the driver/vehicle at that moment. The CAV will apply those manoeuvres automatically, while the drivers of the CV will check the HMI to be advised about the recommended manoeuvre.

Figure 51: HMI wireframe for UC3 CV

4.3.2. Vulnerable Road Users (VRU)

In UC3, the VRU is a pedestrian equipped with a smartphone connected to the available cellular network. It utilizes two applications, the "Passenger App" for accessing shuttle bus services and the "Safety App" to enhance safety by preventing collisions with connected vehicles. In order to transmit C-ITS messages, we have developed a software for Android that implements all necessary ETSI ITS communication protocols and messages (see also Table 6).

4.3.2.1. Functional view

This section describes the functional view of the connected vehicle whose blocks diagram is shown in the figure below.

Figure 52: VRU's functional view diagram

The functionalities that are deployed in a VRU's smartphone and their current development are described next:

Communication Cellular (5G/4G):

Native functionality that enables the smartphone to connect to Internet using the data service of the operator to which the pedestrian is subscribed. No changes or developments are required in this module. Other functionalities use it in order to connect to the cloud or to the MEC.

Localization (GNSS):

Native functionality that provides the device's localization information through a GNSS system. No changes or developments are required in this module. Other functionalities use it in order to obtain the device's current position, speed, acceleration and direction.

ETSI C-ITS communications stack for Android:

This functionality encodes/decodes the following standard ETSI C-ITS protocols:

- GeoNetworking: ETSI EN 302 636-4-1 V1.4.1 (2020-01) [32].
- Basic Transport Protocol (BTP): ETSI EN 302 636-5-1 V2.2.1 (2019-05) [33].
- Facilities messages: CAM (ETSI EN 302 637-2 V1.4.1 (2019-04), [34]), DENM (ETSI EN 302 637-3 V1.3.1 (2019-04), [35]), CPM (ETSI TS 103 324 V2.1.1 (2023-06), [25]) and VAM (ETSI TS 103 300-3 V2.2.1 (2023-02), [22]).

Based on pedestrian motion, positioning and timing, it generates VAMs, that are encoded and encapsulated over protocols Websocket/TCP/IP and transmitted through the cellular network to the V2X Gateway in the MEC. At the same time, it receives from the MEC Websocket/TCP/IP encapsulated CAM, DENM and CPM messages, which decodes and performs simple message processing functions, in order to upload relevant data to the VRU's Local Dynamic Map (LDM).

The current development state is in its final functional development phase. All standardized services have been developed and the application layer solutions are under development. Specifically, for the VRUs we have developed the following services: the Cooperative Awareness Basic Service (CA Basic Service), the Collective Perception Basic Service (CP Basic Service), the Decentralized Environment Notification Basic Service (DEN Basic Service) and the Vulnerable Road User Awareness Basic Service (VRU Basic Service) is almost finished, only lacking the clustering capabilities.

Local Dynamic Map (LDM):

The LDM is the functionality that contains and manages the database where all the information about the road elements known by the VRU is stored. It is populated with fixed information obtained from maps and information obtained from C-ITS messages provided by the communications stack functionality. The consumer of its information is the Safety App. The LDM follows the rules of standard ETSI EN 302 895 V1.1.1 (2014-09) [36].

The LDM development is currently adhering to an agile methodology, with its evolution marked by distinct phases. Initially, it commenced with the creation of a straightforward database, serving as a repository for all incoming C-ITS messages. Subsequently, a database aligned with standard requirements was developed, establishing a framework wherein data producers deposit information into the LDM, and data consumers extract relevant data pertinent to their needs. In the latest phase of development, the focus is on an advanced, graph-based LDM. This iteration not only aligns with standard specifications but also operates with enhanced efficiency, particularly in the handling of geoposition information. The structural design of the graph-based LDM facilitates faster storage, retrieval, and correlation of such information.

This ongoing stage is iterative, rigorously testing each change, improvement, or simplification to ensure a measurable performance boost without undue complexity. The fundamental concept is the utilization of a graph-based database, linking static and dynamic information seamlessly. For instance, a road "object" can be connected to "vehicle" objects through graph edges within the LDM. The advantages of this approach become evident when querying specific streets for vehicle positions.

The graph-based LDM enables swift retrieval of such information, with the added capability of integrating supplementary data, like map layouts, into safety-related applications. This integration proves invaluable in applications that require anticipation of movements by enhancing predictability substantially. By bridging static and dynamic data through a graph-based structure, the LDM enhances the overall efficiency and functionality of the system.

Contents of the LDM:

- Fixed elements:
 - o Roads: Lanes in the roads, direction of the lanes. The roads are stored as a sequence of segments
 - o Intersections: Connection between incoming and outgoing lanes
 - o Traffic signals
 - o Mobile elements
 - o Vehicles: Type of vehicle; last known position, direction, and speed of the vehicle; short-term predicted position, direction, and speed of the vehicle
 - o VRUs: Type of VRU; last known position, direction, and speed of the vehicle; predicted position, direction, and speed of the vehicle used in this UC
- Temporal events in the road:
 - o Event: Type of event; Additional information ...

Functionalities provided by the LDM:

- Registration / Deregistration of data provider applications and data consumer applications
- Subscribe / Unsubscribe for notifications to data consumers
- Storage of objects received from data providers during a time validity and within an area of maintenance

Safety App:

This functionality allows for the triggering of an alarm in the event of a high risk of collision. The collision probability is determined through two distinct methods. Firstly, an application within the MEC system, equipped with enough computational resources and access to a broader range of information in its LDM, calculates this probability. If the calculated probability surpasses a predefined threshold, an alarm is sent to the Safety App using a DENM message. The second method is executed in the same smartphone, which operates with more limited resources, both in terms of CPU capacity and data stored in the LDM, calculating its own collision probability. While the expectation is that the MEC-based computation will yield higher precision, concurrently calculating the collision probability on the smartphone allows us to evaluate its feasibility by assessing CPU consumption and response time, facilitating a comprehensive comparison of both approaches.

The evolution of the safety app aligns with an agile methodology, marked by the initial development of a fully functional yet relatively straightforward version. Subsequent enhancements involve the incorporation of additional features and structural modifications aimed at achieving optimal performance. The current iteration of the app estimates future positions for all dynamic elements within the C-ITS environment. Upon detecting a potential collision, it evaluates factors such as time to impact and the certainty of the prediction. For instance, in scenarios with low-speed intersections and a collision predicted 15 seconds ahead, no warning is issued. Conversely, if a collision is foreseen within 3 seconds in the same lane, a warning is promptly issued.

Notably, the safety app maintains uniformity across various versions, whether for MEC, OBU, or smartphones. Scalability considerations are backed by the LDM, employing a comprehensive graph database for the MEC version and a streamlined Python-based version for OBU and smartphone deployments, where data handling demands are lower. The app's code exhibits flexibility, enabling swift configuration or coding of any type of alarm as a feature. Presently, alerts are displayed on the frontend, representing the HMI.

While the current algorithm relies on basic physics trajectory calculations, future iterations contemplate employing more sophisticated techniques. These may include advanced algorithms such as Kalman Filters [46], recurrent neural networks, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [45], or even Markov Chains [47].

The development approach involves prototyping solutions with these advanced algorithms, rigorous testing, and, upon satisfactory results, integrating them into the overall solution. This iterative process ensures continual refinement and adaptability as the safety app evolves to meet emerging challenges and performance expectations.

Passenger App:

Figure 53: Passenger app functional view

Figure 53 provides a visual representation of the functions offered by a travel management system, structured around the user's interaction with the system. Centred on the figure of the user, the diagram expands into five main branches that detail the available functions:

- **Trip History:** This feature allows the user to access their reservation history, where they can review past trips and corresponding tickets.
- **Registered User:** In this section, a registered user has the ability to log into the system, view their personal profile, and cancel pre-planned trips.
- **Trip Search:** Here, the user can search for available travel routes by applying filters by date and destination, in addition to being able to access the details of the routes found.
- **Trip Reservation:** This feature guides the user through the process of selecting a specific route, choosing the date and time for the trip, and obtaining the travel ticket.
- **Travel:** Finally, during the travel phase, the user can check-in and access real-time information related to their ongoing trip.

4.3.2.2. Sequence view between functional components

This section shows the messages sequences between functional components of the VRU.

Awareness message exchange with MEC: CPM and VAM

The following sequence diagrams show the transmission and reception of C-ITS messages related with cooperative awareness that involve VRUs. Basically, VRUs transmit VAMs and receive and process CAMs and CPMs.

In order to have an awareness view of the vehicles and obstacles around them, VRUs rely on the fact that the MEC distributes the required information. This information can be in the form of CAM messages originated by CVs and CAVs and directly relayed by the MEC, without any modification, or in the form of CPMs generated by the MEC with the information stored in its LDM. Although the VRUs are able to accept both CAMs and CPMs, in UC3 we are only going to use CPMs as our intention is to

propose an optimized mechanism to propagate awareness information aggregating the information of several CAMs into a single CPM. For this reason, we only consider CPMs in the diagrams.

Transmission: VAM

Figure 54: Sequence of VAM transmission by the VRU

Reception: CPM

Figure 55: Sequence of a CPM reception by the VRU

Triggering of a collision risk alarm originated in the MEC

The following sequence diagram shows the sequence diagram of an alarm for high probability of collision between a VRU and a CV or CAV computed in the MEC. The used C-ITS message is the DENM [35], with the direct cause code 97 (collision risk) and sub cause code 4 (collision risk involving VRU).

Figure 56: High collision risk detected by the MEC

Triggering of a collision risk alarm computed in the VRU’s smartphone

The following sequence diagram illustrates the VRU’s smartphone detecting a high collision risk and the subsequent activation of the alarm. In this case, we have to bear in mind that the VRU’s LDM is constantly updated with the local position of the same VRU and of neighbour vehicles by receiving CPMs from the MEC.

Figure 57: High collision risk detected by the VRU

Passenger App

Figure 58: Passenger app Log in and booking sequence diagram

Figure 58 shows the steps that occur so that a user of the App authenticates on the server and can perform operations related to travel search, filtering, and travel reservations.

1. Login: The user begins the process by logging into the mobile application.
2. Authentication Token Return: After authentication, the passenger cloud server returns an authentication token to the mobile App.
3. Trip search: The user searches for trips through the mobile application.
4. Trips available to book: The server provides a list of available trips that the user can book.
5. Make a reservation: The user selects a trip and makes a reservation through the mobile application.
6. Ticket return: Finally, the server returns a travel ticket to the mobile application.

Each step involves a request and a response between the mobile application and the cloud server, indicating an interactive and dynamic process flow, which makes it easier for the user to manage their travel reservations.

Figure 59: Passenger App travel sequence diagram

Figure 59 represents how the user interacts after having obtained a travel ticket, to check in the shuttle and how they receive information in real time during the service. It also shows how the passenger cloud obtains real-time information from Milla's fleet manager.

1. Mobile Application Login: The user logs into the mobile application.
2. Auth Token Return: The Passenger API returns an auth token to the mobile app after login.
3. Ticket viewing: The user requests to view the tickets through the mobile application, and the passenger API provides the tickets.
4. Check-In: The user checks in through the mobile application.
5. Check-In Completed: The mobile application receives a confirmation that the check-in has been completed.
6. Get trip status: The mobile application requests the current trip status.
7. Real-time data return: The passenger API returns real-time data about the trip status to the mobile application.

On the other hand, a parallel interaction is observed with two other cloud services:

8. Request to start a trip to the Scheduler (Scheduler): The Scheduler receives a request to start a trip.
9. Programmer Response: A response is returned to the passenger cloud service.

10. Obtain service status from the Milla Cloud Service: The passenger cloud service queries the service status to the Milla Cloud Service.
11. Service Status: The Milla Cloud Service provides the service status to the passenger cloud service.
12. Service status update: Finally, the service status is updated in the passenger cloud service.

4.3.2.3. IT environment view

The IT environment view presents the software and hardware of the VRU:

- Smartphone: The VRU is equipped with a commercially available mid-range Android smartphone. As our plan is that any pedestrian can use both applications, we cannot set the smartphone requirements too high, so we target a mid-range device.
- Cellular NIC: In the project, the VRU will only be connected in the cm-Wave (FR1) band. As the potential target clients is very wide, we have to support the applications running over 5G and 4G networks.

4.3.2.4. HMI

UC3 uses two user applications with HMI, the "Safety App" and the "Passenger App". Next, we present the main characteristics of each app's HMI.

Safety App: The main purpose of this application is to alert the pedestrian VRU that, suddenly, there is the possibility that he/she collides with a moving vehicle (CV or CAV). As the smartphone could be on standby with the display off or in the VRU's pocket at the moment of this event, a sound alarm is the best choice. Therefore, the HMI to notify a collision risk alarm is a sound alert produced by the smartphone.

Optionally and for demo purposes only, the Safety App will have a frame that will display the VRU's position in the centre, and the known neighbour vehicles in their position relative to the VRU. An initial prototype is shown in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Safety App HMI showing nearby vehicles and "No Risk" sign

Passenger App: The HMI is still under development. The initial wireframes are being prepared around H1 2024.

4.3.3. RSUs

Connected vehicles need to interchange information between them. They also need to exchange information with functionalities provided by the infrastructure. For doing this, PoDIUM uses two complementary radio technologies, C-V2X and cellular networks.

To connect vehicles with the infrastructure (V2I and I2V), the usual option is to use the cellular network. To connect vehicles with vehicles, C-V2X enables direct V2V communications, while cellular networks always need a relay in the fixed infrastructure or in the network, so the model is V2I2V (Vehicle-to-Infrastructure-to-Vehicle) or V2N2V (Vehicle-to-Network-to-Vehicle). The main advantage of each one is that the V2V approach has lower delay, and V2N2V has more coverage, in fact, the coverage provided by the cellular network. Nevertheless, there are two cases where cellular networks are not well suited.

One is that there are always some black spots without coverage, and the other is when the user moves from one country to another that the handover between two different commercial operators is usually very slow, and produces a gap in coverage. One possible solution to solve the lack of connection of vehicles in these situations is to deploy RSUs that cover the specific areas involved in the problem. PoDIUM will demonstrate the case in the border between Spain and France, deploying RSUs in this area. So, during the time the vehicles are performing the handover between the Spanish operator and the French operator, C-ITS messages transmitted between vehicles and infrastructure will be relayed through those RSU.

4.3.3.1. Functional view

The functional view of the RSU is depicted in Figure 61. Its functionalities are described next.

Figure 61: RSU's functional view diagram

Communication C-V2X (LTE-PC5): This functionality represents the facility to transmit and receive messages over the radio interface using the sidelink communication LTE-PC5. No changes or developments are required in this module.

Communication Cellular (5G/4G): RSUs need to be connected to Internet to be able to forward C-ITS messages to and from the servers deployed in the MEC, also connected to Internet. This connection can be implemented in different ways. Due to its flexibility, PoDIUM has chosen to use the cellular interface provided by RSUs to implement this connectivity. Therefore, the "Communication Cellular"

functionality represents the cellular network IP-based interface already existing in the RSUs. No changes or developments are required in this module.

Localization (GNSS): Native functionality that enables synchronization for the LTE-PC5 communication channel. No changes or developments are required in this module.

C-V2X / IP Forwarder: C-ITS messages that are transmitted over LTE-PC5 need to use the ETSI ITS communication protocols GeoNetworking and BTP, and be encoded under certain rules. These functions are performed by an ETSI ITS communication protocols stack. Current commercial RSUs are already shipped with its own manufacturer's communications stack plus an API to externally access to their functions to transmit messages and to get the payload of the received ones. PoDIUM's approach is to use a centralized communication stack virtualized in the MEC, which provides much more flexibility in terms of CPU requirements, or load balancing, required when there are many vehicles under the coverage area of one or several RSUs. Therefore, the functionality "C-V2X / IP forwarder" is in charge to bypass the manufacturer's communications stack deployed in the RSU, and directly forward the C-ITS messages between the LTE-PC5 radio interface and the communications stack of the MEC. For doing this, first, it needs direct access to the radio interface of the LTE-PC5 and, second, to encapsulate C-ITS messages over TCP/IP to be able to transmit them firstly over the cellular network and then over the open Internet, passing through one or several Network Address Translators (NAT), until they get to the MEC.

The current development of this element is:

- We have successfully tested and installed the "C-V2X / IP forwarder" in a Cohda RSU MK6. For doing that we have used the Qualcomm Telematics SDK, which enables to access to the low functions of the Qualcomm's chipset SA515, performed in Cohda MK6 RSUs and OBUs.
- We have checked interoperability between a Cohda MK6 OBU with i2CAT's V2X stack, and the V2X Gateway in the MEC, with C-ITS messages going through a Cohda MK6 RSU. The global path of the C-ITS messages is: i2CAT V2X stack in a laptop - Ethernet - Cohda MK6 OBU - C-V2X transmission - Cohda MK6 RSU - Ethernet - V2X Gateway in the MEC.
- We have also checked interoperability of the "C-V2X / IP forwarder" using the V2X protocol stack provided by Cohda. In this case the path of the C-ITS messages is: V2X stack by Cohda in a Cohda MK6 OBU - C-V2X transmission Cohda MK6 RSU - Ethernet - V2X Gateway in the MEC.
- We have checked the correct operation of the "Communication C-V2X (LTE-PC5)" and "Localization (GNSS) functionalities.

Pending actions:

- To perform the same functionalities with Commsignia devices: In their case, it is more complicated because their Linux version is closed and minimal, so it is not possible to directly compile the required Qualcomm Telematics SDK for these platforms.
- To connect the RSUs using cellular communications, configuring their interfaces and providing the required IP configuration to make them accessible from Internet and from the OBUS, installing VPNs, if required.

4.3.3.2. Sequence view between functional components

The sequence diagram of Figure 62 shows the different steps taken among the different components to transmit messages between CVs / CAVs and the MEC using one RSU connected to Internet through a cellular network.

Figure 62: Message forwarding by the RSU between vehicles and the MEC

4.3.3.3. IT environment view

The IT environment is formed of Commsignia RSUs model ITS-RS4 (Figure 63 left), version D-W-C42x-SGLB, or Cohda RSUs model MK6 (Figure 63 right), supporting both DSRC/G5 and C-V2X, connected to Internet using their cellular interface.

Figure 63: RSU used in UC3. Models: Commsignia ITS-RS4 (left) and Cohda Wireless MK6 (right)

Their main characteristics are:

- NXP i.MX6 1 GHz CPU (RS4); NXP i.MX8 800 MHz CPU (MK6)
- 2 GB SDRAM (RS4); 1 GB SDRAM (MK6)
- 4 GB eMMC (RS4); 16 GB eMMC (MK6)
- 100/1000 Mbps Ethernet (RJ45, PoE)
- IEEE 802.11p radio: Autotalks Sector (RS4); NXP RoadLink SAF5400
- C-V2X radio: Qualcomm 9150 (RS4); Qualcomm SA515 (MK6)
- Hardware Security Module (HSM) – Autotalks Sector integrated (RS4)
- Wi-Fi interface: IEEE 802.11 b/g/n (RS4); IEEE 802.11 b/g/n/ac (MK6)
- Cellular interface: 4G (RS4); 4G/5G (MK6)

4.4. Services and Data Exchange

This section provides an overview of the platforms running for UC3 at functional and IT levels. Also, and a functional description of some relevant services is provided, with details about important data flows, protocols and data/messages involved.

4.4.1. Functional components

In this section we will describe:

- The Platform services (digital twin, traffic management, VRU safety, etc.) serving the vehicles and VRUs and running on the MEC and
- the On-demand shuttle serving specifically the MILLA shuttle and its passengers, which run on their respective clouds.

4.4.1.1. Overview of the Platform services

The Figure 64 below provides an overview of the functional components of the UC3 system, including the Edge and Cloud Traffic Management platforms & their respective Mobility HUBs, Digital Twin (LDM), Cooperative Awareness, Risk assessment, and V2X Gateway.

Figure 64: Detailed functional view diagram

4.4.1.2. Digital Twins and Advanced Perception Models

Local Dynamic Map (LDM)

The LDM is the service that contains and manages the database where all the information about the road elements and users is stored. It is populated with fixed information obtained from maps, information obtained from C-ITS messages transmitted by CAVs and CVs and information from road sensors, and provides information to applications and services requiring it.

The LDM follows the rules of standard ETSI EN 302 895 V1.1.1 (2014-09) [36].

The LDM is present in:

- The Digital Twin of the MEC: It provides information to other applications and services running in the MEC, and its information is forwarded to CVs and CAVs to assist them to perform ITS functionalities.
- Any CV/CAV: All information received through ITS messages and acquired with local sensors is stored in the vehicle's LDM and it could be used for autonomous driving, trigger alarms or advise the driver of different situations.
- Connected VRUs: All information received through ITS messages (CAM and CPMs) is stored in the VRU's LDM and it is used to evaluate risk probability.

While these three preceding instances of the LDM conceptually fulfil the same functionality, they diverge in the volume and types of stored data, geographic region that they cover, as well as the necessary performance for reading from and writing to the database. Each instance is tailored to the specific actor within the overall system, namely the Digital Twin, connected vehicle, and connected VRU.

The current development state of this component and its contents are the same as explained in the section of VRU's LDM.

Intelligent LDM Updater

The main concern about the LDM is that some of the stored objects (mainly vehicles and VRUs) are in continuous movement. The standard method for updating their position in the LDM is by receiving a new C-ITS message (CAM, VAM or CPM), informing about their new position. Nevertheless, this method has the disadvantage that when C-ITS messages are delayed or lost by the network, the LDM data can become inaccurate, or even critically inexact.

To solve the situation of having objects with too inaccurate positions in the LDM, those dynamic objects whose position has not been updated for more than 2 seconds with a new C-ITS message, are removed from the LDM. We have to bear in mind that most C-ITS messages are sent every 100 ms, therefore, 2 seconds means 20 lost messages. In the case of VAMs that are transmitted once per second, this timeout is extended to 5 seconds.

Nevertheless, for a fast vehicle, the fact of not updating its position for around 1 second represents a large error (one vehicle driving at 120 km/h, moves 33,33 m in one second). The "Intelligent LDM updater" is designed to minimize this error. Its main function is to update the LDM with estimated positions during the interval that goes since the last received C-ITS message until the moment that is deleted of the LDM.

Currently, the development of the updater is being carried out with the same methodology as all the components developed by i2CAT. Starting with a minimum valuable product, which is already developed. And then adding features, or proposing structural changes that, once prototyped; are tested to prove they really provide an enhancement.

The current implementation follows simple rules by predicting current positions of objects sensed with C-ITS messages containing information from the past and then checking how plausible this new computed position is.

In ongoing versions under development, the focus shifts towards the integration of neural networks and LSTM mechanisms. This advanced approach incorporates map layout information and factors in the typical manoeuvres that vehicles execute at specific points. Additionally, trajectory history is extended to enhance the precision of predicting expected behaviour.

Currently, we are developing this module by evaluating different estimation methods. We have no results yet.

AI video analytics (VA)

The **Video analytics** software module on the Edge receives in real-time the raw video footage and associated metadata from the traffic camera sensors installed on the highway. The frame-based data is analysed on the fly using Machine Learning (ML) object identification and visual analysis algorithms. As per the requirements in D2.3, the VA must be capable to process HD video feed of 15 fps in real-time. It transforms this feed into a stream of processed data that contains information about the vehicles viewed on the image, lane occupancy and their velocity. This stream of traffic data is then analysed by Local Traffic State calculator in the Local TMC (see below). The data is processed in 2 functions to detect:

- Video traffic analyser: density of vehicles and average traffic speeds in the road section.
- Video event detection functionality: identifying obstacles (stopped vehicles) on the highway.

4.4.1.3. Traffic Management

Local TMC

The Local TMC is a distributed application-level component, deployed at the Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) layer. Technically, this composite component is designed for managing traffic monitoring and control capabilities at a geographically delimited area, as foreseen in the UC3 at the MEC level. This includes acquiring data from sensors, connected vehicles and local telecommunication infrastructure inside the area. The Local TMC processes all acquired data in real-time, leveraging it to derive reliable information about traffic status and detected incidents. It updates the Global TMC at the Cloud layer about the local status of traffic and detected events, and maintains communication with the vehicles to relay traffic and safety messages via the V2X Gateway. In addition, the Local TMC provides data buffering, storage, and management capacities at the Edge (Edge Mobility HUB). This will allow for federated and distributed data architecture that increases the system's scalability and overall resilience and takes advantage of the resources available at the edge for more efficient, distributed and scalable computation.

The Local TMC generates **Traffic Management Strategies** for road section that it handles, which are then dispatched to the CVs via the V2X Gateways. These strategies are:

1. **Limit Speed** (lower than the normal legal speed limit of the road section).
2. **Increase distance from vehicle in front** (for safety reasons and to avoid rough braking).
3. **Avoid lane** (because of blockage e.g. in case of an obstacle, like a stopped vehicle or road works).

The TMC is updated in order to potentially trigger a new strategy through two processes.

Firstly, the TMC **monitors the local traffic flow state**. By combining different data sources (real time and historical data, cameras and CAVs) it is capable to detect an evolving agglomeration (potential traffic jam) in comparison to the previous traffic state. In that event, the TMC is can generate optimal Traffic Management Strategies to ensure safety and reduce the speed of evolution of the traffic jam, e.g. early on, start reducing the speed of incoming vehicles and increase the distance in order to obtain a smoother traffic flow with less abrupt braking.

Secondly, the TMC **listens for any road hazards/incidents/obstacles** as an input for its data strategies. Processed data from the VA and from the LDM, in term of detected obstacles on the road such as a stopped vehicle or other form that could affect road security or the traffic flow. Additionally, self-

emitted distress messages (in the form of DENM) from vehicles that have a technical issue and need to make an emergency stop can also be taken into account in the same way.

When such a hazard is detected, the Local TMC will use the V2X Gateway for communicating alert messages (in the form of DENM) to the CAV and CVs about obstacles or special situations in the road. As with the traffic strategies, those are messages to be sent to the CAV and CVs that are approaching the relevant section of the MEC area (e.g. 2 kilometres before the location of the hazard in the relevant highway direction). Vehicles on the opposite highway direction, or that have already passed the hazard location should not be notified.

When any new information about road obstacles or traffic flow is processed at Local TMC level, two actions are performed. First, this new data is sent to Global TMC in order to update its global overview about the traffic and incidents status of the MEC areas. Second, the information is analysed to anticipate possible traffic issues. If there is an issue, a Traffic Management Strategy would be generated and communicated to the CAV and CVs in the corresponding section of the MEC coverage area via the V2X Gateway.

It is important to note that each Local TMC will manage a defined area of the highway. Any event or traffic condition outside their own area will not be analysed nor controlled by this Local TMC. In those cases, another Local TMC will manage it (assuming it happens within its operational area). Furthermore, Global TMC has the full vision and control of the events and traffic conditions for all the segments managed by the different Local TMCs. As such, it is a very modular and versatile system, allowing deployment of multiple Local TMCs along longer highway stretches at different moments in time.

The Local TMC interacts with three key components: The Global TMC, the V2X Gateway, and the Video Analytics (VA). On their interaction, we can distinguish the following output/services data and dependencies:

Main outputs and/or services to the other components

To the V2X Gateway:

- Instructions to the CAV/CVs (velocity limitation, lane, distance) derived from the traffic management strategy.
- Obstacles detected.

To the Global TMC:

- Obstacles detected.
- Traffic flow.
- Local traffic strategy defined (if any).
- Data to be transferred to the Mobility Data HUB in the cloud.

Dependencies from other components

From the LDM:

- Raw CV data (location, speed, etc.)
- Statistically aggregated data on traffic flow and density per road section.
- Obstacles (stopped vehicles) identified by other CAVs (through CPM messages)
- Self-Alerts emitted by CVs, which have an issue and have stopped on the road, thus becoming an obstacle themselves. The implementation of this development in the TMC 2.0 is to be confirmed (see below).

From the Video Analytics:

- Average traffic flow and density through the road section where the camera is located in.
- Detected obstacles (stopped vehicles visible on the cameras)

From the Global TMC:

- Traffic strategy to be implemented locally in base of the defined global one. This overrides the local strategy.

The figure below shows the component view of the Local TMC, which includes the interfaces to external components and the internal components and interfaces.

Figure 65: Snippet of the Functional view depicting the functional modules of the Local TMC

According to the figure above, the internal components are described as follow:

Incident detection listener: It connects to the Edge Mobility Hub to receive from the LDM any road events/incidents detected by CAVs. This information will be sent to the Local Traffic Data Fusion, which will consolidate it into traffic and hazard information messages.

Local traffic State calculator: Provides local flow traffic and incidents (hazard) data. To do that it combines and fuses data from VA, LDM and 3rd party real time floating cat data providers.

Edge Monitor and Manager: Manages the traffic, incidents, and strategies information at edge level. It is the main component interface and controller between the Local TMC components and communicates the traffic status and strategies info to the Global TMC.

Local Strategy generator: It gets the traffic, detected road obstacles and incidents data to generate the traffic management strategies that will be operated at the edge level.

Traffic Strategy dispatcher: This component manages the interaction with the V2X Gateway for the communication of the traffic strategies to the CAV/CVs on the road layer.

Edge Mobility Hub: It is a middleware that manages real-time data for Local TMC, coordinating data from various sources and internal analytics to update Global TMC on traffic conditions. It securely streams video from roadside sensors and supports robust data exchange through an industrial message broker. The hub ensures secure, reliable messaging for IoT applications, even over unstable networks, and stores data for real-time and temporal analysis. It also facilitates the integration of third-party services for traffic management and other edge-based applications.

Global TMC

The Global TMC is the application-level component that has the full view of the traffic status from all the road sections managed by the different Local TMCs. To achieve this, every Local TMC remits the local traffic and incidents information, as well as any locally generated traffic strategies, to the Global TMC. Using this information, the Global TMC is able to implement traffic management strategies with a global view of road traffic.

First, the Global TMC is able to combine the traffic information from the Local TMCs and from external traffic data providers to provide a continuous view of the traffic status along the whole TMC coverage area of the highways. Finally, it can predict the evolution of the traffic flow in the monitored areas using the information captured (traffic and incidents).

Second, thanks to the higher visibility of the traffic conditions along the road, the Global TMC can generate more intelligent traffic strategies that were not possible to do at Local TMC level. Moreover, these strategies can be the same to all sections or dedicated to specific ones. Thanks to the

combination of the information received from the different Local TMCs, the Global TMC can anticipate the reaction to a predicted traffic issue in subsequent highway sections by implementing specific strategies for them.

It is important to note that the traffic strategies generated at Global TMC level have **higher priority** than the ones of the Local TMC. Therefore, they will be communicated to the Local TMCs, that will in turn be responsible for their local implementation by sending them to the CAV/CVs in the road layer via de V2X Gateway.

From previous experiences in cross-border use cases, differences in legislation and regulations between countries prevent the use of one common Global TMC on a cross-border highway section. Instead, **2 distinct Global TMCs** need to be set up, one covering one side of the border (Spain) and one covering the other (France) – refer to Figure 46. The two Global TMCs need to be **interoperable** and collaborate with each other, in order to ensure seamless Traffic management strategy implementation across the border in case of an incident with close proximity to the border (e.g. a stopped vehicle after the border section). To do that, the two Global TMCs need to communicate incident information between each other, as well as be aware of the traffic strategies implemented in the adjacent border sections. (Note that such interoperable collaboration between TMCs could also be useful in the case of different highway operators managing adjacent highway sections).

As introduced in the previous section, the Global TMC interacts with the multiple Local TMCs (on the Edge), as well as with other Global TMCs. To enable this interaction, we have the following outputs data and dependencies:

Main outputs and/or services to the other components

- To the Local TMC, global traffic strategy to implement on the specific Edge level.
- To other Global TMCs, for exchanging hazard information & traffic strategies among them.

Dependencies from other components

From the Local TMCs:

- Obstacles detected in the local level.
- Local traffic flows.
- Local Traffic strategies.

Figure 66: Snippet of Functional view depicting the functional components of the Global TMC

The internal components are described from the functional point of view below:

Global Monitor and Manager: It is the main controller of the data flow and functionalities of the component at the internal level as well as the main interface with the external components for the TMC operations.

Global strategy generator: It generates the traffic management strategies at global before being redirected to the different Local TMCs along the whole road site.

Global Traffic state: It analyses the traffic status at global level from the traffic information received from the Local TMCs.

Dashboard (HMI): It supports the traffic management process by providing a visual user interface with graphical and numeric metrics available to the traffic management operators.

Cloud Mobility HUB: It is a central data repository within Global TMC, facilitating data storage and access for mobility applications. It improves Global TMC's traffic analysis and management strategies by storing historical data for future traffic pattern studies and ML training. The HUB offers a secure API for data exchange with third-party mobility ecosystem members, featuring robust authentication and access controls to ensure secure communications and data integrity.

As shown in Figure 67, the Mobility HUB is composed of the following functional components:

- The HUB Control Manager handles data access by verifying permissions and managing data tasks, including verification and homogenization.
- The Identity Manager & Data Access Controller manages user roles and access, ensuring secure data exchange through validations and VPNs.
- The Data HUB API facilitates data exchange, supporting various technologies like REST and GraphQL [37], and allows real-time data and metadata integration.
- The Mobility Dashboard offers a web interface for customizable data visualization with geolocation and analytic features.

Figure 67: Mobility HUB internal functional view

TMC 2.0 development roadmap

1. Update the traffic calculation model with real-time location data and vehicle trajectories:

Incorporate and integrate real-time data on the location and trajectories of connected vehicles together with other data sources to generate traffic information.

2. Expansion of inter-communication capabilities with other Global TMCs:

Expand the protocol and implementation of inter-TMC communication (Global TMC) to give it the ability to: exchange information on sets of segments considered “close to the border”, communicate the location of a hazard at the segment level and generate own strategies based on to hazard information from the other TMC.

3. Generation of obstacle information on the road from CPM messages received from CAVs:

Real-time collection in the LDM of CPM messages sent by the different CAVs. Extraction of hazard information from the LDM related to an obstacle on the road (stopped vehicle as detected by the in-vehicle sensors of the CAVs), via the verification of the speeds reported in said CPM messages. Generate obstacle alert input information to be processed by the TMC.

4. Definition and implementation of communication interfaces with V2X Gateway and LDM:

Adaptation and expansion of current communication protocols and interfaces for integration with the V2X gateway as well as the LDM system of the project partners. The appropriate interfaces will be implemented for the reception and sending of data provided for by the new functionalities described.

5. Receive and process Hazard alerts from identified vehicles:

For identified vehicles, the ability to receive information from DENM messages about possible incidents in them. Management and treatment of this alert as a validated road hazard. Communication of the hazard to the V2X gateway and generation of strategies as appropriate.

This was also part of the storyboard UC3 Scenario 2 (MILLA CAV having a technical issue and self-emitting a DENM alert received by the Platform). This development avenue is being assessed currently. A decision whether to include it in the TMC 2.0 development roadmap for PoDIUM or not will be taken within the next months.

4.4.1.4. C-ITS Message handling (V2X Gateway)

Message transmission among vehicles largely depends on the radio technology employed, specifically due to the addressing mechanisms inherent in these systems.

In the context of direct V2V communications, such as in C-V2X LTE-PC5, vehicles must operate within their coverage area, so, messages transmitted by one vehicle are received by all other vehicles within its coverage area. If two vehicles are outside their coverage area, direct communication is not possible unless a forwarding algorithm, like those offered by the GeoNetworking protocol, which is not used in PoDIUM.

Another aspect to consider is that communications can be unicast, groupcast and broadcast. In vehicular communications, most messages are broadcast as they are intended for all vehicles of one area. In C-V2X (LTE-PC5) communications, these broadcast messages only need to be transmitted once by the originating vehicle to reach all others within the coverage area.

For non-direct communication between vehicles, or in the case of having to connect one vehicle with one server in the Internet, we usually have to rely on cellular networks. These are the cases of V2N2V, V2I or I2V communications. However, integrating cellular networks with C-ITS communications presents a challenge due to the disparity between the IP-based nature of cellular networks and the non-IP nature of C-ITS communications. Cellular networks identify source and destination devices using IP addresses, while C-ITS communication protocols were designed to function independently of the IP protocol. Vehicle identifiers in C-ITS (ETSI calls them StationID) are typically random numbers for privacy, and are subject to periodic changes to increase privacy even more. Therefore, in order to transmit these non-IP C-ITS messages over an IP-based network, it is necessary to add a new layer of software composed of a client and a server that basically encapsulate the C-ITS messages inside an IP datagram while they are travelling through the Internet, and remove the IP headers on reception.

In PoDIUM platform this server is called "V2X Gateway" and includes the facility to adapt C-ITS messages to be transmitted over an IP-based network, plus the functionalities to encode and decode ETSI ITS-G5 communication protocols (GeoNetworking, BTP and Facilities messages). While the V2X Gateway is deployed in the MEC, its counterpart clients are deployed in the OBUs of vehicles and VRUs, inside the module named "V2X stack", in its two versions, for Linux in vehicles and for Android in VRUs. This approach follows the functional architecture defined by 3GPP "Application layer support for V2X services" [38], where we can find the definition of the VAE (V2X Application Enabler) layer (Figure 68). The VAE layer provides application support functions like abstracting the underlying network interactions for network resource management, tracking of location, message distribution, file transfer, network monitoring, group management, configuration management, identity management, etc. 3GPP has defined the functionalities and the interfaces of the VAE layer but not its implementation method, and it is not yet commercially available for any operator.

Figure 68: 3GPP architecture model where it establishes the VAE layer

In PoDIUM, we have developed a simple VAE-like layer, that is able to distribute messages to V2X devices, but without the support of the SEAL (Service Enabler Architecture Layer for Verticals) layer because it would have required a close cooperation with the mobile network operator that we did not have.

As the method to implement the VAE layer is not defined, two PoDIUM partners (i2CAT and IDIADA) have developed **two different VAE-like solutions**. In UC3, we suppose that one solution is the one adopted in Spain and the other in France, and vehicles, when crossing the border, have to roam from one solution to the other.

In the i2CAT solution, V2X stack modules deployed in the V2X PCs of the CAV/CV open a TCP/IP socket with the V2X Gateway server in the MEC. The server stores their IP address and, by analysing their transmitted CAM messages, it knows their StationID, current position and type of station (vehicle, VRU, truck). All this information is used for filtering or grouping messages transmitted by the server towards vehicles or/and VRUs. TCP has been chosen over UDP because it facilitates going through the Network Address Translators (NATs) that we surely will find in the path between vehicles/VRUs and the MEC. The payload can consist of the facilities message alone, or it can include the facilities message, along with the BTP and the GeoNetworking headers. We have chosen to use all the protocols (IPv4 - TCP - GN - BTP - Facilities) to fully comply the ETSI ITS standards (see also Table 6) and be able to include message signatures for authentication, if necessary.

The V2X communications with smartphones running the stack is done through Websockets. This bidirectional communication method facilitates interactions over to TCP/IP, connecting browsers and servers. Relevant messages from PC5 and aggregated information of interest to VRUs are efficiently transmitted through this Websockets connection.

The gateway exhibits intelligence by redistributing V2X-related information to all "unicast" clients. Leveraging knowledge of their positions and station types, it filters out unnecessary messages and aggregates others to optimize the connection.

It is worth to comment that, currently, multicast and broadcast transmissions in cellular networks are not yet available. Although these transmissions have been standardized under the name MBMS (Multimedia Broadcast Multicast Service), operators do not offer them. This means that if the server "V2X Gateway" has to send a broadcast message in one geographical area, it will have to send multiple unicast messages, one to each vehicle registered in its LDM that is in this area. This is clearly a non-scalable solution, that will be solved when MBMS services are available.

The V2X Gateway development has successfully concluded, showcasing a unified approach in its implementation across various devices. The code, which integrates the ETSI C-ITS stack, is uniform for OBUs, smartphones, and MEC/server solutions, utilizing Python. This design ensures versatile compatibility, seamlessly operating whether virtualized within a MEC environment, deployed on bare metal in an OBU, or through a smartphone's browser using a WebAssembly (WASM)-based Python interpreter for VRUs. A critical aspect addressed involves ensuring communications in unicast vehicular scenarios, specifically when conventional cellular networks or non-C-V2X communications are employed. This functionality has been implemented and thoroughly tested.

Furthermore, the flexibility of the architecture allows the implementation to be fragmented in different stand-alone services that can later be orchestrated by Kubernetes. One first version of this gateway was presented as a demo in INFOCOM Workshops in May 2023 (see [15]).

IDIADA's Gateway solution is based on the MQTT protocol which is used by the V2X stack on the vehicles to establish a Pub/Sub communication model with the messaging broker placed in the MEC. This brings potential benefits that will be explored in UC3. Since this IDIADA'S V2X gateway is used also for UC2, more details can be found in the Section 3.4.1.5 from UC2 (page 66).

4.4.1.5. Cooperative Awareness (Optimised Awareness Distributor)

The first and primary ITS application is the Cooperative Awareness (CA) basic service [34], which uses the transmission of CAM messages between ITS stations (vehicles or VRUs) to establish and maintain awareness of the presence, location, and status of other ITS-S. CAM messages contain both mandatory and optional information about the disseminating ITS-S as: station identifier, timestamp of the generated information, station type (pedestrian, cyclist, motorcycle, passenger car, bus, light truck, RSU ...), position in latitude and longitude, heading, speed, drive direction, vehicle dimensions, acceleration, lane position, vehicle role (public transport, special transport, dangerous goods, emergency vehicle, ...), exterior lights turned on, path history, and some other specific information for special vehicles.

The current ETSI CAM generation rules establish that the CAM generation interval shall be within $0.1 \text{ s} \leq T_{\text{GenCam}} \leq 1 \text{ s}$ depending on the transmitter change of position or speed as well as the Decentralized Congestion Control (DCC), which tries to prevent radio channel saturation ([34], section 6.1.3). Upon receiving a CAM, the CA basic service makes the content of the CAM available to ITS applications within the receiving station, by storing this information into the LDM.

On the other hand, the Collective Perception Service (CPS) [25] is used to share information about detected objects by the disseminating ITS-S. The message consists of information about the disseminating ITS-S, its sensory capabilities and its detected objects. The CPM is transmitted cyclically with adaptive message generation rates to decrease the resulting channel load while focusing on reporting changes in the dynamic road environment. The CPM generation rules establish that the CPM generation interval shall be within $0.1 \text{ s} \leq T_{\text{GenCpm}} \leq 1 \text{ s}$. Additionally, this CPM should include the known objects if the objects comply to any of the following conditions: i) the object has just been known and has not been reported before, ii) the object has moved 4 m from its last reported position, iii) its absolute speed has changed by more than 0.5 m/s since it was last reported, and iv) the last time the object was reported exceeds 1s.

The CPM message contains: i) the mandatory ITS Protocol Data Unit header with the type of message, version and station identifier; ii) the mandatory Management Container providing the type of station (vehicle, truck, RSU, ...), reference position and CPM segmentation information; iii) the optional Station Data Container provides additional information about the disseminating ITS-S as speed or heading for vehicles, or two parameters to reference information in MAP messages for RSUs; iv) the optional Sensor Information Containers provide information and capabilities of up to 128 sensors of the disseminating ITS-S (sensor type or detection area); v) the optional Perceived Object Containers report information about up to 128 detected objects (distances to the reference point, dimensions, speed,

acceleration, ...); and vi) the optional Free Space Addendum Container which is used to provide different confidence levels for certain areas within the detection area of a particular sensor. These CPM messages can serve as well to aggregate information of several CAM messages in a single CPM message. The size of the CPM plus lower protocols should not exceed the Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU) of the access layer technology. In case that all the information to be send does not fit in the available space, the transmitter shall use the CP segmentation procedure. This mechanism uses several CPM segments, that can be decoded independently, and objects are inserted in a descending order of the product of the object's confidence and speed.

As we have explained in the previous section, direct V2V communication using C-V2X enables to receive direct C-ITS messages from neighbour vehicles, so Cooperative Awareness and Collective Perception services work correctly. Nevertheless, when using communication over a cellular network, C-ITS messages generated from stations finish their path in the V2X Gateway, in the MEC. To make their information reach the rest of stations, it is necessary that some functionality in the MEC collects this information and retransmits it down to the stations, this would be the task of an "Awareness Distributor". The problem of retransmitting awareness C-ITS messages down, from the MEC to ITS stations, is that as these messages should be transmitted to a great number of vehicles, we should employ multicast and broadcast addressing, but current cellular operators do not provide MBMS facilities. The alternative is transmitting multiple unicast messages, one to each vehicle of the area. Evidently, this is not a scalable solution, especially if we would have to retransmit every CAM message generated by every connected vehicle.

The solution that we propose is to aggregate the information of many CAM messages into a few CPM messages and transmit them to specific group of vehicles, even personalizing the CPM information according to some characteristic of the receiving vehicles. This will be the task of PoDIUMs "Optimized Awareness Distributor". However, this approach raises challenges such as determining which information should be included in a CPM, how frequently new CPMs should be generated to ensure fresh information about the positions of neighbouring vehicles trying to avoid overloading the communication channel and diminishing the packet delivery ratio, how large should the CPMs be to avoid high processing load in the receiver, etc.

Additionally, the Optimized Awareness Distributor disseminates information about non-connected vehicles. As the LDM is populated with information received from video cameras recording vehicle traffic, the LDM stores information about non-connected vehicles as well, and this information is included inside the CPMs transmitted to connected vehicles.

Up to now, we have developed the functionality to create CPMs from the LDM's information and personalize its distribution according to certain filters: i) all vehicles in the system, ii) vehicles in predefined areas, iii) type of stations (vehicles, pedestrians, or other not presents in UC3 as bicycles, trucks, etc.), iv) vehicles following a certain direction (North, South, ...), and v) vehicles connected through cellular network or vehicles under the coverage area of a certain RSU (this is employed when vehicles do not have cellular coverage but under RSU coverage). In the following moths we will refine the optimization process in relation to which data should be included inside the CPMs.

As a preliminary result, we have performed a simulation analysis and presented it in ICTON Conference July 2023 (see [16]). Here, we simulated an urban area where all vehicles were connected vehicles using IEEE 802.11p. In the simulated scenario we deployed several RSUs that collected the CAM messages transmitted from vehicles, sent them to a MEC where the "Optimized Awareness Distributor" included information of several CAMs inside one CPM, and this was transmitted again to the RSUs to be broadcasted in their area of coverage. In this way, vehicles that were hidden by buildings or located at long distances could know their presence. This simulation was performed in an urban area because it is easier to stress the system. In this way, we were able to include a large number of vehicles and generate a high level of interferences among them.

The simulated scenario is a Manhattan layout, with streets of 124 m between intersection centres, with four lanes of 4 m width each (Figure 69). We added nodes representing RSUs, one in the centre of each street defined by two intersections. We used the SUMO traffic simulation tool to create realistic car trajectories and OMNeT++ for simulating radio transmission over 802.11p. The transmitted C-ITS messages were CAM and CPM encapsulated in GeoNetworking and BTP headers.

Figure 69: Simulated scenario

The forwarding was done in such a manner that the RSU deployed in each street only forwards the awareness information obtained in its adjacent streets. We used a scenario with a vehicle density average of approximately 12.1 vehicles between two intersections of streets. This is not too low to enable to have some radio interference in the V2X radio channel, and not too high, where vehicles would be stopped most of the time.

As a measurement of the system's performance, we use the Neighbourhood Awareness Ratio (NAR(r)), which describes the portion of cars registered in a given vehicle's LDM from all the cars that are present at a given radius r from that vehicle, and the average Position Error (PE(r)) which computes the average error between the real position of one vehicle and the position of this vehicle stored in the LDMs of the rest of vehicles at a given radius r from that vehicle. The vehicle's LDMs were updated only on reception of CAM or CPM messages, there was no "Intelligent LDM updater" with position estimation. In this way, the loss of messages increased the parameter Position Error.

Figure 70 depicts the NAR perceived by vehicles when we performed the CPM and when we do not. In this last case vehicles only receive CAMs from direct V2V communications. The graph reveals that when no forwarding is employed, there is a 100% NAR up to approximately 60 meters distance, which represents half the distance between street intersections. However, beyond this point, the perception rate declines dramatically due to the presence of vehicles on perpendicular streets that cannot be detected. In contrast, the implementation of awareness forwarding in the form of CPM messages results in a significant improvement in perception. With CPM message forwarding, the NAR remains above 90% even at distances of up to 280 meters.

Figure 70: NAR of the different scenarios.

Figure 71 displays the PE using boxes that extend from the Q1 to Q3 quartile and the median line (Q2). The whiskers display the data range but not exceeding $1.5 * IQR$ ($IQR = Q3 - Q1$) from the box edges, in this last case outliers are represented by separate dots (for IQR see [48]). We observe that there is not much difference between forwarding or not forwarding awareness due to the fact that non perceived vehicles do not compute as samples for PE statistic, and the known vehicles are equally well localized on the scenario in both cases.

Figure 71: PE of the different scenarios.

4.4.1.6. VRU safety

The module VRU risk assessment, deployed in the MEC, is in charge to assess the collision probability among vehicles and VRUs (pedestrians). For the UC3 implementation, it will concentrate its computations in the areas where the shuttle CAV loads and unloads its passengers, to reinforce their safety. Using the data stored in the MEC, it will estimate the trajectories of the actors involved in the possible collision with one advance of around 5 seconds. The estimation algorithms will be similar to those employed in the module "Intelligent LDM Updater" but increasing the estimation time. If the

collision probability exceeds a threshold, it will trigger one alarm transmitting one DENM message to both, the pedestrian and the CV/CAV.

As this module is not essential for the first test beds and prototypes, its development has been planned for the last period of task T3.2 and it has not yet started.

An alternative approach is being also evaluated, which is to embed this service into the Android smartphone of the users, thus also reducing latency. This approach is to be developed and evaluated in 2024, especially in what regards the service's performance requirements for the smartphones.

4.4.1.7. On-demand Shuttle services

In an expanded view (see Figure 64 and Figure 72), the passenger service is made up of a mobile application and a cloud that provides the necessary services for the management of passenger reservations and the management of trips on the routes. The mobile application connects through requests to its own Rest API through which it exchanges information at three different levels: User operations (login, queries on relative user data, view travel tickets, etc.), Operations related to services (schedule queries, trips, status of services, etc.) and Operations and queries related to travel reservations (seat reservation, real-time trip information queries)

Regarding the **ENIDE Cloud of the passenger application**, it has been necessary to extend some functionalities due to technical needs. With this extension, the Passenger Cloud acquires extra functionalities that include the generation of routes and schedules, sending orders to Milla's fleet management, as well as the acquisition of shuttle data in real time. Communication is carried out through a REST API with the MILLA Cloud for the exchange of information.

MILLA Cloud is a private system containing the Milla Fleet Manager whose main goals are:

- Create a unique point to inspect the MILLA vehicle's fleet where MILLA CAVs push their state using a private protocol.
- Store vehicle data for further analysis and reports.
- Create a basic services layer by creating Service-Contexts with a set of deserved-stops associated to each context.
- Expose APIs for the integration in external contexts whose vocations are mainly:
 - Integrate the vehicles into external Supervision Centres.
 - Integrate the vehicles into external Services Orchestrators (such is the case of ENIDE Services Cloud), by exposing a basic command line to be able to command a vehicle to reach a pre-defined destination.

For PoDIUM Project, the MILLA Cloud Fleet Manager's API for external services orchestrators and the internal engine has been enriched to satisfy the designed service as required by the *Business Layer*, that requires the MILLA CAVs to satisfy predefined routes including one or many stops. As a result, the enriched API exposes mainly 5 types of functions, giving visibility and interaction possibilities to external authorized clouds for the vehicles fleet associated to their accorded services. The main goal of this API is to:

- Inform about available services associated to the external cloud service orchestrator: including a set of routes, paths and deserved stops.
- Inform about vehicles capabilities: such as maximum speed, vehicle available associated services, maximum occupancy level...
- Inform about state of the associated vehicles fleet: including position, destination, estimated arrival time...
- Schedule a service associated to a vehicle, associating it to a *Ticket*.
- Inform about the state of evolution of the service *Ticket*.

The complete system is made up of a mobile application, two clouds interconnected through REST API and cellular connection with vehicles from one of the clouds.

Figure 72: Complete architecture of ENIDE-MILLA Cloud services

4.4.2. IT environment view – Platform (Edge & Cloud)

Figure 73: UC3 platform environment view (Edge & Cloud), ideal deployment

Each country (Spain, France) has its own platform, replicating the Cloud and Edge level depicted above. In Spain we will have 2 MECs, but in France we will only have 1 MEC. The Clouds exchange essential information with each other to align cross-border traffic management strategies, as previously mentioned in section 4.4.1.3 (Global HUB).

The Cloud level is hosted on Amazon Web Services. It consists of the HUB_Cloud and the TMC_Global. The Cloud is connected to the HUBs and TMCs on the MEC, coordinating traffic strategies across highway section on the same border side.

The MEC would have an Edge server, segregated in 6 Virtual Machines (via Dockers). Each VM hosts the different modules of our Platform, including HUB_Edge, TMC_Local, LDM, GTW (the V2X gateway), VRU, and VA (Video Analytics). The TMC_Edge only handles the traffic data inputs from the specific highway section that they are dedicated to. Each VA instance only handles the video feed from 1 traffic camera.

In PoDIUM we foresee the following Edge-Cloud deployment hierarchy:

- Local TMC 1: Manage the southern road sections and 2-3 cameras on the Spanish side.
- Local TMC 2: Manages the northern road sections and 2-3 cameras on the Spanish side.

- Local TMC 3. Manages all the road sections on the French side (no cameras).
- Global TMC 1: Coordinates traffic management of the 2 Local TMCs on the Spanish side and collaborates with Global TMC 2.
- Global TMC 2: Coordinates traffic management of the 1 Local TMCs on the French side and collaborates with Global TMC 1.

In an ideal deployment, as depicted in the figure above, we would be using 2 separate and identical MECs (for the Spanish side of the highway), each one handling a specific section of the highway, and located next to the road.

In the Use case implementation for the purposes of testing and demonstration, we will be using an “Edge-Cloud” architecture in the Barcelona datacentre of Cellnex (RETE). It is hosted near the LL, but not roadside on the AP7 highway.

In this “pilot platform” architecture deployment (shown in the figure below), a different strategy is tentatively being assessed: we will co-host the 2 replicated TMCs and 4 replicated VAs in separate Dockers within the same Edge-Cloud. The HUB, LDM, GTW, and VRU modules will be hosted only once in their unique Docker instances.

Figure 74: UC3 platform environment view (Edge & Cloud), LL demo deployment

Performance requirements for this Edge-Cloud VMs have been provided by the respective developing partners based on experience from previous projects or test deployments. Technical trials to confirm correct functioning within the expected Platform parameters (KPIs) will take place soon after deployment.

4.4.3. Data Flow and Storage

4.4.3.1. General view of the exchange of information

This section focuses on describing how the information is exchanged inside the platform components and with the external entities (vehicles, VRUs, etc.).

CAM and CPM messages dissemination from vehicles to the infrastructure

Cooperative perception data in form of CAMs and CPMs is periodically generated by the CAV/CVs. Following a hybrid approach, such vehicles are disseminating those messages to the MEC via cellular network (5G/4G) and to the nearby RSU and other CAV/CVs via C-V2X technology.

All messages received by the MEC are processed in the C-ITS Message Handling, which will face duplications (the messages sent by the CAV/CVs and the same ones retransmitted by RSUs). For that reason, it implements a filter function consisting of detecting those duplications and storing in the LDM only one unit of the message, as shown in Figure 75.

The LDM, as described previously, aggregates all incoming data, including the CAMs and CPMs generated by the vehicles, and provides them to the Local Traffic State on demand.

Figure 75: Flow diagram of CAM and CPM messages dissemination from vehicles to the infrastructure for UC3

Strategies dissemination

The MEC contains a function of the TMC called *Traffic Strategy & incidents dispatcher* which constantly analyses the traffic data (from the connected vehicles, cameras, etc.) and determines the best moment and area where to apply a traffic strategy to solve or mitigate an issue on the road.

As represented in Figure 76, it sends a start command with the required strategy information, which includes the type of strategy (among the three different manoeuvres identified for UC3) and the affected road segments. However, this information is not complete enough to generate the standard C-ITS messages required to provide such strategies. For the strategy to avoid a specific lane, a combination of MAPEM + IVIM is required, while for the strategies to set different max speeds and distance with the vehicles ahead, a MAPEM + MCM is required.

To fill such messages, the C-ITS Message handling, upon the reception of the strategy start request from the TMC, needs to obtain fine-grained details of the relevant road segments from the LDM. Once those messages can be generated, they are transmitted to the CAV/CVs directly via 5G or indirectly through the nearby RSUs.

For the strategy revocation, a stop request is sent to the C-ITS Message Handling to stop the dissemination of the messages.

Figure 76: Flow diagram of strategies dissemination for UC3

Incidents dissemination

The TMC, using the Traffic strategy & incidents dispatcher function, monitors the status of the road network and detects incidents thanks to multiple data sources. Additionally, this function can receive a DENM transmitted by the CAV indicating a malfunction or an incident within the vehicle. This DENM also reaches the nearby vehicles and RSUs via C-V2X.

Regardless the data source, when an incident is detected, a start request is sent to the C-ITS Message Handling which, as for the strategy messages, it needs to ask the LDM for specific geographical information to generate the DENM that will be transmitted to the stations down on the road, as shown in Figure 77.

When the incident is no longer active, the TMC sends a stop request to finalize the dissemination of the C-ITS messages (DENM).

Figure 77: Flow diagram of the incidents for UC3

CPM generation from MEC for awareness distribution

Figure 78 displays the different steps taken by the platform, from the acquisition of awareness data until its dissemination using CPMs.

The MEC gathers awareness data from two primary sources. Firstly, it collects C-ITS messages transmitted by CVs and CAVs. These vehicles periodically transmit CAM messages, and those equipped with Radar and LiDAR capabilities can additionally transmit CPM messages. Secondly, the MEC receives data from roadside sensors, specifically video cameras in UC3. These cameras capture raw video feeds, which are then transmitted to the MEC. Subsequently, through the Video Analytics module, objects detected within these feeds—predominantly non-connected vehicles—are identified and uploaded to the LDM.

As explained above, the LDM is continuously updated with estimated positions of the objects to cope with delays and loss of C-ITS messages.

Finally, the stored information within the LDM is disseminated to connected vehicles through CPMs, leveraging both radio technologies under consideration. These CPM messages offer a tailored approach, allowing for personalization based on various factors such as geographical regions of interest, vehicle types, driving direction, and more.

Figure 78: CPM generation flow diagram

Collision risk estimator and alarm distribution from the MEC

Figure 79 shows the different steps taken by the platform to calculate the risk of collision and the respective alarm distribution.

Initially, the 'VRU Risk Assessment' module retrieves crucial data from the LDM system. This includes the real-time positioning, direction, and speed of VRUs, as well as the corresponding data for the nearest vehicles in their vicinity.

Following this data retrieval process, the module then proceeds to calculate the likelihood of a collision between VRUs and vehicles. If this probability exceeds a predefined threshold, the system activates an alarm mechanism, distributing alerts to both the VRUs and vehicles involved in the potential collision event.

The alarm is distributed using DENM messages. Vehicles receive this alarm through cellular network or C-V2X, depending on the coverage. VRUs receive this alarm only through cellular network.

Figure 79: Collision risk calculation and alarm propagation flow diagram

Shuttle passenger check in process.

Figure 80 represents how the user interacts after having obtained a travel ticket, to check in the shuttle and how they receive information in real time during the service. It also shows how the passenger cloud obtains real-time information from Milla's fleet manager.

1. Mobile Application Login: The user logs into the mobile application.
2. Auth Token Return: The Passenger API returns an auth token to the mobile app after login.
3. Ticket viewing: The user requests to view the tickets through the mobile application, and the passenger API provides the tickets.
4. Check-In: The user checks in through the mobile application.
5. Check-In Completed: The mobile application receives a confirmation that the check-in has been completed.
6. Get trip status: The mobile application requests the current trip status.
7. Real-time data return: The passenger API returns real-time data about the trip status to the mobile application.

On the other hand, a parallel interaction is observed with two other cloud services:

8. Request to start a trip to the Scheduler (Scheduler): The Scheduler receives a request to start a trip.
9. Programmer Response: A response is returned to the passenger cloud service.

10. Obtain service status from the Milla Cloud Service: The passenger cloud service queries the service status to the Milla Cloud Service.
11. Service Status: The Milla Cloud Service provides the service status to the passenger cloud service.
12. Service status update: Finally, the service status is updated in the passenger cloud service.

Figure 80: Passenger data flow check in and use shuttle

4.4.3.2. Message exchange

The table below lists the main types of messages used between entities in UC3 (e.g. MEC, CVs, VRUs), and the standards and data formats for each case.

Type of message	Purpose	Standard	Data format
CAM (Cooperative Awareness Message)	Sent by the C-ITS stations to disseminate its dynamics data (i.e. location, speed, acceleration, etc.) as well as other relevant information of the stations (i.e. vehicle type, status, etc.)	ETSI EN 302 637-2 v1.4.1	ASN.1 binary

DENM (Decentralized Environmental Notification Message)	Generated by the infrastructure (TMC) and by the CAV for events notifications, like vehicle stopped or CAV malfunction.	ETSI EN 302 637-3 v1.3.1	ASN.1 binary
MAPEM (Map Extended Message)	Generated by the infrastructure (TMC), it contains details of the road layout (lanes, size, segments, speeds, etc.) used by the vehicles to better understand the environment	ETSI TS 103 301 v2.1.1	ASN.1 binary
IVIM (Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message)	Generated by the infrastructure (TMC) to advice CAV and CVs about a modification of the road max. speed.	ETSI TS 103 301 v2.1.1	ASN.1 binary
CPM (Collective Perception Message)	Reported by the CVs (with perception) to provide additional information to the TMC about nearby non-connected vehicles. Also, the CPM will be generated in the infrastructure after aggregating all CAM and CVs CPMs messages in order to avoid replicating all CAM messages via 5G.	ETSI TS 103 324 v2.1.1	ASN.1 binary
VAM (VRU Awareness Message)	Sent by the VRUs (smartphone) via 5G to report its location and other dynamic information relevant for detecting risky situation of nearby connected vehicles	ETSI TS 103 300-3 v2.2.1	ASN.1 binary
MCM (Manoeuvre Coordination Message)	Generated by the TMC to suggest/order certain manoeuvres to the vehicles in order to apply a traffic strategy upon an event / incident detected	5GMED version	ASN.1 binary
ENIDE msgs	Passenger app with ENIDE cloud	REST/OWN	JSON
ENIDE/MILLA msgs	ENIDE cloud (passenger app cloud) with MILLA shuttle cloud (fleet management)	REST/OWN	JSON
MILLA msgs	Telesupervision cloud to/from CAV shuttle	OWN	JSON

Table 6 : Types of messages used in UC3 and their standards and data formats

4.4.3.3. Semantic interoperability aspects

MCM for UC3

The Manoeuvre Coordination Service (MCS) is a work-in-progress standard from ETSI (ETSI TS 103 561) [30] which aims to define the generation and exchange of MCM (Manoeuvre Coordination Messages). The main goal of those messages is to negotiate manoeuvres among vehicles, or with the participation of the infrastructure/TMC.

The MCM message definition and the MCS service content is updated in each new version of the draft standard, which forces to fix a specific version for the PoDIUM UC3 development. The UC3 scenarios have been discussed early in the project with the conclusion of having three manoeuvres:

- Max. speed adaptation/reduction
- Lane blocked/busy
- Adaptation of the min. distance with vehicle in front

Such manoeuvres are new strategies applied by the TMC for all vehicles driving in a specific area, which make them mandatory actions to apply (if the road/traffic conditions allow so). This way, no negotiation is required among the vehicles.

Similar manoeuvres have also been defined in 5GMED project, which has already worked in a modification of an early draft version of the MCM which complies with the manoeuvres defined for PoDIUM’s UC3.

Proposal for CPM modification

CPM messages contain information about objects detected by ITS stations, represented as "Perceived Objects" as illustrated in the Figure below. This block of information is specially designed to announce objects that have been detected by a sensor (LiDAR, Radar, camera, ...). However, when CPMs include objects that are actually vehicles already identified through CAM messages sent by those vehicles themselves, it raises a potential issue.

```

PerceivedObject ::= SEQUENCE {
    objectId                               Identifier2B OPTIONAL,
    measurementDeltaTime                   DeltaTimeMilliSecondSigned,
    position                               CartesianPosition3dWithConfidence,
    velocity                               Velocity3dWithConfidence OPTIONAL,
    acceleration                           Acceleration3dWithConfidence OPTIONAL,
    angles                                 EulerAnglesWithConfidence OPTIONAL,
    zAngularVelocity                       CartesianAngularVelocityComponent OPTIONAL,
    lowerTriangularCorrelationMatrices     LowerTriangularPositiveSemidefiniteMatrices OPTIONAL,
    objectDimensionZ                       ObjectDimension OPTIONAL,
    objectDimensionY                       ObjectDimension OPTIONAL,
    objectDimensionX                       ObjectDimension OPTIONAL,
    objectAge                              DeltaTimeMilliSecondSigned (0..2047) OPTIONAL,
    objectPerceptionQuality                 ObjectPerceptionQuality OPTIONAL,
    sensorIdList                           SequenceOfIdentifier1B OPTIONAL,
    classification                         ObjectClassDescription OPTIONAL,
    mapPosition                             MapPosition OPTIONAL,
    ...
}
    
```

Figure 81: Contents of the Perceived Object field included in the CPM and standardized in the common data dictionary by ETSI (TS 102 894-2)

Consider the scenario where a CAV transmits CAM messages containing its Station ID, position, and other relevant parameters. Nearby vehicles receive these CAM messages via C-V2X radio, but vehicles outside the coverage area or those utilizing cellular networks for C-ITS communication may not directly receive these messages. Instead, they obtain the information through an awareness distribution infrastructure like the one designed in PoDIUM. As described earlier, distributing awareness information can be done via individual CAM messages, but poses scalability challenges. To address this, we propose consolidating information from multiple CAM messages into a smaller number of CPMs.

When CAM messages are retransmitted through RSUs, there's a possibility that the originating vehicle receives its own CAM message. However, since the CAM includes its Station ID, the vehicle recognizes it as a retransmission and simply disregards the message, posing no issue.

When performing the same operation with CPMs, a critical issue arises because the Perceived Object field lacks the option to include a Station ID. Consequently, the originating vehicle of the CAM message may receive a CPM containing an object at its own position, potentially being itself, without any means to identify it as such since there's no Station ID included. This presents a significant problem for a CAV, as it may mistakenly interpret the object as an obstacle and abruptly halt the vehicle.

The solution to this dilemma involves incorporating the Station ID within the Perceived Object field. By including the Station ID, the CAV can recognize that the object within the CPM is itself, thereby averting any erroneous interpretation of the object as an obstacle and preventing unnecessary vehicle stops or other problems.

One possible strategy to address this issue would be to propose a modification to the CPM definition that introduces a new optional field within the Perceived Object structure: the Station ID field. This will be evaluated during next months.

5. Use Case 4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance

Use Case 4 “Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance” is demonstrated in the Italian Living lab, at a crossroad in the city of Turin. In this use case, Connected and Automated Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users are assisted at an intersection by CCAM applications running on a MEC server. Information provided by roadside cameras, vehicle sensors and VRU devices is shared (by means of CAM and CPM), fused, stored in a digital twin. It is then used by CCAM application on the PoDIUM infrastructure to inform connected road users on hazards and assist them in crossing, by means of hazard notifications (DENM) and crossing timeslot recommendations (included in IVIM). This use case also demonstrates how the local infrastructure system can act as an attestor of the communicating units approaching the intersection, to ensure that the collective information fused in the digital twin comes only from trusted entities.

5.1. Scenario Descriptions

The scenarios presented in UC4 represent the different possible manoeuvres in the crosspoint. The most relevant and non-trivial were chosen for the sake of space. The scenarios are Straight, right turn and left turn; in all scenarios, CAV and VRUs are sending CAM/VAMs respectively and the CAV has green light, since the CAV in principle does not violate the red light.

5.1.1. Straight

This kind of scenario is triggered when the CAV is going to pass the crosspoint straight as shown in Figure 82, but an irregular pedestrian crosses the crosspoint at the same time having red (VRU violator). The vehicle and VRU arrive to the crosspoint sending standard messages. RSU/SPU feed CPMs into the infrastructure with information continuously.

VIMA (VRU Intersection Movement Assistance) identifies a collision risk with a VRU violator.

Figure 82: UC4 Straight scenario

Given the violation condition by a VRU, the vehicle can handle the situation without PDI intervention, based only on its on-board sensors, or even with the help of a fused-CPM with the unified information taken from all cross-point sensors. VIMA detects the collision risk due to the imminent crossing of both paths and produces a DENM informing all vehicles of this condition. No indications are given to the vehicle to cross the crosspoint.

This kind of scenario includes two scenarios:

- Sc. 1.1: Straight-Pass: VRU is standing at the cross-roads, therefore, no obstacle is considered by CAV.
- Sc. 1.2: Straight-Warn/Brake: CAV has green light, but VRU violates its red and crosses.

The first one is considered only for technical purpose, to check the system performance in filtering out the negative cases. The demonstration scenario is actually 1.2. The following Timeline and diagrams refer to the latter.

Timeline

- t0 - Vehicle and VRU start moving
- t1 - Vehicle and VRU (app) broadcast standard messages while moving
- t2 - CAV and VRU (app) are notified of the presence of each other
- t3 - Truthfulness Module identifies that both road users are in collision course due to red violation by the VRU
- t4 - A collision warning DENM is sent by TM to the relevant road users
- t5 - CAV waits or modulates speed to let VRU cross first
- t6 - CAV ends the crossing

Activity Diagram

Figure 83: UC4 Activity Diagram for the Straight Scenario

5.1.2. Right turn

The vehicle arrives, breaks, and gives way to VRU. Both CAV and VRU have green light but the vehicle has to give way to pedestrian. The vehicle is assisted by the infrastructure that notifies both the presence of a VRU (supported by VAM/CPM from infrastructure) and the IMA indication (supported by IVIM from infrastructure).

Right turn scenarios are three:

- Sc. 2.1: VRU precedence management: VIMA handles the precedence and VRU respects it.
- Sc. 2.2: VRU sudden crossing: VIMA handles the precedence, but VRU crosses outside the timeslot.
- Sc. 2.3: Precedence management after sudden crossing: two VRU crossing. The first one does not respect the timeslot; a second VRU follow but this time VIMA app replans a timeslot, and the second VRU crosses regularly.

Scenario 2.1 (Figure 84) is the main scenario. Scenario 2.2 is similar to scenario 1.2 (DENM to warn the driver of a sudden crossing after IVIM is not respected), and 2.3 is a combination of 2.1 and 2.2, with an IVIM update at the end. For the sake of readability, only scenario 2.1 is presented hereafter (Figure 84) but all three scenarios are tested in the Living Lab.

Figure 84: UC4 Right turn scenario

Timeline

- t0 - CAV and VRU start moving
- t1 - CAV and VRU broadcast standard messages while moving
- t2 - CAV and VRU are notified of the presence of other road users
- t3 - IMA risk assessment identifies that both road users are in collision course due to both have GREEN light
- t4 - Information is sent using C-ITS to the relevant road users to arbitrate the crossing
 - t4.1 - CAV receives an indication to break and wait
 - t4.2 - VRU receives an indication to pass
- t5 - CAV undertakes slowly the turn, but stops some meters before the VRU crossing
- t6 - VRU finishes crossing the intersection
- t7 - CAV receives an indication to start moving and turn to the right, if there is a green light (IVIM update). Two IVIM messages are sent

Trigger

IMA risk assessment identifies that both road users are on collision course.
 IMA gives just indication to slowdown. Traffic light is negligible (green for both VRU and vehicle or no TL).

Requisites

- VRU is using the application
- Green light for all road users

Activity Diagram

Figure 85: UC4 Activity diagram for scenario Right Turn

5.1.3. Left Turn

The following scenario considers that both the VRU and the CAV (purple vehicle in Figure 86) have the right to cross the pedestrian crossing and turn to the left due to both receiving a green light sign (Scene 1). While the pedestrian starts crossing the street, the CAV goes into the centre of the intersection and breaks, to let vehicles (blue vehicles) that are coming from the other street to cross the intersection (Scene 2). When the vehicles have crossed (blue vehicles), the CAV continues the crossing manoeuvre evaluating the presence of the VRU at the pedestrian crossing (Scene 3).

The vehicle is assisted by the infrastructure that notifies both the presence of a VRU (supported by VAM/CPM from infrastructure) and the IMA indication (supported by IVIM from infrastructure).

Figure 86: UC4 Left turn scenario

Timeline

The following timeline represents a step-by-step guide on how the scenario is expected to evolve in real life.

t0 - CAV and VRU start moving

t1 - CAV and VRU broadcast standard messages while moving

t2 - CAV and VRU are notified of the presence of other road users

t3 - IMA risk assessment identifies that the road users are in collision course

t3.1 - IMA analyses the opposite vehicle trajectory

t3.2 - IMA analyses the VRU trajectory

t4 - Information is sent using C-ITS to the relevant road users to arbitrate the crossing

t4.1 - CAV receives an indication to break and wait

t4.2 - VRU receives an indication to pass

t5 - CAV moves towards the centre of the intersection and stops there waiting for the other road users to cross

t6 - Non equipped vehicle finalizes to pass the intersection

t7 - VRU finishes crossing the intersection

t8 - CAV receives an indication to start moving and turn to the left, if there is a green light

Note: This scenario is not relevant if there is a left turn traffic light. In this case the scenario becomes the same as the right turn.

Activity Diagram

The next activity diagram presents the decisional process proposed during the field trial of the UC4 left turn scenario. The blue boxes highlight the moment when the CAV finalizes the left turn manoeuvre and the pedestrian crossing the street.

Figure 87: UC4 Activity diagram for scenario Left Turn

5.1.4. Trust

This scenario is a prerequisite to the RSU and OBU before sending any messages to the CCAM Broker. A vehicle is authorized (or deauthorized) by the remote attestor to start transmitting packets to the PDI. The scenario presupposes that the service discovery is contained in CAV OBU during vehicle connection to 5G, and the OBU is addressed to the remote attestor as the first service to connect to. The remote attestation protocol starts between both actors and finally, the attestation result triggers the generation of new broker credentials or renew old ones. The remote attestation protocol is periodic; OBU and RSU are challenged again periodically, revoking the credentials in the case of loss of integrity.

Activity Diagram

Figure 88: UC4 Activity Diagram: Trust Scenario

5.2. Communication Aspects

This chapter describes the communication aspects of UC4 of the Italian LL.

The goal is to provide an overview of the communication architecture, the communication entities, and the use of communication technologies within the UC4.

5.2.1. Communication Architecture

The communication architecture chapter provides a description of the use case specific communication view including all involved entities. Furthermore, it provides insights of the communication of the entities and their role for the implementation of the use case scenarios, the communication technologies and how they are utilized in the use case, and finally the specific communication features that support specific aspects of the use case. The communication view for UC4 is shown in Figure 89.

Figure 89: UC4 Communication View

The local data processing and communications layer comprises VRUs, CAV as well as RSU/SPUs. Connected and automated vehicles, VRUs and RSUs communicate with the MEC infrastructure via 5G mobile cellular network compliant with 3GPP Rel.16 [39]; wireless short-range communications between RSUs and CAVs are implemented according ITS ETSI EN 302 663 [40] G5 standard in the beginning, then with ETSI EN 303 613 [41] PC5 standard in future releases.

5.2.2. Communication Entities

The individual entities have communication capabilities to fulfil the requirements of the use case scenarios.

5.2.2.1. Connected Automated Vehicle (CAV)

Role:

The CAV of UC4 needs to communicate its presence dynamics and intentions (CAM) as well as the detected objects (CPM) to the MEC services, and receive warnings (DENM), intersection movement assistance (“VIMA” IVI), traffic light phases (SPAT) and local maps (MAP) from the MEC. For this purpose, the CAV prototype is equipped with an Onboard Unit providing ITS-G5, C-V2X (LTE-PC5) and 5G connectivity.

The vehicle has also on-board sensors that allows the vehicle to produce CPM messages. CAVs have hybrid connectivity for redundancy and in order to improve the amount of information fed into the digital twin.

Implementation:

The CAV regularly sends its position and detections using CAM and CPM messages, and receives SPAT and MAP messages from the MEC. It receives DENM by the infrastructure upon a VRU traffic light violation event, and “VIMA” IVI if there is a VRU which is scheduled to pass (so that the vehicle can plan its manoeuvre before or after). All these messages are exchanged over 5G using the hybrid communication approach (ETSI message payload exchanged over AMQP). PC5 is used as secondary communication channel, mostly for technical evaluation purposes, while ITS-G5 is used only in the first stage until PC5 is deployed on the roadside unit. V2I can run in parallel with V2N, whereas the two V2I technologies (PC5 or ITS-G5) are mutually exclusive (only one at a time).

The OBU has a 5G modem configured to access the Service Edge Node (SEN) in the TIM network, as explained in detail in Section 5.2.2.5. C-ITS messages are sent to the MEC via AMQP protocol to a CCAM Broker; The OBU has also a short range radio interface in order to communicate with the RSU. The OBU behaves also as a Trusted Computing Base, so it implements also a Trusted Platform Agent to allow the OBU to be considered as a trusted source by the attestation protocol.

5.2.2.2. Roadside Unit (RSU)

Role:

In UC4, the RSU collects C-ITS messages coming from neighbouring vehicles using its short-range interface and forwards them via AMQP to the edge services. This gives hybrid communication possible and redundancy into the system to enhance trust and security. When a C-ITS message is forwarded through a RSU, it is declaring that the vehicle is within its short-range radio.

Implementation:

The RSU is connected through a 5G module to TIM mobile network. The RSU has also a management interface (not depicted in the communication view since it is useful for remote management purposes). It implements hybrid connectivity thanks to its short range interface and it performs routing functions to forward incoming messages.

The RSU behaves also as a Trusted Computing Base, so it implements also a Trusted Platform Agent to allow the RSU to be considered as trusted by the attestation protocol on MEC Attestor.

5.2.2.3. Sensor Processing Unit (SPU)

Role:

In UC4, the SPU collects data from the sensors (camera and LiDAR) and sends them to the IMA server deployed on the MEC.

Implementation:

The SPU is connected through a 5G module to TIM mobile network, as part of the RSU. The SPUs regularly send data to the MEC using CPM messages as a result of their detections.

5.2.2.4. Vulnerable Road User (VRU)

Role:

The VRU in the UC4 scenario will be represented by pedestrians and cyclists. Pedestrians are connected through a smartphone App to TIM mobile network. Cyclists are connected through a bicycle OBU and a smartphone App to TIM mobile network.

Implementation:

The VRU (pedestrian) is connected via a Nomadic Device. This will be implemented through an App on a standard Android smartphone. The App will regularly send position and movement data to the MEC using standard VAM messages.

The VRU (cyclist) is connected via a Nomadic Device and a OBU. The first will be implemented through an App on a standard Android smartphone. The second will be an ad hoc device supporting positioning and smartphone connectivity. The App / OBU will regularly send position and movement data to the MEC using standard VAM messages.

5.2.2.5. Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)

Role:

Edge Computing is an architectural solution enabling the availability of contents and applications closer to the end customer, in order to meet the requirements of latency, security, resilience and bandwidth; it also allows a more efficient distribution of computational capacity between devices and network.

The MEC has a central role in UC4, it processes information from road users which is transmitted to the MEC.

The MEC fuses the data into a global environment model (digital twin) and uses it to generate an efficient plan for the coordinated execution of cooperative driving maneuvers by sending recommendations for action to all road users involved.

Implementation:

The MEC is connected to 5G core network.

The architecture of a telco node is represented in Figure 90.

Figure 90: UC4 Telco Node architecture

TIM's MEC platform consists of two logical entities: the Telco Edge Node (TEN) and the Service Edge Node (SEN).

The TEN represents the point where the traffic of the attested users is managed: while the traditional traffic continues to the Internet network, traffic that must reach the Edge Computing platform is routed to the SEN, which represents the cloud-like environment (but positioned at the edge) where the applications that must process the data reside.

Since traffic directed to the edge is not routed over the Internet, it is possible to achieve the low latencies necessary for UC, since all the routing involved in Web protocols is avoided.

In details:

- Telco Edge Node component
- Intercepts (partially or totally) the access traffic (Local Breakout): for example, a small portion of 5G Core Network placed at the edge of the network that opens IP interfaces towards service logics;
- Breakout of local traffic sent towards edge applications hosted in Service Edge Nodes;
- Implemented and managed by Telco Operator.
- Service Edge Node components
- Hosts specific Edge applications;
- Offers APIs to enable the environment to external application developers;
- Native hybrid cloud design: public and private cloud cooperate;
- Can be offered by Telco Operator, by Hyperscale providers or in the context of partnerships with operators / third parties.

Telco and Service Edge Nodes are deployed at the edge of Telco network and are connected to Telco's transport. Telco and Service Edge nodes can be deployed jointly or separately.

5.2.3. Communication Features

5.2.3.1. 5G

TIM provides a 5G network at 3700 MHz (cm-Wave) using C-V2X protocols worked out by standard ETSI TC ITS (see Table 7). Messages are exchanged using a AMQP broker.

5.2.3.2. PC5

Known as LTE-V2X PC5 interface, subset of the 3GPP Release 14 specification that defines Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) technology which uses device-to-device communication at 5.9 GHz band without requiring the presence of a base station. In UC4 and UC5 it is referred as "short range".

5.2.3.3. Hybrid Communication

Hybrid communication is used since messages from CAVs might arrive to the MEC from short range interfaces and 5G, as explained correspondingly in RSU functional view.

Purpose:

In real scenarios, usually the redundancy in communications is useful to offer enough coverage for connected vehicles and that no messages are missing. The implementation of redundant paths for messages up to the point of consumption is important.

Implementation:

In UC4 hybrid communication is done through the routing functions of the RSU and the dual interfaces (5G and short range) in the OBU. Both paths are always available, so messages might arrive to the edge services twice, but the fusion functionality benefits of having one message coming from short range interface (hence declaring that the vehicle is perceived by the RSU) and another one directly via 5G.

5.3. Connected Entities

This chapter covers all developments related to entities that interact at road level with PoDIUM platform services in UC4.

5.3.1. Connected and Automated Vehicles

To achieve UC4, the on-board systems of the Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) have been developed. In particular, the work focused on:

- the handling of C-ITS messages
- the localization and positioning of the vehicle
- the development of the logics based on V2X information to help the driver with VRUs management
- the extension of the vehicle perception with the obstacles coming from infrastructure
- the HMI visualization

5.3.1.1. Functional view

This section reports the functional view within CAV.

Figure 91: UC4 functional view of the CAV

The software modules to be developed and added to the legacy implementation for UC4 are:

- Localization/Positioning
- C-ITS message handling
- Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map
- Cooperative applications
- HMI

Below is the explanation of each of these modules.

The **Localization/Positioning** module calculates the absolute position of the vehicle with respect to the Earth coordinate system, getting signal from satellites. This signal is then refined with RTK correction to improve its accuracy. RTK correction data comes from public cloud services, e.g. Italian “Catasto” public service. The Localization/Positioning output is provided to:

- C-ITS message handling to filter incoming V2X messages based on relevance area and to provide vehicle positioning information into outgoing V2X messages.
- Data fusion and LDM to calculate the obstacles relative position with respect to the vehicle.
- HMI for display purposes.

The **C-ITS message handling** module is responsible for the data exchange between CAV and the other connected entities (RSUs and VRUs). It decodes incoming V2X messages and encodes outgoing ones according to the standard. In transmission, the system uses vehicle motion, positioning and perception data to send CAM and CPM messages. In reception, the V2X messages used by the UC4 logics are:

- CPM to perform the cooperative perception; in fact, they carry information about surrounding obstacles detected by external entities.
- CAM, DENM, IVIM, SPATEM and MAPEM to generate the HMI warning recommendations and manoeuvre suggestions. The HMI detail is covered in paragraph 1.3.1.4 “Cooperative Awareness HMI concept”.

The system relies on the 5G cellular network to exchange V2X messages. In particular, it uses the AMQP publish/subscribe standard protocol for the communication with PoDIUM entities.

Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map (LDM) module extends the vehicle perception by taking advantage of V2X. In fact, it combines sensor data with information coming from CPM messages to univocally identify surrounding objects such as neighbour vehicles, bicycles and pedestrians. This is why it is appropriate to talk about “cooperative perception”. It gets information from vehicle perception, positioning, and C-ITS message handling.

Cooperative Applications module is responsible for generating warning recommendations and manoeuvre suggestions to the driver based on vehicle motion and V2X information.

HMI is specifically developed for UC4 to help the driver manage VRUs at intersections. It shows the driving scene with surrounding obstacles and, depending on the content of the V2X messages, can display useful indications such as manoeuvre suggestion, risk of collision warning etc. In case of traffic light intersection, it provides the current phase. It also has information about key performance indicators (e.g., positioning and V2X quality).

5.3.1.2. Sequence view between functional components

This section shows the message sequences between functional components at CAV.

C-ITS message exchange

The following sequence diagrams (Figure 92 and Figure 93) show the messages that the vehicle and the off-board entities exchange, distinguishing between the transmission and reception phases from the CAV point of view.

- Transmission phase: C-ITS message handling module sends CAM and CPM messages based on vehicle motion, positioning, and legacy perception.
- Reception phase: C-ITS message handling module receives and decodes CAM, CPM, DENM, IVIM, SPAT and MAP messages and then forwards their payload to the Data Fusion and LDM module.

Figure 92: C-ITS message transmission

Figure 93: C-ITS message reception

Ego-vehicle localization

The vehicle position is obtained from the satellites signal and adjusted with the RTK correction which improves its accuracy.

Figure 94: CAV Positioning

HMI visualization

The HMI module collects the fused obstacles coming from Data Fusion and LDM module and displays them with reference to the ego vehicle position. It also shows warnings in line with the driver recommendations coming from Cooperative Applications module.

Figure 95: HMI visualization

5.3.1.3. IT Environment View

This view shows the software components allocation into the hardware of the in-vehicle prototype. The main hardware components involved are:

- **Communication Unit:** is responsible for C-ITS message handling and vehicle localization. This component integrates a GNSS receiver for GPS acquisition and a 5G modem for access to the AMQP and RTK services.
- **PoDIUM PC:** contains the cooperative applications and cooperative perception functions.
- **ADF PC:** contains the autonomous driving system logics. These logics are not the focus of UC4 and in fact are inherited. In future developments, however, cooperative applications could interact with ADF planning module to improve automatic driving.
- **Tablet:** displays the HMI interface.

Figure 96: IT Environment View

5.3.1.4. Cooperative Awareness HMI concept

This view shows the information related to the UC4 displayed to the end-user. The graphical layout is not represented as it is not ultimate, but this view is sufficient to represent the contents/data that are displayed and the purpose.

Figure 97: HMI concept view

For UC4 we have the following information to display in the living lab:

- Driving scene with vehicles and other objects detected
- Collision risk warning
- Intersection assist
- Manoeuvre suggestion (e.g., Wait or Pass)
- VIMA data (e.g., scheduled time for VRU crossing)
- Current motion (e.g., vehicle speed)
- If present, traffic light phase
- KPI-related information on V2X and positioning

5.3.1.5. State of development

With reference to the CAV functional view (Figure 91), the software components development status is as follows:

- UC4 CAV prototype for the Turing Living lab is available, with all hardware equipment described in the IT environment view
- Localization/Positioning is available
- C-ITS message handling is available as encoding/decoding functionalities and interface with the other in-vehicle modules (CAN network input/output). Message filtering will be available in future releases
- Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map module is partially available and will be completed in the next releases

- Cooperative applications are developed for the following Scenarios “Straight-Warn/Brake (1.2)” and “right turn with VRU precedence management (2.1)” with basic functionalities
- HMI module has preliminary functions to show scenarios 1.2 and 2.1

5.3.2. Connected VRU

UC4 has the participation of two types of Connected VRUs: pedestrian VRUs and Cyclists. The functionality associated to both is the same, with differences in the HMI and the management of the movement dynamics.

5.3.2.1.1. Functional view

Figure 98 depicts the functionality of a connected VRU, considering the generalized case of VRU; a VRU can be a pedestrian or bicycle; other types of VRUs such as motorized/ or not motorized wheelchair road users might fit into this model; in PoDIUM, from the point of view of camera detection, pedestrians and bicycles are the only considered as VRUs. The difference is more visible in the IT environment view depicted in the following section.

Figure 98: functional view Connected VRU

Functions are separated into four blocks in order to reach the final effect of contributing to the crosspoint digital twin with VAM messages and consume warnings to be displayed to the user.

Communication:

With regards the protocol execution, generation of standard VAM messages based on the status, type and dynamics of the VRU and requests the subscription to warnings generated by the platform. Here the incorporated 5G modem allows the connectivity to the edge services.

Bluetooth/Wifi interfaces handle also communication with VRU sensors as explained below.

Positioning:

Gives the App the positioning capability by reading position and other dynamics data from the available sensors. In the case of the bicycle VRU, the positioning sensors are extended with the sensors present on the bicycle and that allow a proper navigation and precision. Sensors present on the bicycle are :

- GNSS receiver with an RTK subscription (not present in a normal VRU App on smartphone)
- Bicycle wheeltick sensor that gives to the positioning data the speed of the bicycle

- Inertial Measurement Unit

In the case of a pedestrian, all these sensors are not available, but the app relies on other positioning strategies, such as:

- GPS Android localization service for positioning
- Smartphone sensors available (accelerometer, gyroscope) for acceleration and heading

Navigation:

Handles the relevance of incoming messages and helps the user to fetch and match the maps according to the position and future path, which is an additional information that helps the system to infer the intention of the VRU in the crosspoint.

UI:

Handles the user behaviour according to its profile. A bicycle VRU has a different dynamic than a pedestrian and so warnings might be treated on a different way, being on-screen or with an acoustic warning. It presents and receives all information and requests from the user.

5.3.2.1.2.IT Environment view

The VRUs can be described in two forms, referring to Figure 99. Bicycles would have on board sensors, mainly for accurate positioning and speed. These sensors would be more accurate than the positioning sensors present in the smartphone and contributes to the app positioning as data input via WiFi or Bluetooth with the smartphone.

More precise positioning is compatible with the fact that bicycle speeds are higher than in the case of pedestrians. On the other hand, the pedestrians have only the app with no other sensors; internally an LDM is necessary to replicate the pedestrian environment and allow app to react to events. The network interface card present in the smartphone allows the APP to access edge services.

Figure 99: IT Environment view Connected VRU

5.3.2.1.3.State of development

- Communication: completed, missing message relevance filter for incoming messages.
- Positioning: mobile-based positioning techniques (GPS, smartphone sensors) are completed. Not all techniques of positioning are on for VRU app; positioning sensors on bicycle is under development; hardware ready with functionality, the custom firmware is under definition.

- Navigation: under development. Maps visualization showing user’s position, and other road users (VRUs or vehicles) real-time positions taken from incoming messages. Missing: map-matching, future path estimation, relevance of incoming messages.
- UI: almost completed. Map visualization of road users is available but still planned for further visual improvements. Users can setup their user types based on their means of transport state (bicycle, pedestrian, or vehicle). Different natures of warnings for different user types are under definitions.

5.3.3. Connected roadside entities

5.3.3.1. Roadside Units

5.3.3.1.1. Functional view

The figure depicts the functionality of the RSU/SPU highlighting the functionality developed for PoDIUM. Given that the RSU is also an SPU, it has functionality corresponding to RSUs, such as messaging, communication and C-ITS routing functionality; it has SPU functionality such as perception and sensing functions for cameras and LiDARs. In the case of UC4 RSUs are also SPUs.

Figure 100: RSU functionality for UC4

Msg Output

This functionality is mainly for C-ITS messages upload to reach the services in the edge; in particular the C-ITS handling functions and have access to the Digital Twin. Messages are adapted and sent to these services following their required path. This function holds for messages sent out of RSU via 5G. Those messages might be forwarded coming from the short range functions.

Short Range

This deals with the short range messages being handled in binary format and the interactions with the attestation procedures with neighbouring vehicles. In initial phases of the development and integration, some CPM messages are generated in the RSU directed to vehicles.

C-ITS Routing

This covers routing dedicated to C-ITS messages; it identifies the source of a message to be routed to the required output. The possible cases are input/output messages, short range and CPM messages in output to contribute to the digital twin data of the crosspoint.

Remote Attestor

This functionality handles the attestation procedures required to support the integrity verification of the OBUs present in the neighbouring CAV. It searches for the CAV corresponding TPA and

TPA – Trust Platform Agent

Trust Platform Agent functionality is the client functions that search for a Remote Attestor in order to make its integrity verified and to be authorized to send packets to the edge services. This functionality comprises the Trust Platform Module, which is explained in Section 5.5.1.1.

5.3.3.1.2.Sequence view between functional components

In this subsection, the different interactions regarding the RSU functionality will be described. In the case of the TPA and Remote Attestor functionality, the interactions have been described in the Trust scenario and in the Trust and Integrity section.

RSU access relay

This is one of the most common sequences executed since it allows vehicles to transmit C-ITS messages to the MEC via short range interfaces. It requires a previous registration when service starts up. Then all C-ITS messages involved in the crosspoint and transmitted via short range will be forwarded to the edge service (CCAM-Broker).

Figure 101: Access relay sequence

5.3.3.1.3.IT Environment view

The RSU can be deployed with the following components: a main computing board running most of the functionality in containers, and the networking functions on another dedicated hardware, with all interfaces attached. An ethernet switch connects these two hardware components with the Camera and LIDAR sensors.

This RSU would have a TPM chip as described in the trust and integrity section (in Section 5.5.1) connected via SPI. The attestation and Trust agents (TPA client and Attestation) are present also in the main hardware.

Figure 102: RSU IT environment view

5.3.3.1.4.Location

The partners have found a proper crosspoint to place the RSU and the experimentation of UC4. The RSU location was constrained by short range coverage and visibility over pedestrian strips.

The final location is the crosspoint located in Turin in corso Maroncelli and via Ventimiglia:

Figure 103: RSU location for UC4

The red point locates the position of the RSU. The line of sight of antennas reach vehicles along both intersecting roads and it was installed on a height of 4.5m.

The place was selected due to the visibility of all the crosspoint and the availability of traffic light information.

5.3.3.1.5.State of development

The current state of the component development is the following:

- Msg Output: ready for deployment
- Short Range: Initially will be working with ITS-G5 for first tests. PC5 interfaces not yet installed or configured.
- C-ITS Router: under ready for deployment

5.3.3.2. Sensor Processing Units

In UC4 the SPU share the functionality with RSU, so part of the information from RSUs hold for SPU.

5.3.3.2.1. Functional View

In Figure 100 the functional blocks are depicted; here the specific SPU functional block is outlined:

Perception

Perception function oversees detecting objects and recognize physical details such as size, type and direction. It constitutes the first step in acquiring real-time information from the crosspoint. As a result of this processing a fusion between camera and LiDAR streams is done to produce CPM messages either joint or independently from every source.

To produce a joint CPM, the process is as follows:

- Using a neural network all the road actors are detected from the live video.
- A tracking algorithm is performed on the detected road actors, in such a way to associate to each one of them an ID that must be consistent between frames.
- This information is then merged with the pointcloud extracted from the LiDAR in order to compute, for each road actor, the dimensions and the real position.
- This can then be used, on multiple frames, to estimate the speed of the road actors.
- All these detected info of the road actors will be inserted into the CPM message.

An alternative approach is to use the two sensors as two different sources and merge their information after their CPM have been generated, in this case, the process is as follows:

- Using a neural network all the road actors are detected from the live video.
- A tracking algorithm is performed on the detected road actors, in such a way to associate to each one of them an ID that must be consistent between frames.
- A georeferencing algorithm is performed, to map the pixel coordinate of the detected object into a real-world position. This information is then added into the camera CPM.
- Using a neural network specialized in pointclouds, from the LiDAR, the road actors are detected and their dimension and position is inserted into another CPM.
- Both CPM are sent individually to the DT, that will then try to merge them, if possible.

5.3.3.2.2. Sequence view between functional components

C-ITS sensor stream

The perception function receives the streams from camera and LiDAR and produces CPM messages with a certain periodicity of (value here). CPM messages are then routed to the 5G network to reach the edge services. In other cases, for testing purposes, the CPMs can be routed to the neighbouring vehicle via short range. (see Figure 104)

Figure 104: C-ITS Sensor Stream flow

5.3.3.2.3. IT Environment view

The SPU environment view is inherited from the Figure 102 which depicts all components, including SPU.

5.3.3.2.4. Location

For SPU location, please refer to Figure 103, where the position of the RSU is depicted; SPU and sensors are in the same roadside post. The triangle indicates the orientation of the sensors. This allows to cover three pedestrian strips and the centre of the crosspoint.

5.3.3.2.5. State of development

Currently perception development status:

- CPM generation working, and DENM generation working, pending configuration for tests. Fusion between both sensors is at 80%.

5.4. Services and Data Exchange

5.4.1. Functional components

Figure 105: Functional View UC4

Traffic Information

This module acts as a middleware between external C-ITS sources and the PoDIUM platform, inserting this external data into the Digital Twin (through the CCAM Broker). The traffic information module interacts with the Traffic Management Centers (TMC) of Turin, from which the traffic data and events monitored by the TMC are obtained.

Remote Attestor

This functionality is the equivalent of Remote attestation present on the RSUs, but in this case allows the RSUs and OBUs to make their integrity verified. It handles the OBU/RSU access to the broker. Once it receives attestation requests for join and maintains a relationship with the OBUs and RSUs to check their integrity periodically and renewing user access.

Digital Twin

Digital Twin acts as an aggregator of the information retrieved from all the different sources. It receives data from all the possible data sources in the scenario and merges them in a simple-to-access way. The Digital Twin is composed by a series of different submodule, including:

- **CCAM Broker:** a Message Broker, implementing the pub/sub approach. It has also in charge the access management after interacting with the Attestor in the trust scenario. In that case CCAM Broker releases the credentials and maintains them during the amount of attestation periods that the CAV OBU is under MEC coverage.
- **Encode Decode:** This functionality handles the encoding and decoding of the C-ITS messages; CCAM broker uses this functionality to generate/consume messages into the Digital Twin.

- **Data Fusion:** this module reads information published in the DT and detects if multiple sensors perceived the same object; in this case, associates to that object the merged information from all the sources.
- **Truthfulness module:** this module associates to each detected road actor a truthfulness value based on how many different sources detected the presence of the object and the reliability of each one of them.
- **A database:** this database contains all the information available on the road status, already merged and valued by the other modules of the Digital Twin.
- **REST API:** a REST server providing access to the data elaborated inside the Digital Twin.

Vulnerable Intersection Movement Assistant (VIMA)

VIMA considers the specific aspects described for the scenarios of the UC4. The VIMA module processes the trusted data to support manoeuvres of the vehicle. In addition to coordinate and extend its perception range. As inputs, VIMA receives the positions of the road users detected on the intersection, with their speed and heading (if available) from the Digital Twin of the road. Resulting on:

- Collision risk prediction: Considering the detected road users, including data from connected VRUs when available.
- Risk level quantification: Categorize by high, medium, low;
- Minimizing the risks of VRUs and vehicles: Providing them suggestions on how to act in the intersection, sending messages into the CCAM Broker.

5.4.2. Data Flow and Storage

The following three general stages outline the flow of the data in the UC4. The originating ITS is where the events are detected by the sensors installed in the intersection (i.e., cameras), the detection sensors of the vehicle, as well as the data generated by the application used by the VRU. Each of the actors are using its own ITS application (VRU or OBU) to transfer continuously data to the edge.

At the edge, the C-ITS services gather all messages received from the actors (e.g., CPM, CAM, VAM, etc.); and from the road infrastructure (e.g., SPATEM, MAPEM). Therefore, a digital twin of the crossroad is created and updated continuously.

This is the regime condition of the platform in UC4. Services, such as VIMA and truthfulness module monitor continuously the status of the crossroad and generate:

- Fused CPMs with higher reliability than single-sensor CPMs to be used by the road users (CAV).
- DENMs with high information quality informing road users (VRUs and CAV) that events have taken place.
- IVIMs with the timing information necessary for the CAV to take the manoeuvre in the crosspoint.

5.4.2.1. General view of the exchange of information

This section specifies the information exchange, in terms of C-ITS messages (with reference to ETSI standard) and semantic interoperability aspects. The message exchange between entities is specified in the activity diagrams within UC4 scenario descriptions.

In all scenarios, there is a regime initial condition in which the message exchange starts: The SPUs are sending CPMs with their perceptions to the edge services (CCAM_Broker). Also CAV and VRU contribute with CAMs and VAMs; additionally RSUs forward CAMs sent via short range communication. SPATEM and MAPEM messages are being forward from local municipality (not shown in diagrams) through CCAM Broker.

Straight

In absence of VRUs, the vehicle in a first case might pass the crosspoint using only the information provided by the PDU via SPATEM/MAPEM thanks to its internal functions. In presence of irregular VRUs, the CAV can cross by using the fused CPM produced by the truthfulness module following the camera observations, CPMs will be consumed by the legacy perception functions of the vehicle. The vehicle can go straight also with the DENM information generated by VIMA (hidden in the diagram behind Truthfulness Module); CAV uses then spotted irregular VRU crossing DENM information to regulate its speed profile and avoid the imminent accident.

Figure 106: UC4 MSC Straight Scenario Description

Right Turn

Once the VRU is detected physically through CAV sensors, the CAV can stop automatically as its local function states. In the case when all sensors have detected the VRU, the VRU-aware Intersection Movement Assistance service (VIMA) detects a possible collision and sends an IVIM message, passing via the OBU; the OBU determines its relevance to the vehicle and transmits it to CAV host. In the case VIMA does not detect a collision, only an IVIM is sent with indications for the CAV to pass.

Figure 107: UC4 MSC Right Turn Scenario Description

Left Turn

This sequence diagram states that CAV and VRUs are moving, both users receive fused CPMs with the presence of other road users, with consolidated information. C-ITS messages are decoded and filtered so that only relevant payloads are sent to the LDM. The VIMA produces an IVIM message containing the timeslots for crossing. Given that CAV during the crossing would find eventually other vehicles, the fused CPMs sent by the contribution of RSU and CAV sensors, will allow the vehicle to cross, regulating the actual timeslot to cross. CAV will eventually stop in the center of the crosspoint waiting for other vehicles (detected via fused CPMs) to pass.

Figure 108: UC4 MSC Left Turn Scenario Description

Trust

Trust scenario does not have CCAM messages, since it happens just before transmissions. The trust protocol agent present in the CAV OBU must search for the broker and finds the remote attester, they establish a secure session and join to the trust protocol. The attester will require to the agent all necessary OBU hashes until the integrity report is produced. The rest is done by the communication of the remote attester with the CCAM Broker, since the broker can handle dynamically its users' lifecycle.

Figure 109: UC4 MSC Scenario Trust

5.4.2.2. Message exchange

Considering the scenarios described, the C-ITS services are generated considering the interactions between the CAV (e.g., going straight, turning to the left or to the right), the road infrastructure sensors which monitor the roads, and the connected road user at the pedestrian crossing. C-ITS Services are intended to prevent an accident or a potential collision between the road users through alerts or warnings. Therefore, resulting on multiple standardization bodies working on technical documentation on how to deploy and operate the C-ITS Services. Between them, it is worth to mention: the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), the Car-2-Car Communication Consortium (C2C-CC), and the platform of harmonized C-ITS deployment in Europe (C-Roads).

Considering the C2C-CC 2020 Roadmap [17], the UC4 aims to deploy and integrate Day 1 C-ITS services: Awareness Driving (i.e., SPATEM, MAPEM, CAM, DENM), Day 2 C-ITS: Sensing Driving (i.e., CPM) and DAY 3+ C-ITS services: Cooperative Driving (i.e., IVIM, VAM). Therefore, using Day 1 to the exchange of status data of the road infrastructure (e.g., signal phase and timing), and to aware road users about potential risks. Day 2 to share information detected by road or vehicle sensors (Advanced Warnings). Day 3 to coordinate automated vehicle actions in complex traffic situations (Automated Coordination). The following table presents the relation between the C-ITS Services, the message type as well as the respective standard and version to be used in the UC4.

DAY	C-ITS Service	Message Type	Standard	Version
1	Traffic Light Manoeuvre (TLM) service	SPATEM	ETSI TS 103 301	2.1.1
1	Road and Lane Topology (RLT) service	MAPEM	ETSI TS 103 301	2.1.1
1	Cooperative Awareness (CA) basic service	CAM	ETSI EN 103 900	2.1.1
1	Decentralized Environmental Notification (DEN) basic service	DENM	ETSI EN 103 831	2.1.1
2	Collective Perception Service (CPS)	CPM	ETSI TS 103 324	2.1.1
3+	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information (IVI) service	IVIM	ETSI TS 103 301	2.1.1
3+	VRU Basic Service (VBS)	VAM	ETSI TS 103 300-3	2.1.1

Table 7: Messages used in UC4

5.4.2.1. Semantic interoperability aspects

In the case of the IVIM message, there are aspects to be clarified in relation to the implementation of the message and its corresponding interpretation on the CAV's OBU to calculate IVIM relevance and consume its information. The vehicle needs a time window to perform the crossing manoeuvre, indicating the time where the pedestrian lane is busy, so these two times can be coded as follows.

Absolute time + Relative time (time counter): Using the fields "validFrom," "timestamp," and "minimum Awareness Time."

In the predictive phase, to avoid the contention of the pedestrian lane, the timeslot is given by validFrom and [validFrom + minimumAwarenessTime]. It could not be used when the pedestrian crosses the street as validFrom would be in the past, but it encodes the expected future behaviour of the lane occupancy by the pedestrian.

In the crossing phase:

- Combining timestamp + minimum Awareness Time. Using these as the start and final time used to the crossing.
- Using only the timestamp + minimum Awareness Time as the end of crossing time and consider this phase as “its crossing”. This system is based on a rapid IVIM update frequency as the minimum Awareness Time is required to be modified accordingly to act as a counter.

If it is forced the "validFrom" to be used in the past, both phases could always use "validFrom" as the initial traversal time.

5.5. Trust and Integrity

5.5.1. Software Integrity

5.5.1.1. Trusted Computing Approach

The Trusted Computing (TC) approach, as described in deliverable D2.2 [2], is a set of interoperable technologies to achieve a level of trust in the behaviour of a device leveraging a hardware Root of Trust (RoT) called Trusted Platform Module 2.0 (TPM). The TPM 2.0 is a tamper-resistant cryptographic hardware integrated with the system board that implements cryptographic functions on top of which more complex features can be built following the TCG specification TPM2.0 [9]. A device implementing TC principles forms a Trusted Computing Base (TCB).

5.5.1.2. Trusted Computing Base (TCB) Development

The following sections describe the work done so far on the PoDIUM LINKS' OBU to establish a Trusted Computing Base (TCB). As described in deliverable D3.1 [1], both the OBU and the RSU act as a TCB, so this term will be used to refer to both devices.

5.5.1.3. Hardware integration and software configuration

The development of a TCB starts with the integration of the HW TPM into the device. The TPM can be installed on the Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI). This allows the TPM to communicate with the microcontroller via the synchronous serial communication protocol. The first step to integrate the TPM on the devices is to identify the correct pinout configuration:

- SCLK, the pin for clock signal
- MISO (Master In, Slave Out), the slave output pin
- MOSI (Master Out, Slave In), the master pin output pin
- CS (Chip Select), used by the master to choose which slave to communicate with.

The pins should be connected to the corresponding TPM pins, i.e. wiring the MOSI pin of the board with MOSI pin of the TPM. After physically connecting the TPM, it is necessary to configure the Linux kernel by activating the TPM and SPI kernel modules.

The SPI controller of the board must be configured following the manufacturer's instructions, usually compiling the kernel with the configuration

```
CONFIG_SPI=y
```

```
CONFIG_SPI_<controller_name>=y
```

according to the SPI controller of the board.

The TPM kernel module is activated by recompiling the kernel with the configuration:

```
CONFIG_TCG_TPM=y
```

```
CONFIG_TCG_TIS_CORE=y
```

```
CONFIG_TCG_TIS_SPI=y
```

To complete the registration of the TPM, it is necessary to add its configuration in the Devicetree of the Linux kernel. A DevicetreeBlob (DTB) [10] is a compiled data structure used to describe the hardware components and their configuration in an embedded system. It provides a way to describe the hardware platform in a hardware-independent manner, making it easier to port and to maintain

operating system code across different hardware platforms. The DTB includes information about devices, memory regions, interrupt controllers, GPIO (General Purpose Input/Output) pins and their roles, maximum operating frequency, and other hardware-specific details.

By performing these steps, the Linux kernel can register the TPM correctly. A way to validate the registration is to run the shell command *dmesg*, a Unix command that displays kernel messages on the screen, which should show the successful probe message, as depicted in Figure 110, or to check that */dev/tpm0* is present among the devices registered to */dev*.

```

root@inx8mp-var-dart:~# dmesg | grep tpm_tis_spi
[  1.287202] calling tpm_tis_spi_driver_init+0x0/0x28 @ 1
[  1.287233] initcall tpm_tis_spi_driver_init+0x0/0x28 returned 0 after 18 usecs
[  2.120902] tpm_tis_spi spi1.0: 2.0 TPM (device-id 0x18, rev-id 22)
root@inx8mp-var-dart:~# sudo ls /dev/tpm
tpm0      tpmrm0
root@inx8mp-var-dart:~#
    
```

Figure 110: Successfully connected TPM

The next step is to make the TPM2.0 available to the applications that will use it by installing the user space programs that provide the means to interact with the TPM2.0.

- **TPM2 Software Stack (TSS)**, the low-level implementation of the TPM2.0 APIs to interact with the TPM2.0. To install the TSS, follow the instructions in the official repository [11].
- **TPM2 Access Broker & Resource Manager**, is a system daemon implementing the TPM2.0 Access Broker (TAB) & Resource Manager (RM) specifications from the TCG. TPM2.0 has a limited amount of memory and does not support multiple sessions and synchronization between processes, so it needs an access broker such as *tpm2-abrmd*. To install it, follow the instructions in the official repository[12].
- **TPM2 Tools**, a set of command-line software used to interact with the TPM2.0, which uses the TSS to perform tasks such as: key management, sealing and unsealing, remote attestation, and platform configuration. It is installed by following the instructions in the official repository [13].

Once installed, the TPM2.0 can be tested. Figure 111 shows the output of the *tpm2_pcrread* command, provided by the *tpm2-tools* software, to demonstrate the correct software installation and the proper functioning of the TPM2.0 by displaying the PCRs value.

```
inx8mp-var-dart login: root
root@inx8mp-var-dart:~# sudo tpm2_pcrread sha256
sha256:
0 : 0x5C86AE349FDA9250690A30FD460E10B9601C681905ABE9778E6500F0006E3201
1 : 0x15640E3007030696F29B95D962C802DEA1F75521650B331A127179005FC175D6
2 : 0x76832004FC5ABA4A4A92CBC1C967F7A3E8404AF56ACAE80B5670FEF53AB0539
3 : 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
4 : 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
5 : 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
6 : 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
7 : 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
8 : 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
9 : 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
10: 0xB001E884039FC3BEEE4B7B5FB47AF8AF66574D57ECF1AA31AFDF8E1551643868
11: 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
12: 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
13: 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
14: 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
15: 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
16: 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
17: 0xFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFF
18: 0xFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFF
19: 0xFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFF
20: 0xFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFF
21: 0xFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFF
22: 0xFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFFF
23: 0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000
root@inx8mp-var-dart:~#
```

Figure 111: Output of the tpm2_pcrread command output

5.5.1.4. Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) kernel module

Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) [14] is a kernel module that deals with integrity functions, designed to enhance the security of the Linux operating system. It allows a security system to verify the integrity of critical system files and executables. On a policy based, IMA measures the digest (SHA-256) of files at the time of access, and these measurements are stored in a log, analysed as a part of the Remote Attestation protocol to ensure that files have not been tampered with or compromised. As a form of log integrity itself, IMA extends the PCR10 of the TPM2.0 with each measurement in a deterministic manner. A verifier, while analysing the event log reconstructs the value of PCR10, as described in the deliverable D2.2, and it verifies that it is equal to the PCR10 in the TPM Quote. If the recalculated value differs, the verifier has proof that the received IMA log has been forged or tampered with, so the TCB is considered untrusted. Figure 112 shows an example of the IMA log measurement. The first command shown in the figure shows the initial state of the IMA log. Then, a file is deleted, and the log tail is displayed again. The last line of the log displays the measurement of the system application `rm.coreutils`, because IMA recorded the execution of the `rm` command and measured the hash value of the application corresponding to the executed command.

A remote attester can notice if an unexpected program or a modified version has been executed by analyzing which applications are present in the log and if the hash values of the applications match the expected (golden) values or not.

The IMA module can be activated by recompiling the kernel with the following configuration:

```
CONFIG_INTEGRITY=y
CONFIG_IMA=y
CONFIG_CMDLINE="... ima_policy=tcb ima_hash=sha256 ima_template=ima-sig"
```

In some cases, it was found that the TPM module was not loaded in time and IMA activates the TPM2.0 bypass, not extending the PCR10. The solution is to identify which kernel dependencies make the TPM module wait by recompiling the kernel with the parameter:

```
CONFIG_CMDLINE="... initcall_debug ..."
```

which shows the start point and end point of each kernel module during boot. After identifying the modules there are two possible ways to anticipate their execution: if they are compiled as a module `CONFIG_<module_name>=m` they should be compiled built-in into the kernel `CONFIG_<module_name>=y`

```

m8np-var-dart:~# sudo tail /sys/kernel/security/integrity/ina/ascii_runtime_measurements
bade3d7051781afDef0e092648d31cb7dcc2 ina-ng sha256:725b85a19b0ea8278d0f631513e85e5e90faa4ce9c10a40522ace5d8859b284 /home/root/.bash_history
4ef97e2dce06f88b78db71ff1c2b228416d ina-ng sha256:cc713926f66e248643c6d1f5835ac9473b9d03a3c3db814f1f2a2186cf7a32d65 /etc/inputrc
5e1a92379768b7bf6a775f4e121e7ece3bce ina-ng sha256:86d6c72a89565311d6a17a826b4f2413d5dda833f09f38dc055e55444f32edd7 /usr/bin/sudo
af7aa1a43d2c2879b966b92ce3596de4c0de ina-ng sha256:90d72cc54e38ddfcdcf5361b383ed9ca055d6cf1e3c146bcf023bb130eeb1928 /usr/lib/sudo/libsudo_util.so
e132179a212baeeb58cb2db5cdaa4c48a6a4 ina-ng sha256:a13bedd91cf288ce9d6f572ca5f830ae7ccf02168b51a103786795e21cde76a7 /etc/sudo.conf
79101cef776633db4fea14cdd94b21e4b04d ina-ng sha256:a3a080e9ff00bf9d1ec1185c7ef41de157f17997c62177f9ecf6df0a86fd0b50b /usr/lib/sudo/sudoers.so
75bc051c041208097e3fcef3e29ddac6d47f ina-ng sha256:f9a9eb21cc7cccec67bfe982b1268dacea831946ad64863921029212e588f9c8 /etc/sudoers
df7526363e2fa2e6c99c4151e9d726653d0e ina-ng sha256:4f0c33a85f8f63985ed3fa3e7a23533ffe92e515b6f11eafdf9be1072bdac32d /etc/pam.d/sudo
ee800d336009c5f6d958cb8581881ca20d96 ina-ng sha256:375a5944cb61eaf741cdd84e27ed0f964687c3153375ad2043fe9cde4e748f0 /bin/touch.coreut ils
16a754bfee4092e9bf716e1aa77c67b252cb ina-ng sha256:3c64c905eac21c6291c7a726e2734707256edea72d507081130fdd7b1baeab38 /usr/bin/tail.coreut ils
m8np-var-dart:~# sudo rm /var/config/file
m8np-var-dart:~# sudo tail /sys/kernel/security/integrity/ina/ascii_runtime_measurements
4ef97e2dce06f88b78db71ff1c2b228416d ina-ng sha256:cc713926f66e248643c6d1f5835ac9473b9d03a3c3db814f1f2a2186cf7a32d65 /etc/inputrc
5e1a92379768b7bf6a775f4e121e7ece3bce ina-ng sha256:86d6c72a89565311d6a17a826b4f2413d5dda833f09f38dc055e55444f32edd7 /usr/bin/sudo
af7aa1a43d2c2879b966b92ce3596de4c0de ina-ng sha256:90d72cc54e38ddfcdcf5361b383ed9ca055d6cf1e3c146bcf023bb130eeb1928 /usr/lib/sudo/libsudo_util.so
e132179a212baeeb58cb2db5cdaa4c48a6a4 ina-ng sha256:a13bedd91cf288ce9d6f572ca5f830ae7ccf02168b51a103786795e21cde76a7 /etc/sudo.conf
79101cef776633db4fea14cdd94b21e4b04d ina-ng sha256:a3a080e9ff00bf9d1ec1185c7ef41de157f17997c62177f9ecf6df0a86fd0b50b /usr/lib/sudo/sudoers.so
75bc051c041208097e3fcef3e29ddac6d47f ina-ng sha256:f9a9eb21cc7cccec67bfe982b1268dacea831946ad64863921029212e588f9c8 /etc/sudoers
df7526363e2fa2e6c99c4151e9d726653d0e ina-ng sha256:4f0c33a85f8f63985ed3fa3e7a23533ffe92e515b6f11eafdf9be1072bdac32d /etc/pam.d/sudo
ee800d336009c5f6d958cb8581881ca20d96 ina-ng sha256:375a5944cb61eaf741cdd84e27ed0f964687c3153375ad2043fe9cde4e748f0 /bin/touch.coreut ils
16a754bfee4092e9bf716e1aa77c67b252cb ina-ng sha256:3c64c905eac21c6291c7a726e2734707256edea72d507081130fdd7b1baeab38 /usr/bin/tail.coreut ils
b9fba892148a4e6acd11e76071b4cb337b95 ina-ng sha256:f1e9a5e8f1b66cc0740ad5e82f11b8501f3eb04039b8a3ddfc93cf9b78c8a75 /bin/rm.coreut ils
m8np-var-dart:~#

```

Figure 112: Example of IMA measurements

If they are already compiled built-in in the kernel, the boot priority order must be changed by modifying the type of initialization function to a higher priority function.

5.5.1.5. Secure Boot

With reference to Figure 10 in deliverable D2.2, the Secure Boot(strap) is the first portion of the Authenticated Boot(strap) that goes from the Trust Anchor (TA) up to the user space to build the Chain of Trust. Each software component is considered trusted at least to identify and to cryptographic verify the next component because it is built on the transitive property of trust. Since the Trust Anchor (TA) is trusted, the next authenticated component is trusted as well, due to the transitive property of trust, and can verify the subsequent component by extending the trust property. If the verification succeeds, the component is considered trusted and can be loaded and verify the next component but, if the verification fails, the bootstrap process stops. This choice is known as Trust Decision and, in the design of TCB's architecture developed for Podium, there are two Trust Decisions. The first trust decision is performed on the Secondary Program Loader (SPL), a minimal software that prepares the device to load the bootloader, and on the bootloader. The second trust decision is performed on the Linux image that is composed by the Device Tree Blob (DTB) and the Linux kernel.

This process is implemented through hardware-specific features of the microprocessor, as depicted in Figure 112. The OEM, which produces the board and the software that runs on it, generates a cryptographic key pair and the public part is permanently stored in a processor register. With the private key, the OEM signs the images that will run on that device and adds the signature to the final image. During the bootstrap, the final image is loaded in memory and the processor verifies the signature with public key permanently stored in his register. If it is successful, the image is executed, otherwise the boot phase is stopped.

Figure 113: High level description of the Secure Boot process

The Secure Boot in PoDIUM is implemented by the High Assurance Boot (HAB) provided by i.MX platforms of NXP. HAB is responsible for verifying and then loading the software images by using cryptographic operations. The i.MX platforms uses the bootloader U-Boot compiled with the HAB support `CONFIG_IMX_HAB=y`

because provides extra functions for HAB, such as the HAB status logs through the `hab_status` command and support the functionalities to extend the PCRs of the TPM2.0 (necessary for implementing the measured boot described in Section 5.5.1.6).

The HAB based procedure follows the same principles previously described with some additions. It verifies different program images at each trusted decision: the SPL and bootloader image (first trust decision), the DTB and Linux kernel image (second trust decision).

- **Initial preparation:** The OEM generates an RSA key pair and computes the public key digest, which is burned to a one-time programmable processor’s register called Efuse. Then the OEM generates the signature of the image with the private key. Then, the image, the signature and the public key are composed in the final image. The key generation and certificate creation procedure is performed through custom software provided by the vendor.
- **Trust decision:** HAB verifies the signature on the image to be executed with the public key. Then the microprocessor compares the hash the public key in the image with the hash of the public key in the eFuse register. If these checks are successful, the bootstrap continues, otherwise it is blocked.

With the HAB, the images that do not pass the verification generate an error called HAB events. In addition, when the device is deployed on the field, an HAB event blocks the bootstrap. Figure 114 shows the case of a successful verification by calling the `hab_status` command. In fact, the output of the command reports *No HAB Events Found!*

```

Secure boot disabled

HAB Configuration: 0xf0, HAB State: 0x66
No HAB Events Found!

u-boot=> 
  
```

Figure 114: Successful verification of the boot images during the secure boot procedure

5.5.1.6. Measured Boot

Over the years new bugs can be discovered, and older version of program images can be deprecated when they are found vulnerable to attacks. The Secure Boot does not restrict the utilization of these versions. A way to overcome this issue is to verify which version of the image is running during the remote attestation procedure against a set of golden values. This requires implementing the Measured Boot in addition to the Secure Boot. The Measured Boot is an extension of the Secure Boot that takes care of saving the measurements of the loaded images in the TPM during the bootstrap. The TPM2.0 acts as a Root of Trust for Storage via a set of PCRs, to securely accumulate the integrity measurements in the form of hashes. U-Boot provides a basic SPI driver and minimal TPM2.0 support to implement such a mechanism. They are enabled by recompiling it with the configurations:

SPI module

```
CONFIG_SPI=y
```

```
CONFIG_MXC_SPI=y
```

TPM module

```
CONFIG_TPM=y
```

```
CONFIG_TPM_V2=y
```

```
CONFIG_TPM2_TIS_SPI=y
```

The commands to measure and store the measurements in the PCRs

```
CONFIG_CMD_HASH=y
```

```
CONFIG_HASH_VERIFY=y
```

```
CONFIG_SHA256=y
```

```
CONFIG_CMD_TPM_V2=y
```

```
CONFIG_CMD_TPM=y
```

```
CONFIG_CMD_SPI=y
```

To calculate the hash of the images and to extend the PCR during bootstrap, U-Boot makes use of a configurable boot script. The script is executed the kernel boot phase. After enabling the U-boot modules, it is possible to write a script that executes the instructions to implement the measured boot. Figure 115 shows an example of a boot script that measures itself, the DTB and the Linux kernel image. The script first calculates the SHA256 of the images. Then extends the PCRs with the digests: PCR0 is extended with the digest of the bootscript file, PCR1 is extended with the digest of the DTB and the PCR2 is extended with digest of the Linux kernel image.

Figure 113 shows the value of the first three PCRs after the execution of the script. It is worth noting that the value of the three PCR coincide with the value of the PCR shown by the output of the `tpm2_pcread` command as in Figure 111.

A remote attester will use the value of the first 3 PCRs to check that the images running on the TCB are the expected ones, during the remote attestation procedure.

```

Measure boot.scr
715 bytes read in 2 ms (348.6 KiB/s)
sha256 for 42000000 ... 420002ca ==> 009275c1a6b425daf82d0629eb68bbb26e42038cd51392fb35bf779bf91c6882
PCR #0 content (21 known updates):
 5c 86 ae 34 9f da 92 50 69 0a 3d fd 46 0e 1d b9
 60 1c 68 19 05 ab e9 77 8e 65 d0 fd dd 6e 32 01
Measure dtb
64069 bytes read in 5 ms (12.2 MiB/s)
sha256 for 42000000 ... 4200fa44 ==> 5ed430c1b9c1e057836e5ca0e41230594b3e46e6b4ce694cbd873ce1815c2ec7
PCR #1 content (22 known updates):
 15 64 0e 3d d7 d3 06 96 f2 9b 95 d9 62 cb d2 de
 a1 f7 55 21 65 db 33 1a 12 71 79 dd 5f c1 75 d6
Image
12033515 bytes read in 500 ms (23 MiB/s)
Uncompressed size: 29166080 = 0x1BDD0A00
sha256 for 42000000 ... 43bd09ff ==> 19be4fd6ff3e550d2e821032ae2807033a4a6cee70dd73b163e95fd8bab4b449
PCR #2 content (23 known updates):
 76 83 20 04 fc 5a ba 4a 4a 92 cb c1 c9 67 f7 a3
 e8 40 4a f5 6a ca ee 80 b5 67 df ef 53 ab 05 39
Boot
  
```

Figure 115: Output of the bootscript showing the value of the first 3 PCRs correctly extended

The next version of this deliverable (named D3.3) will report on the development and tests of the remote attestation framework to challenge the TCBS (*i.e.*, OBUs and RSUs) in the system. The framework will be responsible for implementing the third trust decision at run time in a periodic fashion.

5.5.2. Redundancy-based Sensor Data Fusion

Different sensors, both on the VRU, CAV and infrastructure, will be used to create a Digital Twin of the road status as shown in Figure 116, that will contain the information about all the road actors detected, such as position, the dimensions, heading and speed.

However, an object could be sensed by different sensors, and in this case the Digital Twin may contain the same object multiple times, with different identifiers and slightly different properties, generating a false perspective of the road status. To avoid this, a Sensor Data Fusion module is implemented.

This module analyses each new added object in the Digital Twin and uses its properties to understand whether it is a second perception of an object already present in it. In that case, the Sensor Data Fusion will not add the new object in the Digital Twin but will update the old road actor merging the information measured by the two sensors. Furthermore, when the presence of an object is confirmed by a second sensor, the Truthfulness value of this object is increased, meaning that the information about that object is more reliable. The same process repeats for every new object arriving to the fusion algorithm.

To detect if different CPM from different source reference the same real road actor, we are developing a software algorithm that, taking into consideration two objects, all their properties and their timestamps within the CPM that has been published, the algorithm computes the probability of those two objects to be the same. If the probability is greater than a threshold, the two objects are merged inside the Digital Twin, if not, they are stored as different objects.

Consequently, the CPMs generated have more reliable information than when generated with a single sensor. The Multiple sensor sources contributing to truthfulness Multiple sensor sources contributing to truthfulness.

Figure 116: Multiple sensor sources contributing to truthfulness

6. Use Case 5: Risk Management in Highway Tunnel

UC5 “Risk Management in Highway Tunnel” is the motorway use case of the Italian Living Lab. It is demonstrated on the A22 “Autostrada del Brennero”, in a road segment which includes the tunnel next to the city of Trento. By means of roadside sensors as well as vehicles’ floating car data (CAM and CPM sent by connected vehicle), a dedicated application in the PoDIUM platform can quantify the risk level within the tunnel in order to inform the upcoming Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs), which can adapt and advance the automation level and/or safely and smoothly slow down. UC5 demonstrate that approaching CAV can receive DENM of road works warnings and hazard notifications, engage cooperative adaptive cruise control through cut-in manoeuvre management through CAM and perform cooperative perception, beneficial to highly automated driving, through the exchange of CPM with neighbour vehicles. An outstanding feature of UC5, is the continuity of vehicle position reference before, during and after the tunnel, by means of in-tunnel positioning solutions, which enable the vehicle self-localization (the latter thanks also to the onboard data fusion) as well as the common GNSS time referencing needed for V2X C-ITS stations to cooperate.

6.1. Scenario Descriptions

This use case has two big scenarios categories:

- Road works
- Traffic jam

6.1.1. Road Works

Two Road Works scenarios are considered from the point of view of the CAV: when the CAV is alone (Section 6.1.1.1) and when the CAV is following a CV with Cooperative adaptive Cruise Control activated (Section 6.1.1.2). In both cases the positioning is put into test, since inside the tunnel there is no sky view and the positioning depends on the systems deployed for UC5.

6.1.1.1. RWW with CAV only

The first scenario intends to demonstrate how the CAV, approaching the RWW, can be informed with due advance by the road infrastructure and perform a lane change (lateral control) and speed adaptation (longitudinal control) constantly being assisted by the infrastructure as shown in Figure 117. Continuity of CCAM service reception (in this case: DENM update) and geo-referencing is provided by the in-tunnel positioning solutions, but the goal is to see any effect when passing to open sky to in-tunnel, as the CAV open sky uses GNSS RTK and correction, while in-tunnel uses a reconstructed position (by SDR or trilateration solutions) in combination with its own sensor-based localization.

Figure 117: UC5 Scenario: Road Works Warning – CAV only (note : figure not in scale)

Timeline

- t0 - CAV drives on first lane: ACC is engaged at user-defined target speed
- t1 - RWW DENM and speed limits IVI from infrastructure is received by CAV
- t2 - CAV reaches the DENM validity area (> 600m) and notifies driver about lane change need
- t3 - CAV changes lane
- t4 - CAV uses IVI speed limit sequence (110, 90, 60 km/h) for longitudinal control
- t5 - CAV proceeds at 60 km/h along the construction zone (DENM speed limit)
- t6 - After construction zone end, CAV returns to user-defined target speed

Trigger

N/A.

Requisites

At least one localization solution available in tunnel.

Activity Diagram

Figure 118: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning – CAV only: activity diagram

6.1.1.2. RWW with cooperative ACC

The second and third scenarios add to the first one the Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control. The latter functionality enables to follow the vehicle in front by means of both in-vehicle sensors and cooperative messages of the vehicle being followed. The scenario in Figure 119 demonstrates how C-ACC is handled before, during, and after the roadworks (engaged/disengaged). The scenario in Figure 120 demonstrates how the CAV can automatically slow down when the CV communicates its intentions to merge before the roadworks. Both scenarios will show how the CAV, fusing V2X and sensing, can handle data coming from the infrastructure – which cause the lane change request and temporary cruise speed limits to the longitudinal control – with data coming from the CV – which determine the engagement/disengagement of C-ACC and the actual cruise speed. Again, the goal here is to assess how positioning (and the related challenge in tunnel) affects the behaviour.

Figure 119: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning – CAV and CV: car follow with C-ACC

Figure 120: UC5 Scenario: “cut-in” with C-ACC (at Road Works)

Timeline (“car follow” scenario as shown in Figure 119)

- t0 - CAV and CV proceed on first lane with C-ACC engaged (CAV speed follows CV speed from CAM)
- t1 - RWW DENM and speed limits IVI from infrastructure is received at CAV and CV
- t2 - As soon as CV changes lane, C-ACC is disengaged
- t3 - CAV reaches the DENM validity area (ca. 600m) and notifies driver about lane change need
- t4 - CAV changes to the same lane as CV. C-ACC is available again.
- t5 - CAV User engages C-ACC again.
- t6 - CAV controls speed in construction zone according to CV, within speed limit sequence (IVI+ DENM)

Trigger
N/A.

Requisites
At least one localization solution available in tunnel.

Activity Diagram (“car follow” scenario)

Figure 121: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning: car follows with C-ACC: Activity Diagram

Timeline (“cut-in” scenario as shown in Figure 120)

- T0 - CAV proceeds on second lane with ACC engaged.
- t1 - RWW DENM and speed limits IVI from infrastructure is received at CAV
- t2 - CAV reaches the DENM validity area (ca. 600m) and notifies driver about Road Works
- t2 - CV intends to cut-in, in order to change to second lane, which is open
- t3 – Upon CAV user cut-in validation, CAV slows down to ease CV cut-in
- t5 - CV changes to the same lane as CAV. C-ACC is available
- t6 - CAV User engages C-ACC.
- t7 - CAV controls speed in construction zone according to CV, within speed limit sequence (IVI+ DENM)

Trigger
N/A.

Requisites
At least one localization solution available in tunnel.

Activity Diagram (“cut-in” scenario)

Figure 122: UC5 Scenario “cut-in” with C-ACC ” (at Road Works): Activity Diagram

6.1.2. Traffic Jam

6.1.2.1. Traffic Jam Alert with take-over

While the previous scenarios focused on the CAV behaviour and were based on the reception of DENM messages directly from the road operator, this scenario introduces the data flow of traffic/event detection and the risk management by PoDIUM platform at the infrastructure (see Figure 123). Roadside sensors detect vehicles going into and coming out of the tunnel, while RSU’s get CAM and CPM from CAV and CV’s. This information, together with the original Traffic Jam information of the road operator, is used by the PoDIUM Risk Assessment module to evaluate a level of risk and issue a Traffic Jam Alert DENM of high information quality. A CAV is coming in in a state of conditional automation or below (note: the prototype vehicle will drive up to L2 in the public road of the living lab, with L3 in terms of perception only). Upon the reception of this alert, the in-vehicle system requests the driver to take over control.

Figure 123: UC5 Traffic Jam Alert with take-over

Timeline

- t0 -RSU's with vehicle counters detect traffic in the tunnel area
- t1 - Risk Management module is informed of queue in tunnel from RSU and publishes HLN-TJA DENM
- t2 - CAV approaches with Highway assist (SAE L2) or ACC (L1)
- t3 - HLN-TJA DENM is received at CAV
- t4 - CAV reaches DENM validity area (>600m from event position) and notifies take-over need
- t5 - Driver disengages automated function (L2 or L1) to manual driving (L0).

Trigger

Traffic Jam condition by Risk management module.

Requisites

RSU and vehicle counter available

At least one localization solution available in tunnel.

Activity Diagram

Figure 124: UC5 Scenario Traffic Jam Alert with take-over: Activity Diagram

6.1.2.2. Traffic Jam Alert and L4 ODD

The following two scenarios are based on the previous Traffic Jam Alert by the PoDIUM risk management application, but in this case the CAV is coming in in a state of high automation (note: SAE L4 in terms perception only). Among the ODD conditions, the ego-vehicle must position itself at lane level, follow a CV with C-ACC (with no vehicle in the middle) and get detected objects by the CV being followed with the ego-vehicle. All these three conditions are strongly dependent on the availability and performance of positioning technologies. In the ideal case (which is also the open sky case) in the first scenario of this kind (Figure 125) the CAV should keep in the L4 ODD and therefore, by receiving Traffic Jam Assist, perform a smooth slowdown manoeuvre without exiting the ODD. In the second scenario (Figure 126) a non-connected vehicle enters in the middle between CV and CAV. The real case will be measured in the test site: as previously said, positioning should be available throughout the tunnel transition, but the positioning sources (and expected quality) in-tunnel are different from the open sky ones. Should any blocking technical limits be evaluated, we may consider demonstrating an alternative “L4 ODD keep” scenario in open sky (e.g. with a TJA DENM before the tunnel).

Figure 125: UC5 Scenario “L4 ODD keep” (with Traffic Jam Alert)

Figure 126: UC5 Scenario Traffic Jam Alert where vehicle exits the ODD

Timeline

“ODD keep” scenario

t0 -RSU's with vehicle counters detect traffic in the tunnel area

t1 - Risk Management module is informed of queue in tunnel from RSU and publishes HLN-TJA DENM

t2 - CAV is coming in L4 perception ODD: C-ACC “car follow” (through CAM) AND “extended perception” (CPM)

t3 - HLN-TJA DENM is received at CAV

t4 - CAV reaches DENM validity area (>600m from event position) and notifies TJA and slowdown need

t5 - CAV slows down keeping in ODD, as car follow and extended perception are still enabled

“ODD exit” scenario

t0 -RSU's with vehicle counters detect traffic in the tunnel area

t1 - Risk Management module is informed of queue in tunnel from RSU and publishes HLN-TJA DENM

t2- CAV is coming in L4 perception ODD: C-ACC “car follow” (through CAM) AND “extended perception” (CPM)

t3 - HLN-TJA DENM is received at CAV

t4 - CAV reaches DENM validity area (>600m from event position) and notifies TJA and slowdown need

t5 - Non-connected vehicle cuts-in. ODD exit. CAV slows down in ACC (L1) or manually (L0).

Trigger

Traffic Jam condition by Risk management module.

Requisites

RSU and vehicle counter available

At least one localization solution available in tunnel.

The following activity and sequence diagrams include both variants of the scenario.

Activity Diagram

Figure 127: UC5 Scenario of “L4 ODD keep” and “L4 ODD exit” (with Traffic Jam Alert)

6.2. Communication Aspects

This chapter describes the communication aspects of UC5 of the Italian LL.

The goal is to provide an overview of the communication architecture, the communication entities, and the use of communication technologies within the UC5.

6.2.1. Communication Architecture

The communication architecture chapter provides a description of the use case specific communication view including all involved entities. Furthermore, it provides insights of the communication of the entities and their role for the implementation of the use case scenarios, the communication technologies and how they are utilized in the use case, and finally the specific communication features that support specific aspects of the use case. The communication view for UC5 is shown in Figure 128.

Figure 128: UC5 Communication View

The local data processing and communications layer comprises connected and automated vehicles and RSUs.

Connected and automated vehicles and RSUs communicate with the MEC / Cloud infrastructure via 5G/4G mobile cellular network compliant with 3GPP Rel.16 / 3GPP Rel. 14 [39]; wireless short-range communications between RSUs and CAVs are implemented according ITS ETSI EN 302 663 [40] G5 standard in the beginning, then with ETSI EN 303 613 [41] PC5 (3GPP Rel. 14/15) standard in future releases.

Regarding UC5 neither the 5G network nor the Edge Computing infrastructure will be used, as the latency requirements of the use case do not require these technologies.

6.2.2. Communication Entities

The individual entities have communication capabilities to fulfil the requirements of the use case scenario.

6.2.2.1. Connected Automated Vehicle (CAV) and Connected Vehicle (CV)

Role:

In UC5 two vehicles exchange presence dynamics and intentions (CAM) as well as the detected objects (CPM) with each other, receive warnings (DENM) and signage (IVI) from the highway operator. CAM

and CPM sent by the vehicle can be used by the roadside systems as floating car data to consolidate the risk management computation. For this purpose, the CAV prototype is equipped with an Onboard Unit providing ITS-G5, PC5 and 5G connectivity, although 5G network and MEC connectivity is not present in UC5 test location. Additionally, the vehicle communicates via ITS-G5 to the RSU dedicated to tri-lateration positioning solution, in order to locate itself within the tunnel.

Implementation:

The CAV regularly sends its position and detections using CAM and CPM messages, and receives DENM and IVI by the infrastructure upon any road event. While vehicle messages are exchanged only via short range communication (PC5), infrastructure messages are received through 4G via the hybrid communication approach (ETSI message payload exchanged over AMQP). Tri-lateration positioning solution uses ITS-G5.

6.2.3. Communication Features

6.2.3.1. 4G

TIM provides 4G network coverage in the Trento living lab, with access to MEC services, as in UC4, with the difference of having higher access times due to the connectivity technology. As in UC4, messages are exchanged using a AMQP broker.

6.2.3.2. PC5

Known as LTE-V2X PC5 interface, subset of the 3GPP Release 14 specification that defines Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) technology which uses device-to-device communication at 5.9 GHz band without requiring the presence of a base station. In UC4 and UC5 it is referred as “short range”.

6.2.3.3. Hybrid Communication

Hybrid communication is used since messages from CAVs might arrive to the MEC from short range interfaces and 5G, as explained correspondingly in RSU functional view. It also allows CAV and other CVs to communicate cooperatively.

Purpose:

In real scenarios, usually the redundancy in communications is useful to offer enough coverage for connected vehicles and that no messages are missing. The implementation of redundant paths for messages up to the point of consumption is important.

Implementation:

In UC5 hybrid communication is done through the routing functions of the RSU and the dual interfaces (4G and short range) in the OBU. Both paths are always available, so messages might arrive to the edge services twice, but the fusion functionality benefits of having one message coming from short range interface (hence declaring that the vehicle is perceived by the RSU) and another one directly via 4G.

6.3. Connected Entities

This chapter covers all developments related to entities that interact at road level with PoDIUM platform services in UC5.

6.3.1. Connected and Automated Vehicles

To achieve UC5, the on-board systems of the Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) and the support Connected Vehicle (CV) have been developed. The CV implements a subset of functionalities of the

CAV. Therefore, this report focusses on the CAV, which is also the target CAV experienced by the Italian Living Lab Users.

6.3.1.1. Functional view

This section reports the functional view within CAV.

Figure 129: CAV functional view for UC5

With respect to the legacy implementation PoDIUM developments focus on:

- C-ITS message handling
- Localization/Positioning
- Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map
- Cooperative applications
- HMI

The functions are explained hereafter.

Localization/Positioning function calculates the absolute position of the vehicle with respect to the Earth coordinate system, getting signals from several sources. The Localization/Positioning output is provided to the C-ITS message handling function and to the Local Dynamic Map.

This function includes the following sub-functions:

GNSS receiver calculates position from

- signals from Satellites (outside the tunnel),
- signals from the Software Defined radio (inside the tunnel) as artificial Satellites signals
- RTK correction data from public cloud services (e.g. Italian “Catasto” public service)
- vehicle odometry data from vehicle motion

Trilateration-based positioning calculates position from

- signals from V2X relative positioning system, roadside units within the tunnel
- vehicle odometry data from vehicle motion

- other relative data from local dynamic map

Positioning manager gets position from the available sources (GNSS receiver, Relative localization), and provides data to the Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map and to the C-ITS message handling.

C-ITS message handling is the functionality enabling standard V2X data exchange, and the connection with Podium platform. This functionality encodes the standard V2X messages to send, it decodes the standard V2X messages received and it performs simple message processing functions, in order to deliver relevant data payload (objects, road events, etc.) to the vehicle’s Local Dynamic Map (LDM). Based on vehicle motion, positioning, timing and perception, it can send and receive CAM, DENM, CPM. It is divided into two subfunctions:

- C-V2X (LTE-PC5) function uses 3GPP Rel.14/15 standard link to broadcast CAM, CPM and receive CAM, CPM, DENM, and IVI from peer nodes (RSU’s, CV’s).
- Uu subfunction uses AMQP standard publish/subscribe protocol to receive messages from the PoDIUM entities.

Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map (LDM) is the new “cooperative perception” thanks to V2X, as an add-on to the legacy perception system based on vehicle sensors. The Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map combines information from multiple sources, and univocally identifies surrounding objects such as neighbour vehicles and roadside units, as well as road events, road signs, traffic lights etc. It gets information from the vehicle perception and from the C-ITS message handling.

Cooperative Applications represent the “new” decision-making/planning features on top of the legacy ADF planning ones. Based on information from LDM and vehicle motion, Cooperative applications enable:

- **“Warning”**: give warnings and recommendations to the driver
- **“L1 V2X”**: prompt the driver for new ACC target speed based on C-ITS and ADF
- **“C-ACC”**: perform longitudinal control is kept by means of standard sensors and CAM
- **“ODD”**: computation of allowed SAE Levels (up to L4) and preventive ODD exits information

It should be noted here that the developed cooperative applications foresee the interaction with the driver, due to the prototype implementation and related safety risks of influencing Automated Driving Functions based on V2X information.

HMI is specifically developed for PoDIUM, to show the driving scene with remote vehicles, oncoming events, other preventive safety and ODD information/application state, suggestions. It also monitors what is happening in the current use cases and has information about the key performance indicators (e.g. positioning accuracy and outage).

6.3.1.2. Sequence view between functional components

This section shows the message sequences between functional components at CAV, for the main functionalities within the vehicle.

1. **Message exchange with Podium platform: CAM, CPM, DENM**

The following sequence diagrams show the transmission and reception of Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAM), and the reception of messages including CAM, Collective Perception Messages (CPM) and Decentralized Notifications Messages (DENM).

Transmission

Figure 130: C-ITS messages transmission

Reception

Figure 131: C-ITS messages reception

2. Positioning/Localization of the ego-vehicle and remote objects

The following sequence diagrams show how input signals from different sources are used to localize the host vehicle (3 ego-vehicle positioning solutions).

Positioning of the ego-vehicle in open sky

Figure 132: Positioning in open sky (GNSS+RTK)

Positioning of the ego-vehicle in tunnel, solution 1

Figure 133: Positioning in tunnel using RF signals from Software Defined Radio positioning system

Positioning of the ego-vehicle in tunnel, solution 2

Figure 134: Positioning in tunnel using RSU trilateration-based system

The following sequence diagram shows that positioning information on the ego-vehicle and of remote vehicles are used by the data fusion and local dynamic map functionality to obtain the relative position of obstacles around the vehicle, to be used by cooperative applications.

Usage of position information by cooperative applications through Data fusion and LDM

Figure 135: Positioning information for the cooperative applications

3. Assisted/Automated Driving functions

Automated driving functions based on cooperative perception

This sequence diagram shows how cooperative perception data (based on remote vehicles, events, etc.) is used by cooperative applications to influence the Automated Driving plans, mediated by the HMI in the loop (for safety reasons).

Figure 136: General scheme of automated driving functions based on cooperative applications

6.3.1.3. IT environment view

This view presents software and hardware of the in-vehicle prototype. Highlights are:

- C-ITS message handling is based on hybrid communication unit, with own PC5 modem and connected to an LTE modem. The LTE modem serves internet connections to other services (e.g. RTK correction service)
- Positioning/localization functional block is managed by the PoDIUM PC which is connected to two receivers: GNSS receiver for GNSS and SDR signals, ITS-G5 for Vehicle-RSU trilateration-based positioning
- The software processing V2X information for AD in this prototype is detached (in a “PoDIUM PC”) from the legacy AD functionalities, for safety reasons. In a future product there would be most likely a higher degree of integration with the ADF

Figure 137: IT environment view

6.3.1.4. Cooperative Awareness HMI concept

This view shows the information displayed to the end-user to show use case 5 on the CAV. The graphical layout is not represented as it is not ultimate, but this view is sufficient to represent the contents/data that are display and the purpose.

Figure 138: HMI concept view

For UC5 we have the following information to display in the living lab

- Driving scene with vehicles and other objects detected
- Hazard/event Warning
- Additional information: text, recommendations, requests to the drivers
- AD/ADAS related information: SAE automation level, ACC and C-ACC related information
- KPI-related information on V2X and positioning (latency, position outage)
- Diagnostics

6.3.1.5. State of development

With reference to the CAV functional view diagram in Figure 129, the software components development status is as follows:

- UC5 CAV and CV prototypes for the Trento Living lab is available with all hardware needed.
- Localization/Positioning is available using an existing GNSS solution, GNSS is enough for SDR-based in tunnel, with RTK correction outside the tunnel and vehicle data interface for lane localization and dead reckoning. As future activities are the integration of 802.11p trilateration positioning solution and the usage of an alternative GNSS receiver.
- C-ITS message handling is available as CAM, DENM, IVIM functionalities and interface with the other in-vehicle modules (CAN network input/output). The CPM will be available in future releases. Preliminary implementation is available from previous project 5G-CARMEN using “virtual CAM” instead of CPM.

- Data fusion and Local Dynamic Map module is partially available and will be completed in the next releases (CPM and extended perception).
- Cooperative applications are developed for Scenarios 1.1 "RWW single vehicle" and "Sc. 1.2: RWW and C-ACC follow". The remaining scenarios will be developed in the future releases.
- HMI module has been development for the aforementioned scenarios. Its development follows the timeline of Cooperative applications.

6.3.2. Connected Roadside Entities

In the context of connected and autonomous driving systems, the precise calculation of one's position plays a fundamental role. Without the ability to accurately determine one's position, all the information received from autonomous driving systems cannot be used effectively as there are underlying distance calculations of approximate dangers which leads to incorrect risk assessments and perceptions.

When it comes to navigation and tracking within tunnels, the Global Positioning System (GPS) encounters unique challenges. The presence of tunnels introduces various obstacles that may compromise the accuracy and dependability of GPS positioning, leading to potential adverse effects.

Obstacles:

- Signal Blockage: tunnels, by their nature, restrict the line of sight between GPS receivers and satellites. This obstruction can result in signal blockage or multipath interference.
- Reflection and Absorption: The reflective surfaces within tunnels can cause signals to bounce off walls, creating multiple signal paths. Additionally, certain construction materials can absorb GPS signals, further complicating accurate positioning.
- Satellite Visibility: The number of visible satellites is reduced in tunnels, limiting the availability of signals for triangulation.

Consequences:

- Position Drift: the GPS system struggles to provide a stable and accurate location.
- Signal Dropout: GPS signal may be completely lost within tunnels, resulting in a temporary dropout of the navigation system.
- Impact on Safety Systems: inaccuracies in tunnel environments can have serious consequences, potentially impacting safety and operational effectiveness.

To tackle this issue within the ongoing UC5 scenario, two parallel and independent strategies are being implemented to address the challenges associated with determining precise positions in a tunnel. The first strategy involves utilizing software-defined GPS radio technology. Simultaneously, a position triangulation system based on Cohda antennas, originally employed in the C-ITS legacy system, is being deployed as the second strategy.

6.3.2.1. Software-defined GPS radio technology

SDR-based positioning refers to a technology that utilizes Software-Defined Radio, for determining the location of devices or objects. SDR enables the processing of radio signals through software, allowing for dynamic adaptability and customization.

The system is based on 3 fundamental pillars as shown in Figure 139:

- Software-Defined Radio (SDR): SDR replaces traditional hardware components with software, providing flexibility in signal processing. It allows for the modification of signal characteristics and protocols without altering the underlying hardware.
- Antenna Arrays: Multiple antennas are employed to receive signals from various sources, contributing to enhanced accuracy and reliability in positioning.

- Signal Processing Algorithms: Advanced algorithms process the received radio signals to extract relevant information for positioning. [Time of arrival (TOA), time difference of arrival (TDOA), or received signal strength (RSS) measurements].

The main advantages of such a solution are:

- Flexibility and Adaptability: it can adapt to different signal environments and standards.
- Improved Accuracy: By employing multiple antennas and sophisticated signal processing techniques, SDR-based positioning systems can achieve higher accuracy compared to traditional methods.
- Cost Efficiency: SDR eliminates the need for dedicated hardware for different communication standards.

The main drawback of this solution is its complexity: it requires expertise in both radio signal processing and software development.

Furthermore, its installation had posed technical and technological obstacles, as well as strong impacts on traffic. In order to install this infrastructure, it was necessary to provide temporary closures of the tunnel and therefore the impacts on motorway traffic had to be assessed.

Figure 139: Simplified representation of the arrangement of the SDR along the tunnel

6.3.2.2. Trilateration Positioning System

Trilateration is a technique used in positioning systems to determine the location of a point in space by measuring its distance from known points, as shown in Figure 140. In a trilateration positioning system, the position of an object is calculated based on the distances to at least three reference points. Trilateration is used for indoor positioning, especially in environments where GPS signals may be weak or unavailable, as it is in our UC5 scenario, a tunnel.

The system is based on 3 fundamental pillars:

- Reference Points: Also known as anchors or beacons, these are fixed points with known coordinates. They are equipped with devices that can communicate with the target device and measure signal travel time or signal strength.

- **Target Device:** The object or device for which the position is to be determined. It needs to be equipped with the capability to communicate with the reference points and measure the signal characteristics.
- **Distance Measurement:** Trilateration relies on accurate distance measurements between the target device and each of the reference points. [Time of flight (TOF) or received signal strength (RSS)].

The drawbacks of this solution are:

- **Signal Interference:** Signal interference or obstacles between the target and reference points can impact the accuracy of distance measurements.
- **Multipath Effects:** Reflections or signal bouncing off surfaces can introduce errors in distance calculations.
- **Line of Sight Requirements:** For accurate measurements, trilateration often requires a clear line of sight between the target device and reference points.
- **Target Device:** The object or device for which the position is to be determined. It needs to be equipped with the capability to communicate with the reference points and measure the signal characteristics.

Figure 140: Simplified representation of the arrangement of the trilateration system

For trilateration, we depended on proprietary software developed by the RSU supplier of the existing C-ITS system, which is Cohda Wireless. Through collaborative efforts, optimal locations for installing the equipment inside the tunnel were identified, ensuring the highest possible precision for this system.

Due to the specific characteristics of the tunnel, such as its shape, safety considerations, and width, there were significant constraints on potential sites for antenna installation. The chosen arrangement offers excellent accuracy in terms of longitude; however, there are some limitations in terms of latitude accuracy.

6.3.2.3. Roadside Units and Sensor Processing Units

6.3.2.3.1. Functional view

Figure 141 depicts the functionality of the RSU/SPU highlighting the functionality developed for PoDIUM. As for UC4, the RSU is also an SPU, it has functionality corresponding to RSUs, such as messaging, communication, and C-ITS routing functionality; it has also SPU functionality such as perception and sensing functions for cameras and LiDARs. The difference with respect to UC4

RSU/SPUs is the absence of the Trust Platform Agent and the Remote Attestation functionality, which belongs only to UC4.

Figure 141: RSU functionality for UC5

For the rest of the functionality, please refer to section 5.2.2.2 (Roadside Unit (RSU)).

6.3.2.3.2. IT Environment view

Following Figure 142, the RSU can be deployed with the following components: a main computing board, running most of the functionality in containers, and the networking functions on another dedicated hardware, with all interfaces attached. An ethernet switch connects these two hardware components with the Camera and LIDAR sensors.

Figure 142: UC5 RSU IT environment view

6.3.2.3.3. Location

The partners have defined the tunnel managed by BRE and it has been decided to place two RSU/SPUs at both ends of the A22 tunnel in the neighbourhood of Piedicastello (see Figure 143). The exact place must still be defined, considering the availability of fixed infrastructure and the image setup for orientation. Both RSUs will be looking in the same direction to allow the objects to be seen from the same perspective at the entrance and exit. This would also constrain the number of cameras placed.

Figure 143: RSU location for UC5

6.3.2.3.4. State of development

The current state of the component development is the following:

- Msg Output: ready for deployment.
- Short Range: Initially will be working with ITS-G5 for first tests. PC5 interfaces not yet installed or configured.
- C-ITS Router: ready for deployment.
- Installation still to be planned.

Currently perception development status:

CPM generation working, and DENM generation working, pending configuration for tests. Fusion between both sensors is at 80%.

6.4. Services and Data Exchange

6.4.1. Functional components

The functionality required for services in UC5 are mostly similar (see Figure 144), with the exceptions that VRUs are not managed and that the application using the digital twin information is different.

Figure 144: UC5 Functional View

Digital Twin

Digital Twin acts as an aggregator of the information retrieved from all the different sources. It receives data from all the possible data sources in the scenario and merges them in a simple to access way. The Digital Twin is composed by a series of different submodule, including:

- **CCAM Broker:** a Message Broker, implementing the pub/sub approach. It has also in charge the access management after interacting with the Attestor in the trust scenario. In that case CCAM Broker releases the credentials and maintains them during the amount of attestation periods that the CAV OBU is under MEC coverage.
- **Encode Decode:** This functionality handles the encoding and decoding of the C-ITS messages; CCAM broker uses this functionality to generate/consume messages into the Digital Twin.
- **Data Fusion:** this module reads information published in the DT and detects if multiple sensors perceived the same object; in this case, associates to that object the merged information from all the sources.
- **Truthfulness module:** this module associates to each detected road actor a truthfulness value based on how many different sources detected the presence of the object and the reliability of each one of them.
- **A database:** this database contains all the information available on the road status, already merged and valued by the other modules of the Digital Twin.
- **REST API:** a REST server providing access to the data elaborated inside the Digital Twin.

RMT

The Risk Management in Tunnel module receives as input the positions of all the road users detected,

with their speed and heading (if available) and also optional additional information (e.g., dangerous payload or special merch) from the Digital Twin of the road.

Then, this module then will:

- Compute the risk of the travel inside the tunnel (e.g., too many vehicles in the tunnel);
- Send warning to vehicles inside the tunnel and/or approaching the tunnel, using messages sent to the CCAM Broker.

6.4.2. Data Flow and Storage

6.4.2.1. General view of the exchange of information

This section illustrates the data exchange between components for Use Case 5 scenarios. Overall, the data flow consists in event notifications sent by the infrastructure (DENM) to inform CAV and CV about the road event (road works, traffic, etc.) along with related dynamic signage (IVIM) if applicable. In the case of traffic, vehicles’ CPM and CAM collected by the roadside units, as well as roadside sensors data, are combined with road operator’s source information to issue high quality Traffic Jam Alert DENM. On the vehicle side, DENM and IVIM are received and filtered according to relevance. CAM are exchanged between CAV and CV and used for assessing car following and cut-in situations, while CPM strengthen the CAV perception, enabling SAE L4. Not depicted in the sequence diagram, but mentioned before in the CAV description, is the key role of positioning data which in Podium is enhanced with in-tunnel positioning signal and enables the self-localization of CAV and CV as well as the V2X time sync outside and inside the tunnel.

Road Works Warning with CAV only

In this scenario, DENM corresponding to Road Works Warning and IVIM corresponding to the speed limits before the construction site, are published by the road operator (C-ITS-S) onto the CCAM Broker (AMQP server). These messages are consumed by the AMQP client of the CAV on board unit. A relevance filter applied to the message content, checks whether the CAV is headed towards the signs and the road event or not. If the messages are relevant for the CAV, the application performs the RWW scenario.

Figure 145: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning – CAV only: sequence diagram

Road Works Warning with Cooperative ACC – car follow.

In this scenario, both CAV and CV approach the RWW on the lane which is closed due to the

construction site. Therefore, both vehicles need to change lanes. The CAV is following the CV cruise speed by means of the cooperative ACC function. The exchange of RWW DENM and IVI-DSL I between the infrastructure and each one of the vehicles (CAV and CV) follows the same sequence as “RWW with CAV only”. The exchange of CAM through direct communication, in particular the periodic reception of CV CAM by the CAV (1-10Hz, per ETSI standard), enables the C-ACC car follow functionality whenever the CV and CAV are on the same lane (this is determined at the CAV receiving CV position and heading in the CAM). In the C-ACC, the speed of CV (included in CAM) is set as the new target speed of the CAV. When the CV first performs the lane change (due to roadworks), then the C-ACC is disengaged at CAV. When the CAV performs the lane change, too, the C-ACC is available again, and engaged upon driver confirmation (note: the following sequence diagram shows just the engagement, while the driver confirmation was previously shown in the activity diagram).

Figure 146: UC5 Scenario “car follow” with C-ACC (at Road Works): Sequence Diagram

Road Works Warning with Cooperative ACC – cut-in.

In this scenario both CAV and CV approach the RWW, but the CAV is running on the open lane, whereas the CV is initially on the lane that, farther ahead, is closed due to the construction site. Thus, the CV needs to merge. The intention to merge is communicated from CV to CAV through the CAM (turn indicator of the CV “on”) which is exchanged via direct link. The CAV, upon receiving the indication, slows down to ease the lane change manoeuvre of the CV. Afterwards, being CV and CAV on the same lane (the one that passes through the construction site) the C-ACC car follow functionality can be activated at the CAV, similarly to the previous scenario.

Figure 147: UC5 Scenario: “cut-in” with C-ACC: Sequence Diagram

Traffic Jam Alert with take-over

This scenario is of particular interest for the data exchange. As the sequence diagram shows, the original Traffic Jam notification by the road operator (i.e. legacy system) is published onto the C-CAM broker and in this way received then by the Digital Twin which is subscribed to the service. This holds in general for other risky events identified by the road operator, and named “source DENM” in the

sequence diagram. In parallel, roadside units (RSU’s), through vehicle counting sensors (specific Podium system) detect vehicles passing through the tunnel. Said RSU’s collect also CAM and CPM from vehicles (in Podium: CAV and CV prototypes). The combination of CAM, CPM and sensed vehicles yields a perception message which is called “RSU_CPM”. This RSU_CPM is sent by the RSU to the Digital Twin via the CCAM broker. The Digital Twin, in turn, combines the RSU_CPM with the aforementioned “source DENM” and provides a more fine-grained traffic condition to the Risk Management module. The latter performs a risk assessment and, if a threshold is passed, issues a TJA DENM with higher quality (“refined DENM”), which is published on the broker and thus received by the CAV. In this scenario the CAV, after a relevance check with positive result, requests the driver to take over.

Figure 148: UC5 Scenario Traffic Jam Alert with take-over: Sequence Diagram

Traffic Jam Alert with ODD information

This scenario adds the cooperation between vehicles to the former Traffic Jam Alert scenario. The CAV on board system periodically receives CAM and CPM from the CV. Combining these messages with on board sensors, the CAV itself can determine whether it is currently following a CV that has collective perception mode, with no other vehicles in the middle. This condition corresponds to “extended perception mode” and is one of the necessary conditions to enable L4 ODD. If L4 is active, the CAV system can handle the traffic jam situation its own (thus the received TJA alert does not cause a take-over request) and slow down automatically. Instead, the cut-in of a non-equipped vehicle will cause an ODD exit, as one of the conditions for L4 automation is no longer in place. This condition will eventually lead to a take-over request generated by the TJA, similar to the previous scenario “Traffic Jam Alert with take-over”.

Figure 149: UC5 Scenarios of “L4 ODD keep” and “L4 ODD exit” (with Traffic Jam Alert): Sequence Diagram

6.4.2.2. Message exchange

The considerations made in section 5.4.2.2 in UC4 hold also for UC5.

6.4.2.3. Semantic interoperability aspects

A highlight of vehicle-infrastructure semantic interoperability in UC5, is the usage of information quality in the DENM. In the scenario 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 for example, the Risk Management in Tunnel component (RMT) – through the Digital Twin - combines an original Hazardous Location Notification – Traffic Jam Alert (HLN-TJA) by the A22 with additional information from sensor counters and vehicles (floating car data from collected CAM and CPM) to issue a refined HLN-TJA DENM. The incoming road users – e.g. the CAV – needs to prioritize the latter TJA with respect to the original one. To achieve this prioritization, the following DENM Data Element was chosen:

InformationQuality ::= INTEGER {unavailable(0), lowest(1), highest(7)} (0..7)

This is the defined as the Quality level of provided information by the ETSI Common Data Dictionary [42]. From ETSI Decentralized Notification Message Part 3 [35], quality indicates the probability of the detected event being truly existent at the event position.

The C-ROADS platform recommends that information validated by the Traffic Control Centre be set to a quality of 4, and considers quality <4 as information to be discarded by the receiver. Therefore, A22

issues TJA-RWW with quality = 0. In PoDIUM, the RMT can potentially raise the quality of the original message to a level=5. Quality =6 has been excluded, because this value corresponds to a source completely *certain of the occurrence of the situation or event*, and refers to *recent human verification of a detected event by a qualified person who belongs to the same organisation as the source or originator of the ITS message (e.g. road operator or operator of ITS stations)*. *Human verification can be provided by a qualified person who is on-site or observes the event via CCTV*. Therefore, the current system is not suitable, yet, to issue quality warning >5, as the risk management feature is not integrated into the operator system and verification processes.

Even so, the two levels (level=4 original DENM by A22, level=5 refined DENM by the RMT) are sufficient for the receiving CAV to distinguish prioritize the two different warnings that are referred to the same event.

7. Conclusions

In this document, we have described the architecture design developed within the PoDIUM project based on the requirements derived in previous deliverables, especially D3.1 [1]. It builds upon existing standards and approaches from previous projects, extending them, if necessary, to include the contributions of PoDIUM in the field of CCAM, especially:

Each use case was described in detail, with variations described as scenarios. Each scenario was provided with a sequence diagram, outlining the individual steps which have to be realised for a successful use case execution.

For each use case, the communication aspects were detailed. Hereby, the UC's relationship to the general PoDIUM architecture as presented in deliverable D3.1 was presented. Then, all involved communication entities – including CAVs, RSUs, SPUs, VRUs, EVs, MECs, CLOUDS – and their functionalities were explained. For each connected entity, the respective functional and IT environment view were outlined. For some connected entities and use cases, more specific aspects such as multi-connectivity or cooperative awareness HMI were additionally explained. The used communication features were 5G-cm-Wave, 5G-mm-Wave, ITS-G5, C-V2X (LTE-PC5), 60-GHz-Wifi, multi-connectivity, and hybrid communications were introduced.

Services and data exchange was also presented for each UC. The functional components are rather use case specific. Examples for functional components were digital twins, collision risk detectors, ITS message handling, manoeuvre planning, cooperative awareness, traffic management, the operation of emergency vehicles, and cross-border handling. Sequence diagrams of C-ITS message (data) exchange were showcased.

Software integrity refers to the quality of the software, and is a measure of how safe, secure, and reliable it is. Software integrity was implemented in UC4, covering a Remote Attestor, the entity responsible for challenging and verifying the trustworthiness of a remote device referred to be a Trusted Computing Base. Especially for the Digital Twin services, the reliability of its output and, in a direct consequence, the reliability of the information received to be fused into the DT is crucial. UC1 presented a general approach to check the data truthfulness before the data is incorporated in the digital twin.

In the next step, based on this deliverable, the final status for each use case and its implementation will be covered in deliverable D3.3.

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